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Executive Summary

In order to facilitate knowledge exchange among relevant stakeholders within the European broiler sector, a database was established containing both scientific and grey literature. This file summarizes a selection of interesting knowledge sources (both scientific and practice-based knowledge) related to all Sector Priority Challenges of BroilerNet WP 3 "Animal welfare". It contains, among others, scientific research and review papers, practical guidelines, project reports, and industry reports. In total the database includes 180 references. We describe how this knowledge database was developed (**Chapter 1**), list a maximum of 10 scientific literature sources and 10 grey-literature sources per challenge (**Chapter 2-10**), and provide an informative abstract/summary for each source (**Chapter 2-10**). This knowledge database file belongs to Deliverable 3.3 'Finalizing the database including both literature and practice-based knowledge in animal welfare'.

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Chapter 1 Introduction into the database

1.1 Description of the knowledge database content

In order to facilitate knowledge exchange among relevant stakeholders within the European broiler sector, a database was established containing both scientific and grey literature. The database consists of, among others, scientific research and review papers, practical guidelines, project reports, and industry reports. Those sources relate to all BroilerNet Sector Priority Challenges for animal welfare and can contain knowledge about broiler welfare and examples of potential good practices. The Sector Priority Challenges were identified by the National Level BroilerNet Innovation Network (BIN) groups of each participating country. In addition, the BINs proposed Good Practices (GP) as innovative best practice solutions to the identified challenges. Those GPs were evaluated by the Thematic Expert Network (TEN) with the use of the Good Practice Evaluation Tool (GPET). This evaluation resulted in a Top 5 of Best Practices (BP) based on the technical quality, impact, and probability of success of a GP. Additional information on the BroilerNet challenges can be found in the [Thematic Reports](#).

1.2 Development of the database

For each challenge, both scientific and practice-based knowledge were collected. To this end, Web of Science and Google Scholar were used to search for scientific literature, and search engine Google was used to search for grey literature. Only those sources with full text available and English or German language were selected. Other exclusion criteria were relevance, sources published prior to 2010, and publications about backyard production systems. In total the database includes 180 references. This is a selection made by the work package leaders based on relevance and novelty.

1.3 Usage of the database

For the purpose of simple and quick searching, sources are listed per Sector Priority Challenge for Animal Welfare (i.e. **Chapter 2-10**) of all BroilerNet cycles. By these means, the end user can select its topic of interest within the database. For Sector Priority Challenge, a maximum of 10 scientific literature sources and 10 grey-literature sources are listed. Informative abstracts/summaries are provided for each source as well. By these means, the end user can find the most important information directly inside the database. Nevertheless, a digital object identifier/website link to the original source can be accessed by clicking the title of the abstract/summary. The user can jump through the file using "ctrl" and clicking the link.

Chapter 2 Farming training

2.1 List of scientific knowledge sources

1. Factors that Influence Farmers' Views on Farm Animal Welfare: A Semi-Systematic Review and Thematic Analysis

Balzani, A.; Hanlon, A. 2020. *Animals*, 10(9), 1524. DOI: [10.3390/ani10091524](https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10091524)

[ABSTRACT](#)

2. A comparison of online and live training of livestock farmers for an on-farm self-assessment of animal welfare

Michaelis, S.; Schubbert, A.; Gieseke, D.; Cimer, K.; Zapf, R.; Lühken, S.; March, S.; Brinkmann, J.; Schultheiß, U.; Knierim, U. 2023. *Front.anim.sci.*, 3, 1102029. DOI: [10.3389/fanim.2022.1102029](https://doi.org/10.3389/fanim.2022.1102029)

[ABSTRACT](#)

3. Use of "demonstration farm" videos to affect attitude change toward animal welfare on beef, egg, and fish farms in China

Yang, Y.; Liu, T.; Nilsson, D.; Hartcher, K.; Shih, H.; Wu, Z.; Liu, Z.; Sinclair, M.; Samayoa, X.; Henning, K.; Descovich, K. 2023. *Outlook on Agriculture*, 52(4), 399-410. DOI: [10.1177/00307270231173137](https://doi.org/10.1177/00307270231173137)

[ABSTRACT](#)

4. Tools for on-farm self-assessment of animal welfare

Schultheiß, U.; Zapf, R.; Brinkmann, J.; Cimer, K.; March, S.; Schrader, L.; Schubbert, A.; Lühken, S.; Gieseke, D.; Michaelis, S.; Knierim, U. 2023. *Landtechnik*, 78(3), 114-123. DOI: [10.1515/LT.2023.3293](https://doi.org/10.1515/LT.2023.3293)

[ABSTRACT](#)

5. Training to improve stockperson beliefs and behaviour towards livestock enhances welfare and productivity

Coleman, G. J.; Hemsworth, P. H. 2014. *Rev. Sci. Tech*, 33(1), 131-137. DOI: [10.20506/rst.33.1.2257](https://doi.org/10.20506/rst.33.1.2257)

[ABSTRACT](#)

6. Interactive methods to educate and engage poultry producers on the importance of practicing on-farm biosecurity

Julien, D.; Thomson, S. 2011. *J. Agric. Ext. Rur. Dev*, 3(8), 137-140. <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:110134273>

[ABSTRACT](#)

7. Appropriate data visualisation is key to Precision Livestock Farming acceptance

van Hertem, T.; Rooijackers, L.; Berckmans, D.; Peña Fernández, A.; Norton, T.; Vranken, E. 2017. *Comput. Electron. agr.*, 138, 1-10. DOI: [10.1016/j.compag.2017.04.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2017.04.003)

[ABSTRACT](#)

8. Danish stable schools for experiential common learning in groups of organic dairy farmers

Vaarst, M.; Nissen, T. B.; Østergaard, S.; Klaas, I. C.; Bennedsgaard, T. W.; Christensen, J. 2007. *J.D.S.*, 90(5), 2543-2554. DOI: [10.3168/jds.2006-607](https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2006-607)

[ABSTRACT](#)

9. Transferring results of behavioral research to industry to improve animal welfare on the farm, ranch and the slaughter plant

Grandin, T. 2003. *Appl. Anim. Beh. Sci.* 81(3), 215-228. DOI: [10.1016/S0168-1591\(02\)00282-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591(02)00282-4)

[ABSTRACT](#)

10. Assessing the Impact of On-Farm Biosecurity Coaching on Farmer Perception and Farm Biosecurity Status in Belgian Poultry Production

Amalraj, A., Van Meirhaeghe, H., Chantziaras, I., Dewulf, J. 2024. *Animals*, 14(17), 2498. DOI: [10.3390/ani14172498](https://doi.org/10.3390/ani14172498)

[ABSTRACT](#)

2.2 Informative abstracts

1. **Factors that Influence Farmers' Views on Farm Animal Welfare: A Semi-Systematic Review and Thematic Analysis**

Farm animal welfare (FAW) is a growing societal concern, reflected by over 30 years of research to inform policy and practice. Despite the wealth of evidence to improve FAW, implementation of good practice continues to be an issue. The role of the stakeholder, particularly farmers, is pivotal to FAW improvement. This semi-systematic review synthesizes the evidence published in the last 30 years, worldwide, to address two main questions "what do farmers think (farmer's general view) about farm animal welfare?" and "what are the factors that influence their thinking?". A thematic analysis was conducted to identify factors that influenced the implementation of FAW innovation. The main outcomes extracted from 96 peer-reviewed publications on a range of livestock species identified 11 internal factors including farmer knowledge, empathy, personality, values, and human-animal bond; 15 external factors including economic advantages, communication, time and labor influenced the perception of FAW. Farmers' knowledge and cost implications of FAW were the most frequently reported factors. The review further highlights the need for promoting interdisciplinary collaboration and stakeholder participation. This study suggests strategies to improve FAW, including tools to support behavioral changes amongst farmers.

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2. **A comparison of online and live training of livestock farmers for an on-farm self-assessment of animal welfare**

One approach to strengthening the involvement of farmers or stockpersons in the evaluation and improvement of animal welfare is the implementation of an on-farm self-assessment. A valid comparison of the results with reference values, between or within farms, requires that training of the farmers and reliability testing have taken place. We investigated two different training methods (online vs. live) with a total of 146 livestock farmers from farms with dairy cows and calves, beef cattle, sows and suckling piglets, weaners and fattening pigs, laying hens, broiler chickens, and turkeys from all over Germany. Online tests were conducted by assessing photos/videos of each indicator of the assessment scheme to estimate the inter-

rater reliability (prevalence adjusted and bias-adjusted kappa, PABAK). The farmers were requested to provide information on their professional background and rate their motivation to participate in the training and their subjective training success, meaning their confidence in assessing each indicator later on-farm. They evaluated the feasibility of the training and its impact on their views and attitudes. In general, farmers achieved at least substantial inter-rater reliability (PABAK ≥ 0.61) in 86.8% of all initial tests; 13.4% of the tests were repeated once or more times, resulting in a significant improvement of the agreement, with 90.9% of the tests reaching a PABAK ≥ 0.61 . However, reliability was higher for indicators with a lower number of score levels. The subjective evaluation of training success was, on average, positive (score = 74.8 out of 100). No effects of the training method or the farmers' professional background on the inter-rater reliability or the subjective training success were detected. Furthermore, for both methods, farmers moderately agreed that the training had sharpened their views on the animals, encouraged them to implement the assessment on their farm, and made it clear that self-as on the assessment of animal-based indicators assessment supports animal management. Although the reported costs and time investment for the online training were significantly lower, the effort required for both methods and the ease of integration into the workflow were ranked as similarly acceptable. Overall, both training methods appear feasible for the training of farmers/stockpersons.

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3. Use of "demonstration farm" videos to affect attitude change toward animal welfare on beef, egg, and fish farms in China

"Demonstration farms" can disseminate knowledge on farming practices and help to promote animal welfare. When on-farm visits are impractical, remote demonstrations are a feasible alternative. This study used videos of higher welfare beef, fish and free-range egg farms in China. It aimed to determine whether the videos affected attitudes and intentions toward animal welfare and whether such videos are useful training tools. Participants indicated a high acceptability of demonstration farm videos for learning about their industry and the needs of animals. Videos shifted participant attitudes toward animal welfare, but only when actively engaged in rating the farm on specific characteristics. Attitude changes suggested participants gained a greater understanding of animal welfare, a greater intention to improve on-farm welfare, and more confidence in peer support for welfare innovations after viewing the video. The findings indicate videos of demonstration farms are useful for remote training but passive viewing may be insufficient to create change, and outcomes should be monitored for success.

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4. Tools for on-farm self-assessment of animal welfare

Livestock farmers are required to monitor the welfare of their animals regularly and systematically by collecting animal protection indicators within the framework of on-farm self-assessment (German Animal Welfare Act § 11 (8)). They can thus identify potential animal welfare problems at an early stage and initiate remedial measures accordingly. To ensure comparability of on-farm self-assessment, animal welfare indicators must be collected in a standardised way. The aim of this work was to test the feasibility of the indicators for cattle, pigs and poultry which had been proposed for on-farm self-assessments in a previous process. To train livestock farmers on how to apply the indicators, live and online trainings were developed and tested. Data recording sheets and an Excel® application were created to facilitate data collection in the stable. Furthermore, numerous experts jointly developed and agreed on a reference evaluation framework in a multi-stage process (Delphi survey, literature review, expert panels, field studies). The framework includes target and alarm values which livestock farmers can use to compare and evaluate their results. Finally, all tools were evaluated in interviews.

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5. Training to improve stockperson beliefs and behaviour towards livestock enhances welfare and productivity

The principle that supervising and managing animals affects farm animal welfare is widely recognised within the livestock industries. However, the manner in which the stockperson affects animal welfare, both directly and indirectly, is probably not fully appreciated. Together with the opportunity to perform their tasks well, stockpeople require a range of well-developed husbandry skills and knowledge to effectively care for and manage farm animals. There are three main factors that can be considered to contribute to a stockperson's work performance: capacity, willingness and opportunity. Capacity includes variables such as skills, health, ability and knowledge, while willingness includes motivation, job satisfaction, attitude to the animals and work attitude, and opportunity includes working conditions, actions of co-workers and organisational policies and rules. This paper briefly reviews the influence of the stockperson on livestock welfare and productivity and the opportunities to improve the stockperson's performance through training. It is clear that there is a continuing need for livestock industries to train their personnel to effectively care for and handle their stock. Underestimating the role and impact of the stockperson will seriously risk the welfare and productivity of livestock. Indeed, the stockperson may be the most influential factor affecting animal handling, welfare and productivity. Furthermore, it is likely that, in the near future, both the livestock industries and the general community will place an increasing emphasis on ensuring the competency of stockpeople to manage the welfare of livestock.

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6. Interactive methods to educate and engage poultry producers on the importance of practicing on-farm biosecurity

Biosecurity is the key within the poultry industry in preventing the spread of diseases and infections. A "biosecurity culture" is needed to increase the adoption of farm biosecurity practices because financial incentives are not always apparent. The objective of this project was to provide innovative and participatory education and extension to industry leaders that would enable them to act as "biosecurity champions" and promote recommended practices sparking a "biosecurity culture". By using Glogerm™, a luminescent product (under UV light) in this project was able to visually and immediately demonstrate the effectiveness and importance of inexpensive, but yet effective biosecurity practices.

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7. Appropriate data visualisation is key to Precision Livestock Farming acceptance

Most farmers do not have the skills and time to utilize new Precision Livestock Farming (PLF) technologies effectively. It is time consuming to combine and analyse the data coming from sensors in different formats and frequencies. As part of the EU-PLF project, the authors have developed a visualisation tool to bring together and analyse the scattered data, and present them in an easy to use format to the end user. The correct use of these data might improve animal welfare, and reduce emissions through the application of PLF techniques. Data were collected at five broiler farms and ten pig farms across Europe. At the farms, a number of variables were automatically measured including climate data, production data, environmental data, and data on animal behaviour coming from cameras and microphones. Simultaneously, the welfare of the animals was assessed by trained assessors on a regular basis by using the standardized Welfare Quality protocol. All data were gathered, stored and processed on a daily basis, and visualised on a web-based tool. End-users of the tool were trained on how to interpret the available information on the visualisation tool. This paper presents the development of this PLF data visualisation tool. The farmer's use of this tool and the early warning capabilities are described by six case studies. The selected farmers

participated actively in evaluating its usefulness, resulting in a web-based visualisation tool that is practical and useful for both the farmer and other stakeholders (e.g. vets, advisors, researchers, etc.)

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8. Danish stable schools for experiential common learning in groups of organic dairy farmers

The farmer field school (FFS) is a concept for farmers' learning, knowledge exchange, and empowerment that has been developed and used in developing countries. In Denmark, a research project focusing on explicit non-antibiotic strategies involves farmers who have actively expressed an interest in phasing out antibiotics from their herds through promotion of animal health. One way of reaching this goal was to form participatory focused farmer groups in an FFS approach, which was adapted to Danish conditions and named "stable schools." Four stable schools were established and went through a 1-yr cycle with 2 visits at each of the 5 or 6 farms connected to each group. A facilitator was connected to each group whose role was to write the meeting agenda together with the host farmer, direct the meeting, and write the minutes to send to the group members after the meeting. Through group focus interviews and individual semistructured qualitative interviews of all participants, the approach of the farmers' goal-directed work toward a common goal was judged to be very valuable and fruitful and based on a common learning process. Complex farming situations were the focus of all groups and in this context, problems were identified and solutions proposed based on each farmer's individual goals. In this article, we describe the experiences of 4 stable school groups (each comprising farmers and a facilitator), and the common process of building a concept that is suitable for Danish organic dairy farming.

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9. Transferring results of behavioral research to industry to improve animal welfare on the farm, ranch and the slaughter plant

Knowledge obtained from research has been effectively transferred to the agricultural industry in some areas and poorly transferred in others. Knowledge that has been used to create a product such as a pharmaceutical or a device is more likely to be adopted by industry than a behavioral management technique. During my career, I have observed that some people will purchase a new cattle-handling system, which is designed with animal behavioral principles, but they will continue to handle cattle roughly. People are more willing to purchase new equipment than they are to use easy-to-learn, low-stress handling techniques. Even when financial benefits are clear, some people find it difficult to believe that a behavioral management method really works. From my experience, I have learned that successful transfer of knowledge and technology to industry often requires more work than doing the research. For an effective transfer of technology to take place, the method or equipment must be used successfully by the people who initially adopt it. If the new piece of equipment fails on the first or second place that attempts to adopt it, transfer to the industry may fail. In this paper, I describe a successful case study of transfer of a conveyor restrainer system, based on behavioral principles, from the research lab to US and Canadian beef slaughter plants. I also describe the successful implementation of a measurement system for auditing animal handling in slaughter plants. Based on my experience, the following steps for successful transfer of behavior research to the industry are: (1) Communicate your results outside the research community. Write articles in popular and industry magazines. Speak at producer meetings and develop websites that can be used to transfer research results into practice. (2) Choose places (e.g. farms or plants) that have managers who believe in your research, and be prepared to spend a lot of time with the first place that uses your findings. (3) Closely supervise other early adapters to prevent mistakes which could cause the method or technology to fail. (4) Do not allow your technology to get tied up in patent disputes.

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10. Assessing the Impact of On-Farm Biosecurity Coaching on Farmer Perception and Farm Biosecurity Status in Belgian Poultry Production

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Veterinary coaching was tested to assess its efficacy in promoting adherence to biosecurity procedures. Poultry farmers (n = 13) in Belgium were profiled using ADKAR®, coached and audited prior to and 6 months after coaching. The ADKAR® (Awareness, Desire, Knowledge, Ability, and Reinforcement) profiling technique identified 5/13 participating farmers with relatively low scores (≤ 3) for one or more elements that block change (biosecurity compliance in this case). Education was the only demographic variable that influenced knowledge scores. Through the Biocheck.Ugent™ methodology, farm biosecurity was assessed and benchmarked to allow for tailored guidance. The farmer, farm veterinarian, and coach defined a farm-specific action plan that covered infrastructure, site access, staff/visitors, purchase policies, transport and depopulation, feed and water supplies, flock management, cleaning and disinfection between flocks, and measures between houses. From a total of 49 proposed actions, 36 were adopted. Purchasing policy had the highest (100%) and cleaning and disinfection had the lowest compliance (38%). Time, cost, and feasibility (e.g., inadequate farm layout) were the main reasons cited for not implementing action points. Overall, biosecurity improved significantly ($p = 0.002$) from $67.1 \pm 5.7\%$ to $70.3 \pm 5.7\%$ (mean \pm Std. dev). The study, hence, presents convincing proof of how coaching can lead to new solutions not previously considered.

2.3 List of practical knowledge sources

1. Inspirational idea: A national network stimulating knowledge exchange on animal welfare in Germany

EU CAP Network. 2023. https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/news/inspirational-idea-national-network-stimulating-knowledge-exchange-animal-welfare-germany_en

[SUMMARY](#)

2. Assessing and improving poultry welfare in commercial production systems

Knierim, U.; Jung, L.; Gieseke, D. 2021. Lohmann Information. <https://lohmann-breeders.com/de/lohmanninfo/assessing-and-improving-poultry-welfare-in-commercial-production-systems/>

[SUMMARY](#)

3. Improving Farm Animal Productivity and Welfare, by Increasing Skills and Knowledge of Stock People

Spoolder, H.A.M.; Ruis, M. 2015. International Symposium on Animal Environment and Welfare. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330066108_Improving_Farm_Animal_Productivity_and_Welfare_by_Increasing_Skills_and_Knowledge_of_Stock_People

[SUMMARY](#)

4. GCAW Recommendation on the use of Welfare Outcome Measures for Broiler Chickens

Chapter 2 Farming training

Global Coalition for Animal Welfare. 2023. Broiler Chicken Welfare Working Group. <https://www.gc-animalwelfare.org/2023/01/10/gcaw-publishes-recommendations-for-welfare-outcome-measures-for-broiler-chickens/>

SUMMARY

5. Capacity building to implement good animal welfare practices

Fraser, D.; Kharb, R. M.; McCrindle, C.; Mench, J.; da Costa, M. P.; Promchan, K.; Song, W. et al. 2008. FAO Expert Meeting. <https://www.fao.org/3/i0483e/i0483e00.htm>

SUMMARY

6. Poultry welfare assessment on the farm: Focusing on the individual

Linares, J. A.; Dougherty, S.; Millman, S. 2018. In Advances in Poultry Welfare. DOI: [10.1016/B978-0-08-100915-4.00007-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-100915-4.00007-5)

SUMMARY

7. Training course: Animal welfare in poultry production - broilers

BTSF Academy. 2021. Better Training for Safer Food. <https://better-training-for-safer-food.ec.europa.eu/training/course/info.php?id=335>

SUMMARY

8. Review of existing courses and materials for poultry

EURCAW-Poultry-SFA. 2021. <https://zenodo.org/records/7437083#.Y-EwBnbMKUk>

SUMMARY

9. The welfare of broiler chickens in the EU

EuroGroup for Animals. 2020. https://www.eurogroupforanimals.org/files/eurogroupforanimals/2020-11/2020_11_19_eurogroup_for_animals_broiler_report.pdf

SUMMARY

10. IPWA Broiler Guide Key Welfare Indicators

International Poultry Welfare Alliance. 2022. <https://poultrywelfare.org/files/IPWA%20Broiler%20Chickens%20Guide%20V13.pdf>

SUMMARY

2.4 Informative summaries

1. Inspirational idea: A national network stimulating knowledge exchange on animal welfare in Germany

This news article describes a German initiative that stimulates sector wide sharing of skills and knowledge for animal-welfare oriented, sustainable and environmentally friendly livestock farming. This includes exchange of knowledge on national level between government and farmers about legislation, new scientific knowledge, and technical solutions using events, check lists, guidelines, farm visits, workshops, fairs, articles, videos or podcasts. Also performing via the Fokus Tierwohl website and social media (Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, Spotify, Youtube...).

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2. Assessing and improving poultry welfare in commercial production systems

Animal welfare is of growing concern in many countries. The objective of this article is to discuss why there are differing definitions and approaches to the assessment and improvement of animal welfare, whether differences matter and where there is general agreement in current scientific concepts. Furthermore, future directions regarding on-farm welfare improvement are proposed. It is generally agreed that animal welfare refers to the multi-faceted physical as well as mental state of the individual animal and can range from very good to very poor. In order to cover the multitude of relevant aspects, different approaches, and thus welfare definitions, are used. They commonly do not contradict each other, but approach welfare from slightly different perspectives or with different focal points. For the assessment of welfare, a broad number of indicators must be used that may be either animal- or resource- and management-based. In terms of validity, animal-based indicators are to be preferred, but due to feasibility aspects, often a mixture of different types of indicators are recommendable and used. The selection of individual welfare indicators is, however, not only based on scientific and feasibility criteria, but is also value-dependent. This similarly applies to the interpretation of conflicting results regarding different measures. Transparency about the decision-making concerning measure selection and therefore crucial. When deciding about acceptable welfare levels, various human interests come on board, generating a societal debate. **Keywords:** animal welfare, welfare assessment, poultry production. The practical welfare assessment must be reliable in order to be useful and trustworthy, which requires considerable efforts. The assessment can serve different purposes, but most importantly provides poultry farmers useful information and starting points for improvement. Many multifactorial welfare problems can only successfully be tackled by farm-specific, longer-term optimisation processes. Joint learning and knowledge sharing in networks of farmers together with other experts is a very promising approach for this. While further knowledge about risk factors for welfare problems is still needed, practice-led innovations should also be stimulated. Moreover, continued methodical research is necessary to improve the choice and practicability of valid animal-based indicators for application in commercial production systems.

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3. Improving Farm Animal Productivity and Welfare, by Increasing Skills and Knowledge of Stock People

Animal welfare and production results are closely linked. There is a lot of variation in both, even if the circumstances under which the animals are kept appear to be similar. This means that the farmer himself plays an important role in maintaining a good level of welfare, and a good level of production. Taking care of animals is a job for which skills and training are required. Some of the most important attributes are a sound technical understanding of what animals need, a keen eye for the signals animals send regarding their health and welfare and the personal characteristics to act on information. Stock people should be supported to do their job well, e.g., through training on technical issues, but also by training on how to learn about the 'signals' that animals send to us. A correct assessment of the welfare status, e.g., through the Welfare Quality® protocol, will also facilitate the issues which need to be addressed through good farm management. Finally, the attitude of the stock person to his or her work is of crucial importance to animal wellbeing. Training which addresses attitudes is available, and has also proven to be effective in increasing farm productivity.

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4. GCAW Recommendation on the use of Welfare Outcome Measures for Broiler Chickens

Animal welfare and production results are closely linked. There is a lot of variation in both, even if the circumstances under which the animals are kept appear to be similar. This means

that the farmer himself plays an important role in maintaining a good level of welfare, and a good level of production. Taking care of animals is a job for which skills and training are required. Some of the most important attributes are a sound technical understanding of what animals need, a keen eye for the signals animals send regarding their health and welfare and the personal characteristics to act on information. Stock people should be supported to do their job well, e.g., through training on technical issues, but also by training on how to learn about the 'signals' that animals send to us. A correct assessment of the welfare status, e.g., through the Welfare Quality® protocol, will also facilitate the issues which need to be addressed through good farm management. Finally, the attitude of the stock person to his or her work is of crucial importance to animal wellbeing. Training which addresses attitudes is available, and has also proven to be effective in increasing farm productivity.

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5. Capacity building to implement good animal welfare practices

Capacity building for implementing good animal welfare practices involves four elements: (a) education to create awareness of animal welfare and an understanding of its significance for successful animal production, (b) engagement to foster active involvement of people who work with animals, (c) training in specific procedures, and (d) communication among different international organizations, between stakeholders and providers of training, and among the different government departments, professional bodies and other organizations involved in animal welfare. Capacity building needs to be sympathetic to local knowledge and resources. Rather than seeking to impose standards that cannot be realized immediately, capacity building should facilitate the problem-solving abilities of participants so that they will be able to meet standards in the future. Ultimately, training should be done by local organizations and personnel; external expertise is most efficiently used to train future trainers.

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6. Poultry welfare assessment on the farm: Focusing on the individual

Animal welfare assessment and post-assessment decisions are made within the complexity of issues involving ethics, science, veterinary medicine, economics, and policy. Animal welfare itself is complex and it is best understood by considering its three components: biological functioning, affective states, and opportunities for natural living (Fraser et al., 1997). We find it useful to employ all three of these components when assessing poultry welfare. Training and experience are keys to carrying out a practical, accurate, and informative assessment. This chapter is designed to review practical issues related to the assessment of the welfare of compromised individual birds in a poultry flock, as well as their treatment or euthanasia. Assessing individual birds is easier in small flocks of up to 100 birds. In larger flocks, individuals may be overlooked. It takes time and a trained eye to identify individual deviations from normal, and it takes a systematic approach to find the affected individuals. Compromised birds can most readily be recognized by their behavior and appearance. The use of behavior in the assessment of health at the flock level was covered in a previous publication (Linares and Martin, 2010). The natural social structure within flocks is expressed and governed by competition for resources, breeding behaviors, parental care, aggressive and submissive behaviors, pecking orders, and synchronized behaviors (Estevez, Chapter 12). The presence, absence, frequency, and intensity of these behaviors are some of the parameters used for the assessment of poultry welfare. An individual bird's welfare depends on its ability to cope with this natural social structure, the environment, management practices, and the overall health status of the flock. Sickness and injury can impair an individual bird's ability to cope.

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7. Training course: Animal welfare in poultry production - broilers

This is an example of a virtual training program regarding the organisation and implementation of training activities on animal welfare on the farm, animal welfare at the time of killing of animals (at slaughterhouses and for disease control purposes) and animal welfare during transport. The overall objectives of the BTSF Training Courses on Animal welfare in poultry production - broilers are: Raising awareness and promoting a common understanding of the EU animal welfare rules applicable to poultry and pig productions, slaughtering practices and long-distance transportation. Ensuring consistent and high implementation standards across the Union. Promoting the exchange of good and best practices among EU Member States as regards control activities at farm. Improving the welfare conditions of live farmed animals in Europe. Improving awareness of the EU legislation on animal welfare in selected non-EU Countries. Stimulating a constructive dialogue among the interested parties (including business operators, NGOs and their umbrella organisations), and also a collaborative climate among EU and Non-EU National Competent Authorities towards common achievements concerning the most controversial aspects in the interpretation of the relevant pieces of legislation.

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8. Review of existing courses and materials for poultry

This deliverable contains an overview of existing courses and what is taught in both BTSF and EU National training for the three priority areas of EURCAW-Poultry-SFA: Broilers welfare on farm.

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9. The welfare of broiler chickens in the EU

This report is divided in three sections: the first section concisely presents the legislation in place that affects broiler welfare. The subsequent chapters present and discuss the welfare of broiler chickens during the three phases of their lives that are covered by EU legislation: rearing (growing), during transport and at the time of slaughter. These chapters highlight the key issues for welfare and discuss how some of these issues can be mitigated. The second section deals with aspects for which species-specific norms do not apply, with the exclusion of Directive 98/58/EC (Farm Animals Directive). Chapter 4 provides an extensive overview of the welfare of the parent animals that produce the broiler chickens that are reared for meat. This is not a well-known part of the chicken meat industry and there are several welfare risks for these birds. Chapter 5 examines the main welfare challenges of newly hatched chicks and how these can be mitigated in commercial hatcheries and on-farm, primarily by means of technological innovations. The last section looks into the future. Chapter 6 deals with the welfare of higher welfare, slower-growing broiler chickens in various rearing systems. Chapter 7 reviews the current state of knowledge on sustainability, describes the market forces driving change in this sector, and makes the case for the importance of integrity along the whole supply chain. Finally, in Chapter 8 we summarise the animal advocacy perspective on the importance of transitioning towards a higher-welfare broiler chicken industry.

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10. IPWA Broiler Guide Key Welfare Indicators

While there are different welfare programs and standards used around the world, there was a need for a comprehensive list of outcomes-based key welfare indicators with standardized instructions for the measurements that can be used in different poultry species and at different production stages. IPWA's subject matter experts formed multistakeholder groups to discuss and develop a list of KWIs that can be applied to poultry, broken out by the specific needs of broilers, layers, and turkeys. Members of the IPWA Poultry Health & Welfare

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Committee, who served as the primary authors, included 57 production managers, welfare program supervisors, business owners, veterinarians, and other professionals actively involved in the creation, implementation, or verification of welfare protocols for poultry. Their expertise and current work covered every poultry market in the world. The IPWA Research & Education Committee completed a rigorous academic review and revision process of the guide, bringing together 18 research experts from the world's leading institutions and growing poultry research programs. This guide was built to help farmers assess their poultry welfare at the foundational level based in proven science that can be consistently used around the world.

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Funded by
the European Union

Chapter 3 Genetics & Breeding

3.1 List of scientific knowledge sources

1. Genetic selection of broilers and welfare consequences: a review

Hartcher, K.M., Lum, H.K. 2020. *J. World's Poult. Sci.* 76 (1): 154-167. DOI: [10.1080/00439339.2019.1680025](https://doi.org/10.1080/00439339.2019.1680025)

[ABSTRACT](#)

2. In pursuit of a better broiler: growth, efficiency, and mortality of 16 strains of broiler chickens

Torrey, S.; Mohammadigheisar, M.; dos Santos, M.N.; Rothschild, D.; Dawson, L.C.; Liu, Z. Z.; Kiarie, E.G.; Edwards, A.M.; Mandell, I.; Karrow, N.; Tulpan, D.; Widowski, T.M. 2021. *Poult. Sci.* 100(3):100955. DOI: [10.1016/j.psj.2020.12.052](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2020.12.052)

[ABSTRACT](#)

3. Leg health of meat chickens: impact on welfare, consumer behaviour, and the role of environmental enrichment

Phibbs, D.V.; Groves, P.J.; Muir, W.I. 2021. *Anim. Prod. Sci.* 61(12) 1203-1212. DOI: [10.1071/AN19511](https://doi.org/10.1071/AN19511)

[ABSTRACT](#)

4. Behaviour and meat quality of chicken under different housing systems

El-Deek, A.; El-Sabrou, K. 2019. *J. World's Poult. Sci.* 765(1):105-114. DOI: [10.1017/S0043933918000946](https://doi.org/10.1017/S0043933918000946)

[ABSTRACT](#)

5. Welfare of broilers on farm

Nielsen, S.S., Alvarez, J., Bicout, D.J., Calistri, P., Canali, E., Drewe, J.A., Garin-Bastuji, B., Rojas, J.L., Schmidt, C.G., Herskin, M.S., Chueca, M.A., Padalino, B., Pasquali, P., Roberts, H.C., Spooler, H., Stahl, K., Velarde, A., Viltrop, A., Winckler, C., Tiemann, I., Jong, I. de, Gebhardt-Henrich, S.G., Keeling, L., Riber, AB, Ashe, S., Candiani, D., Matas, R.G., Hempen, M., Mosbach-Schulz, O., Gimeno, C.R., van der Stede, Y., Vitali, M., Bailly-Caumette, E., Michel, V. EFSA Panel Animal Health and Welfare. 2023. *EFSA J.* 21, 1–236. DOI: [10.2903/j.efsa.2023.7788](https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2023.7788)

[ABSTRACT](#)

6. Effects of pen enrichment on leg health of fast and slower-growing broiler chickens

Güz, B.C.; Jong, I.C. de; Da Silva, C.S.; Veldkamp, F.; Kemp, B. Molenaar, R.; van den Brand, H. 2021. *PLoS One.* 16(12):e0254462. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0254462](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0254462)

[ABSTRACT](#)

7. Breeding for better welfare: genetic goals for broiler chickens and their parents

Dawkins, M.S., Layton, R. 2012. *Animal Welfare.* 21(2):147-155. DOI: [10.7120/09627286.21.2.147](https://doi.org/10.7120/09627286.21.2.147)

ABSTRACT

8. Evaluating broiler welfare and behavior as affected by growth rate and stocking density

Zhou, S., Watcharaanantapong, P., Yang, X., Thornton, T., Gan, H., Tabler, T., Prado, M., Zhao, Y. 2024. *Poult. Sci.*103(4):103459. DOI: [10.1016/j.psj.2024.103459](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2024.103459)

ABSTRACT

9. Effects of Elevated Grids on Growing Male Chickens Differing in Growth Performance

Malchow, J., Puppe, B., Berk, J., Schrader, L. 2019. *Front Vet Sci.* 6:203. DOI: [10.3389/fvets.2019.00203](https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2019.00203)

ABSTRACT

10. Review of environmental enrichment for broiler chickens

Riber, A.B.; van de Weerd, H.A.; Jong, I.C. de; Steinfeldt, S. 2018. *Poult. Sci.* 97(2):378-396. DOI: [10.3382/ps/pex344](https://doi.org/10.3382/ps/pex344)

ABSTRACT

3.2 Informative abstracts

1. Genetic selection of broilers and welfare consequences: a review

The genetic selection of broilers over the past 60 years has focused narrowly and intensely on production traits, namely growth rate and feed efficiency. This has led to significant welfare problems in birds grown for meat, including leg disorders, cardiovascular diseases, and resulting high mortality rates, while the breeder birds are subjected to severe feed restriction. Bone problems such as bacterial chondronecrosis and tibia dyschondroplasia are prevalent, and recent studies have reported the prevalence of birds with moderate to severe gait impairment to be between 5.5 and 48.8%. Worldwide, over 66 billion broilers are slaughtered annually. This huge scale of meat chicken production means that welfare problems are widespread and are likely to increase in severity due to the increasing global human population, increasing demand for meat, and a continued focus on efficiency of production in the agricultural sector. The commercial broiler industry therefore represents some of the most serious animal welfare issues in agriculture. There is an urgent need to address these problems by making welfare traits high priorities in breeding programmes and integrating these with other breeding goals. Many studies recommend the use of slower-growing breeds that do not have the same welfare problems. Addressing these welfare issues is essential to improve bird welfare and for social acceptability and sustainability of the broiler industry worldwide.

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2. In pursuit of a better broiler: growth, efficiency, and mortality of 16 strains of broiler chickens

To meet the growing consumer demand for chicken meat, the poultry industry has selected broiler chickens for increasing efficiency and breast yield. While this high productivity means affordable and consistent product, it has come at a cost to broiler welfare. There has been increasing advocacy and consumer pressure on primary breeders, producers, processors, and retailers to improve the welfare of the billions of chickens processed annually. Several small-scale studies have reported better welfare outcomes for slower-growing strains compared to

fast-growing, conventional strains. However, these studies often housed birds with range access or used strains with vastly different growth rates. Additionally, there may be traits other than growth, such as body conformation, that influence welfare. As the global poultry industries consider the implications of using slower growing strains, there was a need for a comprehensive, multidisciplinary examination of broiler chickens with a wide range of genotypes differing in growth rate and other phenotypic traits. To meet this need, our team designed a study to benchmark data on conventional and slower growing strains of broiler chickens reared in standardized laboratory conditions. Over a 2-year period, we studied 7,528 broilers from 16 different genetic strains. In this paper, we compare the growth, efficiency, and mortality of broilers to one of two target weights (TW): 2.1 kg (TW1) and 3.2 kg (TW2). We categorized strains by their growth rate to TW2 as conventional (CONV), fastest-slow strains (FAST), moderate-slow strains (MOD), and slowest-slow strains (SLOW). When incubated, hatched, housed, managed, and fed the same, the categories of strains differed in body weights, growth rates, feed intake, and feed efficiency. At 48 d of age, strains in the CONV category were 835 to 1,264 g heavier than strains in the other categories. By TW2, differences in body weights and feed intake resulted in a 22 to 43-point difference in feed conversion ratios. Categories of strains did not differ in their overall mortality rates.

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3. Leg health of meat chickens: impact on welfare, consumer behaviour, and the role of environmental enrichment

The Australian and global chicken meat industries have benefited from rapid improvements in the efficiency of chicken meat production that have been predominantly achieved through genetic selection, optimisation of bird nutrition and improved bird health. However, this has also resulted in morphological changes in the bird with an increase in the prevalence of leg health disorders. Compromised leg health can cause pain and lameness and bodes poorly for bird wellbeing, bird mortality, and economic returns. There are also implications for the consumer who is increasingly mindful of animal welfare and is demanding more welfare friendly products. Accurate on-farm assessment of bird leg health has challenges due to the diversity of leg disorders and the variety of techniques used to assess their severity and impact. Overall prevalence of leg disorders shows great variability between properties (farms) and flocks. Opportunities to improve bird leg health have been the focus of considerable research which has frequently included an evaluation of environmental enrichment as a means to reduce lameness and improve bird mobility. To this end, currently in Australia, 78% of chicken meat is produced under the conditions of the Australian RSPCA Approved Farming Scheme, which requires perches in the birds' environment. However, the value of perches in providing enrichment and improving bird welfare is unclear. Therefore, this review explores animal welfare and consumer attitudes towards meat chicken welfare, describes leg disorders, outlines techniques for assessing leg health and discusses opportunities to enrich the birds' environment to improve bird mobility and leg health.

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4. Behaviour and meat quality of chicken under different housing systems

Chicken housing systems have been an interesting subject of research for many years and remains a topic of debate. The information detailed in the literature provides opposing views on recommended housing systems (indoor or outdoor) for chickens, and thus, producers are searching for more precise information in terms of animal welfare, productive performance, chicken behaviour and meat quality. Approximately 80% of customers worldwide prefer chicken products with perceived higher quality derived from free-range (organic) systems with increased welfare standards. Based on published literature, the majority (approximately 70%) of intensive production systems that are currently used do not usually support the natural behavioural needs of poultry. However, mortality rate of broilers can reach more than

10% in outdoor production systems due to cannibalism. Suitable housing systems that focus on the animals' well-being translate into better behavioural activities and higher productive performance. The present review provides the critical information detailed in the existing literature on different housing systems and their effect on chicken behaviour and meat quality. It can be concluded that the housing system, as a non-genetic factor, directly affects the welfare of the birds and can impact their behaviour and certain meat quality traits. Thus, the free-range production system might be considered favourable alternative housing system.

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5. Welfare of broilers on farm

This Scientific Opinion considers the welfare of domestic fowl (*Gallus gallus*) related to the production of meat (broilers) and includes the keeping of day-old chicks, broiler breeders, and broiler chickens. Currently used husbandry systems in the EU are described. Overall, 19 highly relevant welfare consequences (WCs) were identified based on severity, duration and frequency of occurrence: 'bone lesions', 'cold stress', 'gastro-enteric disorders', 'group stress', 'handling stress', 'heat stress', 'isolation stress', 'inability to perform comfort behaviour', 'inability to perform exploratory or foraging behaviour', 'inability to avoid unwanted sexual behaviour', 'locomotory disorders', 'prolonged hunger', 'prolonged thirst', 'predation stress', 'restriction of movement', 'resting problems', 'sensory under- and overstimulation', 'soft tissue and integument damage' and 'umbilical disorders'. These WCs and their animal-based measures (ABMs) that can identify them are described in detail. A variety of hazards related to the different husbandry systems were identified as well as ABMs for assessing the different WCs. Measures to prevent or correct the hazards and/or mitigate each of the WCs are listed. Recommendations are provided on quantitative or qualitative criteria to answer specific questions on the welfare of broilers and related to genetic selection, temperature, feed and water restriction, use of cages, light, air quality and mutilations in breeders such as beak trimming, de-toeing and comb dubbing. In addition, minimal requirements (e.g. stocking density, group size, nests, provision of litter, perches and platforms, drinkers and feeders, of covered veranda and outdoor range) for an enclosure for keeping broiler chickens (fast-growing, slower-growing and broiler breeders) are recommended. Finally, 'total mortality', 'wounds', 'carcass condemnation' and 'footpad dermatitis' are proposed as indicators for monitoring at slaughter the welfare of broilers on-farm.

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6. Effects of pen enrichment on leg health of fast and slower-growing broiler chickens

Pen enrichment for broiler chickens is one of the potential strategies to stimulate locomotion and consequently contribute to better leg health and welfare. This study was designed to evaluate effects of using a plethora of pen enrichments (barrier perches, angular ramps, horizontal platforms, large distance between feed and water and providing live Black Soldier fly larvae in a dustbathing area) on tibia characteristics, locomotion, leg health and home pen behaviour of fast and slower-growing broiler chickens. The experiment was set up as a 2 x 2 factorial arrangement with a total of 840 male broiler chickens in a complete randomized design (7 pens per treatment and 30 chickens per pen) with the following treatments: 1) pen enrichment (enriched pen or non-enriched pen); 2) broiler strain (fast-growing Ross 308 or slower-growing Hubbard JA 757). Home pen behaviour and use of enrichment were observed. At approximately 1400 and 2200 g body weight, two chickens per pen were randomly selected and slaughtered, to investigate tibia morphological, biophysical and mechanical characteristics and leg health. Pen enrichment positively affected tibia biophysical characteristics, e.g., osseous volume ($\Delta = 1.8 \text{ cm}^3$, $P = 0.003$), total volume ($\Delta =$

1.4 cm³, $P = 0.03$) and volume fraction ($\Delta = 0.02\%$, $P = 0.002$), in both fast and slower-growing chickens, suggesting that pen enrichment particularly affects ossification and mineralization mechanisms. Accordingly, locomotion and active behaviours were positively influenced by pen enrichment. However, pen enrichment resulted in lower body weight gain in both strains, which might be due to higher activity or lower feed intake as a result of difficulties of crossing the barrier perches. Regarding the strain, slower-growing chickens showed consistently more advanced tibia characteristics and more active behaviour than fast-growing chickens. It can be concluded that pen enrichment may lead to more activity and better bone development in both fast and slower-growing chickens.

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7. **Breeding for better welfare: genetic goals for broiler chickens and their parents**

Genetics is key to the improvement of welfare in broiler chickens at both juvenile and adult (breeder) stages but progress is hampered currently by the seemingly conflicting demands of welfare, commercial production, food security and calls for increasing intensification to curb climate change. Animal welfare is therefore most likely to be improved on a commercial scale by future breeding programmes that incorporate multiple goals of different stakeholders as far as possible and give higher priority to animal welfare. These include: i) broilers with high welfare traits; ii) broiler breeders that do not need feed restriction; iii) birds that can be grown in an economically profitable way; iv) birds with low disease levels without the need for routine medication; v) chicken meat that is healthy and good for humans to eat; and (vi) broilers and breeders that thrive in systems that are environmentally sustainable. Progress towards achieving these goals is hampered currently by the assumptions that high juvenile growth rate is incompatible with good welfare and that feed restriction in adults is inevitable with fast-growing juveniles. We challenge these assumptions at both genetic and whole-animal level and argue that the conflict between good welfare and productivity can be reduced by making use of all available genetic variation from existing breeds and other sources and selecting birds in the range of environments they will encounter in commercial production.

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8. **Evaluating broiler welfare and behavior as affected by growth rate and stocking density**

This study evaluated the welfare and behaviors of Cobb 700 broilers as affected by growth rate (GR) and stocking density (SD). Slower-growth (weight gain < 50 g day⁻¹) and medium-growth (weight gain = 50 to 60 g day⁻¹) broilers were produced by providing 57.1% and 78.6% of the feed intake listed in the Cobb 700 production manual for standard (fed ad libitum) broilers (weight gain > 60 g day⁻¹). Broilers at all 3 GRs were reared at 2 SDs of 30 and 40 kg/m². Broiler welfare indicators, including gait score, tibia strength, feather coverage, and footpad condition were evaluated when birds reached 1, 2, and 3 kg of body weight. The activity index was determined by overhead cameras and image processing, and the time spent at feeders was recorded using the radio-frequency identification (RFID) systems. The results show that it took 45 days for standard, 52 days for medium-growth, and 62 days for slower-growth broilers to reach a 3 kg market body weight. Feed conversion ratios (FCR, kg/kg) were 1.57 for standard, 1.67 for medium-growth, and 1.80 for slower-growth broilers. GR and SD had an interaction effect on feather cleanliness ($P=0.03$), and belly feather coverage ($P=0.02$). Slower-growth broilers were more active and had better feather coverage and gait scores than medium-growth and standard broilers (all $P<0.01$) but may feel hungry and depressed, medium-growth broilers spent the most time at the feeder among the 3 growth groups ($P=0.02$), and standard broilers showed the best production performance. Broilers at 30 kg/m² showed better bone strength ($P=0.04$), and footpad condition ($P<0.01$) compared to those at 40 kg/m². In conclusion, reducing GR and SD may

slightly improve broiler leg health at the high expense of compromised production performance and prolonged production cycles.

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9. Effects of Elevated Grids on Growing Male Chickens Differing in Growth Performance

Pullets, i. e., chickens of layer lines are often raised in housings equipped with perches. In contrast, broiler chickens most often are raised in a barren environment that lacks any three-dimensional structures, even though broilers also are motivated to use elevated structures. In addition, environmental enrichment may improve welfare problems in broiler chickens, such as skeletal disorders or contact dermatitis. Due to ethical reasons, currently there are attempts to fatten the male chickens of layer strains or to use dual purpose strains. However, there is only limited knowledge on the behavior of these chickens until now. The aim of this study was to test the use of elevated grids and their effect on animal-based indicators (e.g., physical condition). In two successive trials, we kept a total of 1,217 male chickens from three strains (Lohmann Dual, Lohmann Brown Plus, Ross 308) that show differences in growth performance in 24 pens (two trials x three strains x eight pens). In half of the pens, grids were offered at three different heights (enriched groups); in the other half of the pens, no elevated structures were installed (control groups). We recorded the number of birds using the grids at the different heights as well as locomotor activity, walking ability, plumage cleanliness, and the footpad health of chickens. Chickens with low and medium growth performance preferred the highest grids during both the light and dark periods. In contrast, fast-growing chickens used the lowest grid more frequently. Fast-growing chickens kept in the enriched pens tended to have a higher level of locomotor activity and reduced chest cleanliness. Chickens from the medium growth performance strain showed better walking ability when kept in the enriched pens. Enrichment did not affect any of the welfare measures in the slow-growing chickens. These findings suggest that elevated structures may improve chicken welfare, particularly for medium growing chickens. For fast-growing chickens we found evidence for an improvement of animal-based indicators although they used the elevated structures less. However, regardless of growth performance, elevated grids offer the birds an opportunity to rest in a species-specific manner.

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10. Review of environmental enrichment for broiler chickens

Welfare problems are commonly found in both conventional and organic production of broiler chickens. In order to reduce the extent of welfare problems, it has been suggested to provide stimulating, enriched environments. The aim of the present paper is to provide a review of the effect on behavior and welfare of the different kinds of environmental enrichments in the production of broilers that have been described in the scientific literature. Environmental enrichment is defined as an improvement of the environment of captive animals, which increases the behavioral opportunities of the animal and leads to improvements of the biological function. This definition has been broadened to include practical and economic aspects, as any enrichment strategy that adversely affects the health of animals or that has too many economic or practical constraints will never be implemented on commercial farms and thus never benefit animals. Environmental enrichment for broilers often has the purpose of satisfying behavioral needs and/or stimulating the broilers to an increased level of activity, which among others will reduce the occurrence of leg problems. Potentially successful environmental enrichments for broiler chickens are elevated resting-places, panels, barriers, and bales of straw ("point-source enrichment"), as well as covered verandas and outdoor ranges ("complex enriched environments"). Many of the ideas for environmental enrichment for broilers need to be further developed and studied, preferably in commercial trials, with respect to the use, the effect on behavior and on other welfare aspects such as leg health,

and the interaction with genotype, production system, stocking density, light, and flock size. In addition, information on the practical application and the economics of the production system is often lacking, although it is important for application in practice.

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3.3 List of practical knowledge sources

1. Decades of Breeding for Welfare and Sustainability

Aviagen. 2023. https://aviagen.com/assets/Welfare/AviagenDecades-of-WelfareReport_2023.pdf

[SUMMARY](#)

2. Welfare Sheet: Broiler chickens

Compassion in World Farming, 2013. <https://www.ciwf.org.uk/media/5235309/Welfare-sheet-Broiler-chickens.pdf>

[SUMMARY](#)

3. Could dual-purpose poultry improve welfare and ecological outcomes?

Poultry World, 2025 <https://www.poultryworld.net/poultry/genetics/could-dual-purpose-poultry-improve-welfare-and-ecological-outcomes/>

[SUMMARY](#)

4. The poultry industry reacts to landmark welfare report

WATTPoultry 2020. <https://www.wattagnet.com/broilers-turkeys/broilers/article/15531992/the-poultry-industry-reacts-to-landmark-welfare-report-wattagnet>

[SUMMARY](#)

5. Adopting slower-growing breeds of chicken would reduce animal suffering significantly

Our World in Data, 2023. <https://ourworldindata.org/adopting-slower-growing-breeds-of-chicken-would-reduce-animal-suffering-significantly>

[SUMMARY](#)

6. Rules to create gene-edited farm animals must put welfare first - review

BBC, 2021. <https://www.bbc.com/news/science-environment-59480907>

[SUMMARY](#)

7. Slower growing chickens experience higher welfare, commercial scale study finds

University of Bristol, 2020. <https://www.bristol.ac.uk/news/2020/september/broiler-chickens.html>

[SUMMARY](#)

8. In ovo vaccine could combat bacterial lameness in broilers

WATTPoultry, 2024. <https://www.wattagnet.com/broilers-turkeys/diseases-health/news/15710995/in-ovo-vaccine-could-combat-bacterial-lameness-in-broilers>

SUMMARY

9. Fast-growing chickens have long suffered from unique health problems. Is it time to ban them from animal welfare certifications?

The Counter, 2020. <https://thecounter.org/fast-growing-broiler-chickens-animal-welfare-gap-research/>

SUMMARY

10. Protecting chickens from heart disease

The Poultry Site, 2023. <https://www.thepoultrysite.com/articles/protecting-chickens-from-heart-disease>

SUMMARY

3.4 Informative summaries

1. Decades of Breeding for Welfare and Sustainability

This paper will demonstrate the decades long commitment of Aviagen to the genetic improvement of welfare and sustainability of broiler and turkey breeds. It will also cover the techniques used to ensure robustness and optimal welfare under a wide range of production conditions, as well as new methods to improve the accuracy of our selection and further drive genetic progress for better welfare and sustainability outcomes.

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2. Welfare Sheet: Broiler chicken

This document gives an overview of the different welfare problems that are associated with intensive meat chicken production. It will also outline how these welfare problems may be overcome in housing systems that offer an alternative to intensive systems. There are serious welfare issues associated with the breeding and intensive rearing of broilers and it is generally accepted that most of the welfare problems are caused by genetic factors, environmental factors and the interactions between them.

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3. Could dual-purpose poultry improve welfare and ecological outcomes?

A UK research project will combine desk-based research with small-scale trials to explore the practicalities and sustainability of dual-purposed, pasture-raised poultry. Planton Farms in Shropshire is embarking on the pioneering project as a potential integrated enterprise for UK farms. Co-founder Dr Annie Rayner said dual-purpose poultry was important given the ethical issues around culling day-old male chicks and various bans across EU countries. It is expected to be restricted by regulations in the UK in the next 5-10 years. Specialised breeding has resulted in highly productive chickens with efficient feed conversion rates, but these breeds rely on high-protein feeds, often sourced from imported ingredients like soy. These breeds are poorly suited to outdoor organic systems.

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4. The poultry industry reacts to landmark welfare report

A newly released animal welfare report may lead to further pressure on the broiler industry and breeding companies to adopt some degree of slower-growing broiler genetics.

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5. Adopting slower-growing breeds of chicken would reduce animal suffering significantly

Research into the intensity and duration of pain in livestock is still emerging. Researchers are trying to develop various techniques to evaluate animal behavior and its relationship to pain. One example is using camera surveillance and flow patterns to understand aggressive or distressed behavior in pigs or chickens. But there are a range of unanswered questions.

The research from Schuck-Paim and Alonso suggests that moving from fast-growing to slower-growing breeds would offer significant benefits to animal welfare. The reductions in pain for individuals are already large. But considering we raise and kill more than 70 billion chickens every year, even small gains at the individual level lead to a massive reduction in animal suffering.

Slower growth rates are one of several policies that form part of the Better Chicken Commitment that many European countries have signed up to. This suggests that there is growing support for adopting better practices.

The other obvious conclusion from this research is that slower-growing breeds still experience significant amounts of suffering. That's why the largest welfare benefits come from eating less meat overall.

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6. Rules to create gene-edited farm animals must put welfare first - review

Regulations to allow the production of gene-edited farm animals must put welfare first, according to an independent review. The technology allows scientists to alter DNA so as to introduce specific traits, such as resistance to disease. The UK government is mulling proposals to allow the commercial development of gene-edited livestock in England. An independent analysis has called for a review of the government's proposals for regulating the technology. A report by the Nuffield Council for Bioethics warns that scrapping the current ban on the commercial development of gene-edited animals could increase livestock suffering

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7. Slower growing chickens experience higher welfare, commercial scale study finds

Slower growing broiler chickens are healthier and have more fun than conventional breeds of birds, new evidence from an independent commercial scale farm trial has shown. The study carried out by researchers from FAI Farms, the University of Bristol and The Norwegian University of Life Sciences, is published today [16 September], in Scientific Reports.

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8. In ovo vaccine could combat bacterial lameness in broilers

"Bacterial chondronecrosis with osteomyelitis is caused by multiple different types of bacteria. In our vaccine, we only have different species of Staphylococcus, but our future plan is to incorporate more types of bacteria to enhance the vaccine," said Palmy Jesudhasan, PhD, research microbiologist at the U.S. Department of Agriculture's (USDA) Poultry Production and Product Safety Research Unit.

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9. Fast-growing chickens have long suffered from unique health problems. Is it time to ban them from animal welfare certifications?

A major animal welfare certifier will consider eliminating fast-growing breeds from its program.

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10. Protecting chickens from heart disease

The team's results, which were published recently in Avian Pathology, suggest that heart issues in fast-growing broiler chickens might be linked to how their genes respond to epigenetic factors, like nutrition and their environment.

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Funded by
the European Union

Chapter 4 Barn climate

4.1 List of scientific knowledge sources

1. Thermal conditioning in the broiler production: challenges and possibilities

Mascarenhas, N.M.H.; Pereira, M.L.L.; Alves de Caldas; A.C.; Batista, L.F.; Andrade, E.L.G 2018. J. Anim. Behav. Biometeorol. 6(2), 52-55. DOI: [10.31893/2318-1265jabb.v6n2p52-55](https://doi.org/10.31893/2318-1265jabb.v6n2p52-55)

[ABSTRACT](#)

2. System for assessing broilers thermal comfort

de Oliveira Júnior, A. J., dos Santos Sousa, G., Dal Pai, E., de Almeida, O. C. P., Neto, M. M., Simões, R. P., de Souza, S. R. L., 2021. Smart Agric. Technol. 1, 100007. DOI: [10.1016/j.atech.2021.100007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atech.2021.100007)

[ABSTRACT](#)

3. Positioning of sensors for control of ventilation systems in broiler houses: a case study

Curi, T. M. R. de C., Conti, D., Vercellino, R. do A., Massari, J. M., Moura, D. J. de, Souza, Z. M. de., & Montanari, R. 2017. Sci. Agric. 74, 101-109. DOI: [10.1590/1678-992X-2015-0369](https://doi.org/10.1590/1678-992X-2015-0369)

[ABSTRACT](#)

4. Heat stress impacts on broiler performance: a systematic review and meta-analysis

Liu, L.; Ren, M.; Ren, K.; Jin, Y; Yan, M. 2020. Poult. Sci. 99(11), 6205-6211. DOI: [10.1016/j.psj.2020.08.019](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2020.08.019)

[ABSTRACT](#)

5. Impact of Heating Systems on Air and Litter Quality in Broiler Houses, Performance, Behavior, and Immunity in Broiler Chickens

Wasti, S.; Sah, N.; Mishra, B. 2020. Adv. Anim. Vet. Sci, 9(2), 301-314. DOI: [10.17582/journal.aavs/2021/9.2.301.314](https://doi.org/10.17582/journal.aavs/2021/9.2.301.314)

[ABSTRACT](#)

6. Ammonia concentrations, litter quality, performance and some welfare parameters of broilers kept on different bedding materials

Brink, M.; Janssens, G. P. J.; Demeyer, P.; Bağci, Ö.; Delezie, E. 2022. Br. Poult. Sci. 63(6), 768-778. DOI: [10.1080/00071668.2022.2106775](https://doi.org/10.1080/00071668.2022.2106775)

[ABSTRACT](#)

7. Sprinkler Technology Improves Broiler Production Sustainability: From Stress Alleviation to Water Usage Conservation: A Mini Review

Liang, Y.; Tabler, G.T.; Dridi, S. 2020. Front. vet. sci, 7, 544814. DOI: [10.3389/fvets.2020.544814](https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2020.544814)

[ABSTRACT](#)

8. **The reduction of gas concentrations in broiler houses through ventilation: Assessment of the thermal and electrical energy consumption**

Costantino, A.; Fabrizio, E.; Villagra, A.; Estells, F.; Calvet, S. 2020. Biosyst. Eng. 199, 135-148. DOI: [10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2020.01.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2020.01.002)

[ABSTRACT](#)

9. **Technology and Poultry Welfare**

Sassi, N. B., Avers, X., Estevez, I. 2016. Animals, 6(10), 62. DOI: [10.3390/ani6100062](https://doi.org/10.3390/ani6100062)

[ABSTRACT](#)

10. **Impacts of projected climate change scenarios on heating and cooling demand for industrial broiler chicken farming in the Eastern U.S**

Izar-Tenorio, J., Jaramillo, P.W., Griffin, M., Small, M. 2020. J. Clean. Prod. 255: 120306. DOI: [10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120306](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120306)

[ABSTRACT](#)

4.2 Informative abstracts

1. **Thermal conditioning in the broiler production: challenges and possibilities**

With the introduction of new technologies that lead to the development of new systems of poultry breeding, have been promoted to the animals better thermal comfort conditions. This lessens the great challenge for industrial poultry, with regard to aviary constructions, resulting in increased productivity. It is known that an animal in heat stress conditions presents lower productive performance. A lower feed conversion caused by decreased feed intake is the main cause. Multidisciplinary studies have been developed seeking deepening the needs and possibilities already available about these new systems. With this, this review seeks to approach in a didactic and simplified way the planning and construction of aviary shed aiming to provide suitable thermal conditioning for broiler accommodation.

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2. **System for assessing broilers thermal comfort**

One of the ways to optimize animal production environments is through the understanding of the bioclimatic factors that are harmful to the animals. Among the techniques currently applied for measuring and analyzing bioclimatic factors, the vast majority demand that the producers and researchers have high level of technical skills, those techniques (e.g. using maps of spatial variability) hinder the rapid evaluation of certain environments. It is important to note that there is currently no software and hardware tool that allows for an on-site bioclimatic analysis, for example using an Android or iOS app. Thus, the present study was conducted with the objective of developing a system capable of collecting air temperature measurements (T_a), black globe temperature (T_g) and relative humidity (RH), to interact with Aurora mobile app, enabling the on-site development of maps with spatial variability of the air temperature and indices of thermal broilers comfort, using data interpolation. The system was developed through the creation of six transmitters and one receiver. The results obtained indicate that the system operated correctly and allows on-site analysis of thermal animal comfort. During the validation period a total of 48 maps were developed, considering the periods of morning and afternoon, and using the T_a , BGHI, and THI measurements. The maps allowed the on-site identification of regions with conditions of comfort, discomfort and thermal stress (both by heat and cold). According to the maps of thermal comfort indices, the afternoon period presented conditions that were often heat

stress. The maps of air temperature and thermal comfort indices allow the producers and researchers to have, at hand, a highly portable tool for evaluating the broilers welfare.

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3. **Positioning of sensors for control of ventilation systems in broiler houses: a case study**

Ventilation systems are incorporated at intensive poultry farms to control environment conditions and thermal comfort of broilers. The ventilation system operates based on environmental data, particularly measured by sensors of temperature and relative humidity. Sensors are placed at different positions of the facility. Quality, number and positioning of the sensors are critical factors to achieve an efficient performance of the system. For this reason, a strategic positioning of the sensors associated to controllers could support the maintenance and management of the microclimate inside the facility. This research aims to identify the three most representative points for the positioning of sensors in order to support the ventilation system during the critical period from 12h00 to 15h00 on summer days. Temperature, relative humidity and wind speed were measured in four different tunnel ventilated barns at the final stage of the production cycle. The descriptive analysis was performed on these data. The Temperature and Humidity Index (THI) was also calculated. Then, the geostatistical analysis of THI was performed by GS+ and the position of sensors was determined by ordinary kriging. The methodology was able to detect the most representative points for the positioning of sensors in a case study (southeastern Brazil). The results suggested that this strategic positioning would help controllers to obtain a better inference of the microclimate during the studied period (the hottest microclimate), considered critical in Brazil. In addition, these results allow developing a future road map for a decision support system based on 24 h monitoring of the ventilation systems in broiler houses.

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4. **Heat stress impacts on broiler performance: a systematic review and meta-analysis**

Heat stress (HS) is a major problem in poultry business which affects chickens' performance and may trigger large economic losses. This study intends to analyze the impact of HS on broiler chickens' performance compared with those under normal condition. A literature search was performed on PubMed, Web of Science, and Cochrane Library for studies published in English up to January 17, 2020. Outcomes of body weight gain (BWG), feed intake (FI), feed conversion ratio (FCR), and mortality were calculated by weighted difference (WMD) or odds ratio (OR) with 95% confidence interval (CI). A total of 12 studies with 470 broiler chickens were included. HS significantly decreased FI (11 trials: WMD = -97.95, 95% CI: -141.70, -54.20) and BWG (7 trials: WMD = -151.40, 95% CI: -198.59, -104.21) and significantly increased FCR (9 trials: WMD = 0.17, 95% CI: 0.04, 0.29) and mortality (8 trials: OR = 3.74, 95% CI: 1.39, 10.12) compared with the control. In conclusion, HS significantly affected broiler chickens' BWG, FI, FCR, and mortality, indicating the importance to control housing temperature to avoid unnecessary costs.

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5. **Impact of Heating Systems on Air and Litter Quality in Broiler Houses, Performance, Behavior, and Immunity in Broiler Chickens**

Achieving optimum thermoneutral zone in broiler houses provokes enhanced performance, productivity, and welfare. The influence of different heating systems on microclimatic air quality, litter abiotic, performance, behavior, some carcass characteristics, intestinal microbiota, E. coli & Salmonella isolation, immunoglobulin concentrations, and cortisol levels

in broilers was studied. Two hundred one-day-old female Ross® 308 broilers were divided into four groups (50 each) in four independent rooms (G1, G2, G3, and G4) supplied with gas-operated, halogen, oil, and portable air conditioner heaters, respectively. A total of 1520 samples including 200 litter, 200 air, 160 sera, 160 intestinal swabs, 160 breast muscles, and 640 organ samples including liver, spleen, heart, and bursa of Fabricius were collected. The results revealed highly significant declines ($P < 0.01$) of carbon dioxide and ammonia concentrations, litter pH and moisture percentages, feed conversions, water intakes, locomotion & panting behaviors, alanine aminotransferase, aspartate aminotransferase, urea, creatinine, total bacterial and Enterobacteriaceae counts, E. coli and Salmonella isolation and counts, and cortisol levels, as well as, highly significant increases ($P < 0.01$) of weight gains, performance indices, live weights, feeding & resting behaviors, carcass and organs weights, total protein, albumin, and immunoglobulin concentrations in broilers raised with oil and portable air conditioner heaters rather than those reared with a gas-operated torch and halogen heaters. The study concluded that using an advanced and clean source of heat as oil or air conditioner heaters can meet the broiler's microclimatic requirements without representing a source of stress on birds.

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6. Ammonia concentrations, litter quality, performance and some welfare parameters of broilers kept on different bedding materials

Litter quality has been related to broiler performance, behaviour, welfare, dust and ammonia (NH₃) emissions. Drier litter leads to a reduction in NH₃ emissions and reduces the formation of foot- and hock lesions. However, maintaining good litter quality is often challenging. This study investigated the effects of different bedding materials on litter quality and NH₃ concentrations at litter level, broiler performance, foot- and hock lesions, plumage cleanliness and breast skin irritation. A total of 2160 Ross 308 male broilers were randomly assigned to 36 floor pens. There were six replications for each of the following six litter treatments: wood shavings, flax, peat, maize silage, chopped wheat straw and flax pellets. For the total period, the highest feed intake and body weight was obtained for broilers housed on peat. The NH₃ concentrations measured at litter level was highest for peat and chopped wheat straw at 36 d of age and numerically the lowest for flax at 30 and 36 d of age. Maize silage remained friable, but did not result in lower NH₃ concentrations compared to wood shavings. Chopped wheat straw and wood shavings gave rise to the highest incidence of foot lesions at 38 d of age, while broilers kept on flax, peat, maize silage and flax pellets had the lowest incidence of foot lesions at the end of the rearing period. The results of the current study suggest a complicated relationship between the type of bedding material, litter conditions and NH₃ volatilised from the litter.

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7. Sprinkler Technology Improves Broiler Production Sustainability: From Stress Alleviation to Water Usage Conservation: A Mini Review

Global poultry production is facing several challenges including a projected increase in global demand for high quality animal proteins and the need to adapt to environmental contrasts including heat stress and the increasing pressure on natural resource (water, land, and energy) availability. Heat stress is one of the most challenging stressor to poultry production because of its strong adverse effects on welfare, production, mortality, and water usage. Most commercial poultry houses worldwide are equipped with a combination of tunnel ventilation and evaporative cooling system (pads, fogging, or low-pressure misting systems) as the status quo to overcome heat stress. Despite prior investments in these systems, critical problems continue to impede poultry production efficiency, which still declines during hot seasons. In fact, these systems tend to saturate the barn air with moisture (>70% relative humidity) which is counterproductive to the bird's own physiological ability to cool

itself by hyperventilation (evaporative heat loss). The second challenge with these systems is the significant amount of water usage. This review will summarize some of the benefits of surface wetting of birds through sprinkler technology (SPRINK) that has higher efficiency to maintain birds' comfort with significantly less use of cooling water. Despite higher air temperature and lower relative humidity in the sprinkler house, the SPRINK decreased broiler body core temperature, reduced systemic and intracellular stress, preserved intracellular energy, and averaged six points better FCR compared to evaporative cooling system.

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8. The reduction of gas concentrations in broiler houses through ventilation: Assessment of the thermal and electrical energy consumption

Ammonia and carbon dioxide are the most relevant among the harmful gases present in broiler houses and their effects on animal health depend on concentration and exposure time. Inside these houses, increasing ventilation is the most common strategy adopted to control the concentration of these gases. This strategy is effective but increases electrical energy consumption (for fan operation) and thermal energy consumption (for inlet air heating). In this work, the variations of energy consumption due to the increase of ventilation to maintain ammonia and carbon dioxide concentrations below established thresholds were evaluated. To carry out this analysis, various parameters (e.g. indoor air temperature and gas concentrations) of a broiler house located in the Mediterranean area were monitored during a production cycle in the cool (winter) season in which outdoor air temperature varied between 2 and 25 °C. The assessment of the increase in the energy consumption for climate control was carried out using the Specific Fan Performance and a customised building energy simulation model. The analysis showed that during the monitored period, the established thresholds of gas concentrations were exceeded approximately 60% of the time. To maintain the desired gas concentrations, the ventilation flow rate should be increased by 9%. This variation in the ventilation flow rate entailed a rise in the energy consumption by about 10% for electrical energy and by about 14% for thermal energy. Maintaining the gas concentration below the established thresholds entails an extra cost of around 0.02 € per harvested broiler.

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9. Technology and Poultry Welfare

Consideration of animal welfare is essential to address the consumers' demands and for the long-term sustainability of commercial poultry. However, assessing welfare in large poultry flocks, to be able to detect potential welfare risks and to control or minimize its impact is difficult. Current developments in technology and mathematical modelling open new possibilities for real-time automatic monitoring of animal welfare and health. New technological innovations potentially adaptable to commercial poultry are appearing, although their practical implementation is still being defined. In this paper, we review the latest technological developments with potential to be applied to poultry welfare, especially for broiler chickens and laying hens. Some of the examples that are presented and discussed include the following: sensors for farm environmental monitoring, movement, or physiological parameters; imaging technologies such as optical flow to detect gait problems and feather pecking; infrared technologies to evaluate birds' thermoregulatory features and metabolism changes, that may be indicative of welfare, health and management problems. All these technologies have the potential to be implemented at the commercial level to improve birds' welfare and to optimize flock management, therefore, improving the efficiency of the system in terms of use of resources and, thus, long term sustainability.

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10. Impacts of projected climate change scenarios on heating and cooling demand for industrial broiler chicken farming in the Eastern U.S

Industrial poultry production is a resource-intensive activity due to specific indoor temperature requirements to ensure optimal chicken growth. The energy consumption to maintain this ideal microclimate demands substantial operating expenses that are subject to climate conditions. As such, energy demand for heating and cooling (HVAC) for commercial broiler chicken production may be influenced by increased temperatures that occur due to climate change. This study focuses on evaluating the effects of climate change on future HVAC demands in a typical commercial broiler house in the Eastern U.S. To estimate such demands, we developed a simplified thermodynamic model that uses downscaled air temperature as input. These inputs stemmed from twenty General Circulation Models (GCM) for business-as-usual (RCP 8.5) and moderate (RCP 4.5) climate change scenarios. Our results indicate that increased temperatures from climate change scenarios by mid-century will increase energy demand for cooling by $5.5 \pm 1.8\%$ (RCP 4.5) and $6.6 \pm 2.1\%$ (RCP 8.5), and reduce energy demand for heating by $9.0 \pm 3.2\%$ (RCP 4.5) and $10.3 \pm 3.7\%$ (RCP 8.5) with respect to 2018. Furthermore, our results suggest that warmer temperatures under climate change will substantially increase water withdrawals for evaporative cooling. However, there may be a point where cooling pads may not be efficient enough to cool down chickens and other innovative alternatives may be required. Such changes could include the use of air conditioning units, which would further increase electricity demand. Efficiency improvements that could mitigate some of the negative changes in energy demand could include increasing the size of the house, modifying the production schedule to minimize energy use, and adding insulation.

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4.3 List of practical knowledge sources

1. Profitable Practices: Poultry innovation improves bird health and reduces costs

Real Agriculture, 2025. <https://www.realagriculture.com/2025/02/profitable-practices-poultry-innovation-improves-bird-health-and-reduces-costs/>

[SUMMARY](#)

2. How the climate can negatively affect broiler health

The Poultry Site, 2021. <https://www.thepoultrysite.com/articles/how-the-climate-can-negatively-affect-broiler-health>

[SUMMARY](#)

3. CP Foods' High-Tech Broiler Farm Praised as Regional Benchmark for Smart Chicken Farming

Asian Food Journal, 2024. <https://asiafoodjournal.com/cp-foods-high-tech-broiler-farm-praised-smart-chicken-farming/>

[SUMMARY](#)

4. BEST PRACTICES FOR BROILER FARMING

UK Kenya Shipping. <https://ukkenyashipping.co.uk/best-practices-for-broiler-farming/>

[SUMMARY](#)

5. Best practice in broiler house management

ZOOTECNICA, 2021. <https://zootecnicainternational.com/featured/best-practice-in-broiler-house-management/>

SUMMARY

6. Climate in Poultry Houses

Poultry hub Australia, 2005. <https://www.poultryhub.org/all-about-poultry/husbandry-management/climate-in-poultry-houses>

SUMMARY

7. 10 Key Daily Management Practices for Successful Broiler Breeding | Boost Your Poultry Farm Efficiency

AGTech, 2024. <https://agtech.folio3.com/blogs/10-key-broiler-management-practices/>

SUMMARY

8. Best Practices for Broiler Brooding Management

Shambani College, 2017. <https://www.shambanicollege.com/blogs/broiler-brooding-best-management-practices>

SUMMARY

9. 15 management tips for better poultry performance potential

Alltech, 2018. <https://www.alltech.com/blog/15-management-tips-better-poultry-performance-potential>

SUMMARY

10. Best Practices for Poultry Litter Management

Ralco Agriculture, 2022. https://www.ralcoagriculture.com/post/best-practices-for-poultry-litter-management?srsId=AfmBOor74KjSMiiKpWBbacQerlfcVvXKO6ly0vdqnQhJTX_6sTUwbEm

SUMMARY

4.4 Informative summaries

1. Profitable Practices: Poultry innovation improves bird health and reduces costs

Summary Scott Buchan sees the impact of technology whenever he's watching his broiler chickens or looking at his hydro bills. For Buchan, who operates Buchrest Farms along with his family in Ontario's Waterloo Region, investing in technology and innovation plays a key role in making the operation more profitable and sustainable. Buchan notes that his energy bill is a clear indicator of the impact of technology on the farm. The installation of solar panels has led to a significant reduction in hydro bills and cooling technology has also helped create a more comfortable environment for birds, improving both health and welfare. On this episode of Profitable Practices, Buchan emphasizes the critical role the barn environment plays in the success of a chicken farm. Birds dislike significant temperature changes, so maintaining a consistent environment is crucial. He shares how an evaporative cooling system cools the barn by about 10 degrees using a car radiator-like mechanism and 60-inch cooling fans. The high air speed and water evaporation process keep the barn environment dry, preventing disease. It also helps improve feed efficiency as birds can eat throughout the day without being affected by extreme heat. The exterior of the barn also features a solar wall that uses sunlight to preheat incoming air, reducing the need for propane heat. Heat exchangers further optimize the system by using warm air to preheat cool air, reducing external heat requirements by 40 to 45 per cent. There's also energy efficient LED lighting and a series of tree wind breaks which minimize wind exposure and reduce heat requirements

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2. How the climate can negatively affect broiler health

Broiler well-being is significantly affected by the house climate. Draughts, harmful gases and incorrect temperatures can all compromise the birds' immune systems. As a result, inconsistencies when creating the right climate can leave the birds susceptible to viral and bacterial infections, thus leading to losses. Although this is the worst-case scenario, smaller and less noticeable losses are also possible, including reduced daily weight gains and a low feed conversion rate.

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3. CP Foods' High-Tech Broiler Farm Praised as Regional Benchmark for Smart Chicken Farming

SuThailand's Department of Livestock Development, in collaboration with the Asian Productivity Organization (APO) members, including government officials, lecturers, farmers, and experts from 19 countries, lauded CP Foods' "Kroksomboon" Broiler Farm for its outstanding adoption of smart farming technology. This farm has successfully enhanced productivity using innovative digital solutions while upholding animal welfare standards. The insights and best practices gained will be disseminated to boost small-scale farmers throughout the Asia Pacific region, thereby aiding in regional food security.

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4. BEST PRACTICES FOR BROILER FARMING

Overview about management of monitoring behaviour, barn climate, feeding and others.

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5. Best practice in broiler house management

How the right technology and proactive management can ensure best practice in housing on broiler farms

In partnership with Cobb, this article examines best practice in broiler production, focusing specifically on housing. How can producers create an environment for their birds that consistently fosters excellent performance and robust animal health?

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6. Climate in Poultry Houses

The climate in poultry houses influences the wellbeing and health of humans as well as the birds. Respiratory, digestive and behavioural disorders are more likely to occur in houses in which the climatic conditions are not up to standard. The efficiency with which feed is utilised is related to the health status of the flock. Animals that are not healthy cannot be expected to perform optimally. The younger the animals are or the higher their production level, the more sensitive they become to the climatic conditions in the house. Climate can be defined as the sum of environmental factors which influence the functioning of man and animal.

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7. 10 Key Daily Management Practices for Successful Broiler Breeding | Boost Your Poultry Farm Efficiency

This blog dives deep into the heart of successful broiler breeding, highlighting the 10 key daily broiler management practices you need to prioritize. When you incorporate these essential routines into your farm operations, you'll be well on your way to raising healthy, productive broiler flocks and maximizing your poultry farm's efficiency.

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8. Best Practices for Broiler Brooding Management

Dr. Scott Gillingham, a poultry veterinarian with over 30 years of experience across Canada, shares valuable insights on effective broiler chicken farming practices, focusing on brooding parameters to optimise chick health and growth.

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9. 15 management tips for better poultry performance potential

Achieving good bird, barn and gut health requires operational excellence and attention to detail. A combination of quality nutrition, veterinary guidance, and increased consideration of barn and bird management will help to ensure birds have the best possible chance to perform at their maximum potential.

The acronym “FLAWS” has commonly served as a reminder to check feed, light, litter, air, water, (bio)security, sanitation, space and staff. FLAWS actually serves as a detailed approach to best management practices, not only during brooding but throughout the life of the flock.

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10. Best Practices for Poultry Litter Management

The period between when broilers go to market and when the next flock comes into the barn is referred to as downtime. However, this is far from a period of inactivity as managing a broiler flock does not begin when the first chick is placed but instead right after the previous flock ends.

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Chapter 5 Improving on-farm welfare assessment and management

5.1 List of scientific knowledge sources

1. Welfare of broilers on farm

Nielsen, S.S., Alvarez, J., Bicout, D.J., Calistri, P., Canali, E., Drewe, J.A., Garin-Bastuji, B., Rojas, J.L., Schmidt, C.G., Herskin, M.S., Chueca, M.A., Padalino, B., Pasquali, P., Roberts, H.C., Spooler, H., Stahl, K., Velarde, A., Viltrop, A., Winckler, C., Tiemann, I., Jong, I. de, Gebhardt-Henrich, S.G., Keeling, L., Riber, AB, Ashe, S., Candiani, D., Matas, R.G., Hempen, M., Mosbach-Schulz, O., Gimeno, C.R., van der Stede, Y., Vitali, M., Bailly-Caumette, E., Michel, V. EFSA Panel Animal Health and Welfare. 2023. EFSA J. 21, 1–236. DOI: [10.2903/j.efsa.2023.7788](https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2023.7788)

ABSTRACT

2. How Are Information Technologies Addressing Broiler Welfare? A Systematic Review Based on the Welfare Quality® Assessment

Rios, H.V., Waquil, P.D, Soster de Carvalho, P., Norton, T. 2020. Sustainability, 12 (4), p. 1413. DOI: [10.3390/su12041413](https://doi.org/10.3390/su12041413). DOI: [10.3390/su12041413](https://doi.org/10.3390/su12041413)

ABSTRACT

3. Implementation of the Welfare Quality® broiler assessment protocol – final report

de Jong, I.C., Gunnink, H., Hindle, V. 2014. Project number BO-20-008-002.05. Wageningen Livestock Research. Report

ABSTRACT

4. Poultry welfare monitoring: group-level technologies

Dawkins, M.S., Rowe, E. 2020. In: Nicol, C. (Ed.), Understanding the behaviour and improving the welfare of chickens. Burleigh Dodds Science Publishing, Philadelphia, PA, pp. 177–196. DOI: [10.1201/9781003048039](https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003048039)

ABSTRACT

5. Smart Farming: A Review of Animal-Based Measuring Technologies for Broiler Welfare Assessment

Azarpajouh, S., Weimer, S.L., Calderón Díaz, J.A., Taheri, H. 2022. CABI Reviews, Article 033. DOI: [10.1079/cabireviews202217033](https://doi.org/10.1079/cabireviews202217033)

ABSTRACT

6. Poultry health monitoring and management: bone and skin health in broilers

Caplen, G. 2020. In: Nicol, C. (Ed.), Understanding the behaviour and improving the welfare of chickens. Burleigh Dodds Science Publishing, Philadelphia, PA, pp. 603–652. DOI: [10.1201/9781003048039](https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003048039)

ABSTRACT

7. Improving welfare assessment indicators and protocols for poultry

Keeling, L. 2020. In: Nicol, C. (Ed.), Understanding the behaviour and improving the welfare of chickens. Burleigh Dodds Science Publishing, Philadelphia, PA, pp. 197–224. DOI: [10.1201/9781003048039](https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003048039)

ABSTRACT

8. Reliability, practicability and farmers' acceptance of an animal welfare assessment protocol for broiler chickens and turkeys

Michaelis, S., Gieseke, D., Knierim, U. 2024. Poult. Sci., 103(10). DOI: [10.1016/j.psj.2024.103900](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2024.103900)

ABSTRACT

9. Positive Welfare Indicators and Their Association with Sustainable Management Systems in Poultry

Papageorgiou, M., Goliomytis, M., Tzamaloukas, O., Miltiadou, D., Simitzis, P. 2023. Sustainability, 15(14). DOI: [10.3390/su151410890](https://doi.org/10.3390/su151410890)

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10. Real-time monitoring of broiler flock's welfare status using camera-based technology

Fernández, A. P., Norton, T., Tullo, E., van Hertem, T., Youssef, A., Exadaktylos, V., Vranken, E., Guarino, M., Berckmans, D. 2018. Biosyst. Eng., 173. DOI: [10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2018.05.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2018.05.008)

ABSTRACT

5.2 Informative abstracts

1. Welfare of broilers on farm

This Scientific Opinion considers the welfare of domestic fowl (*Gallus gallus*) related to the production of meat (broilers) and includes the keeping of day-old chicks, broiler breeders, and broiler chickens. Currently used husbandry systems in the EU are described. Overall, 19 highly relevant welfare consequences (WCs) were identified based on severity, duration and frequency of occurrence: 'bone lesions', 'cold stress', 'gastro-enteric disorders', 'group stress', 'handling stress', 'heat stress', 'isolation stress', 'inability to perform comfort behaviour', 'inability to perform exploratory or foraging behaviour', 'inability to avoid unwanted sexual behaviour', 'locomotory disorders', 'prolonged hunger', 'prolonged thirst', 'predation stress', 'restriction of movement', 'resting problems', 'sensory under- and overstimulation', 'soft tissue and integument damage' and 'umbilical disorders'. These WCs and their animal-based measures (ABMs) that can identify them are described in detail. A variety of hazards related to the different husbandry systems were identified as well as ABMs for assessing the different WCs. Measures to prevent or correct the hazards and/or mitigate each of the WCs are listed. Recommendations are provided on quantitative or qualitative criteria to answer specific questions on the welfare of broilers and related to genetic selection, temperature, feed and water restriction, use of cages, light, air quality and mutilations in breeders such as beak trimming, de-toeing and comb dubbing. In addition, minimal requirements (e.g. stocking density, group size, nests, provision of litter, perches and platforms, drinkers and feeders, of covered veranda and outdoor range) for an enclosure for keeping broiler chickens (fast-growing, slower-growing and broiler breeders) are recommended. Finally, 'total mortality', 'wounds', 'carcass condemnation' and 'footpad dermatitis' are proposed as indicators for monitoring at slaughter the welfare of broilers on-farm.

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2. How Are Information Technologies Addressing Broiler Welfare? A Systematic Review Based on the Welfare Quality® Assessment

This systematic review aims to explore how information technologies (ITs) are currently used to monitor the welfare of broiler chickens. The question posed for the review was “which ITs are related to welfare and how do they monitor this for broilers?”. The Welfare Quality® (WQ) protocol for broiler assessment was utilized as a framework to analyse suitable articles. A total of 57 studies were reviewed wherein all principles of broiler welfare were addressed. The “good health” principle was the main criteria found to be addressed by ITs and IT-based studies (45.6% and 46.1%, respectively), whereas the least observed principle was “good feeding” (8.8%). This review also classified ITs and IT-based studies by their utilization (location, production system, variable measured, aspect of production, and experimental/practical use). The results show that the current focus of ITs is on problems with conventional production systems and that less attention has been given to free-range systems, slaughterhouses, and supply chain issues. Given the valuable results evidenced by the exploitation of ITs, their use in broiler production should continue to be encouraged with more attention given to farmer adoption strategies.

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3. Implementation of the Welfare Quality® Broiler assessment protocol – final report

This report presents the final results of the project ‘Implementation of the Welfare Quality® (WQ) broiler assessment protocol’ with respect to two topics:

- potential for use of the animal-based measures of the WQ broiler welfare assessment protocol as outcome-based measures for broiler welfare, based on WUR-LR experience with the Welfare Quality® broiler assessment protocol (chapter 2);
- a general discussion regarding the Welfare Quality® broiler assessment protocol as indicator of broiler welfare on-farm: possibilities for simplification, the relevance of current protocol measures and the Welfare Quality® aggregation model, including suggestions on how the assessment protocol can be applied in practice (chapter 3).

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4. Poultry welfare monitoring: group-level technologies

In one sense, the health and welfare of commercial poultry is already highly automated. Modern broiler houses, for example, have sophisticated climate control systems that keep birds within the temperature and humidity guidelines recommended by the breeding companies (Yahav et al., 2005; Jones et al., 2005), delivery of food and water is automated and alarms are fitted to ensure a constant supply and light is regulated for both intensity and photoperiod (Corkery et al., 2013). There are environmental sensors to measure temperature (D'Alfonso et al., 1996; Carvalho et al., 2013; Coelho et al., 2016; Curi et al., 2017), ambient dust (Zhao et al., 2009), relative humidity (Carvalho et al., 2013; Coelho et al., 2016; Curi et al., 2017), vibration (Chen et al., 2010), ammonia concentration (Ji et al., 2016) and carbon dioxide concentration (Carvalho et al., 2013; Ji et al., 2016). In other words, the birds' basic needs for food, water and physical comfort can be catered for automatically (Fournel et al., 2017), thus fulfilling at least some of the requirements for good welfare as set out in the Five Freedoms (Brambell, 1965; Webster, 2001), Welfare Quality® (2009), World Organization for Animal Health General Principles (Fraser et al., 2013) and other welfare systems.

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5. Smart Farming: A Review of Animal-Based Measuring Technologies for Broiler Welfare Assessment

The growing world population has increased the demand for meat production and has led to a rapid growth in the scale of broiler enterprises globally. Poultry producers need to implement several changes in their production systems to supply the increasing demand for poultry products while considering farming sustainability and ensuring high standards of animal welfare. The recent advancement in technology and engineering tools and materials, such as advanced sensors and sensing devices, data processing, and machine learning methods, provides effective tools for the broiler industry to monitor broiler welfare indicators. This review paper will (a) explain smart broiler farming, (b) describe on-farm broiler welfare assessment, and (c) explore on-farm applications of smart technologies that can be used as animal-based welfare assessment tools.

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6. Poultry health monitoring and management: bone and skin health in broilers

High lameness and contact dermatitis levels persist within intensively reared broiler flocks; a consequence of long-term genetic selection for ambitious production parameters. Key welfare issues include pain, reduced mobility and increased susceptibility to additional pathologies. Fully understanding the risk factors for these disorders is important so that effective management strategies can be implemented. Genetics is key to improving leg and skin health; most conditions can be selected against in breeding programmes, while greater utilisation of slow-growing strains would immediately benefit welfare. Wet litter is largely responsible for contact dermatitis, yet with strict environmental management it is possible to maintain litter quality, even under high stocking densities. Utilisation of enrichment (to encourage activity), and sequential feeding regimes, have the potential to improve leg health and confer economic benefits. It is hoped that automated video surveillance systems will soon utilise flock behaviour to monitor foot and leg health and highlight impending welfare problems.

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7. Improving welfare assessment indicators and protocols for poultry

There have been considerable advances in welfare assessment in the past decades. This chapter explains some of the terminology related to welfare assessment and why the emphasis is moving towards including indicators of poultry welfare taken on the birds themselves rather than from the environment. It also reviews some of the more commonly used laying hen and broiler welfare assessment indicators, focusing on those that reflect the behaviour of birds. Among the clinical indicators discussed are assessments of pecking damage and bird cleanliness. Behaviour indicators include those that are recorded from undisturbed birds, such as vocalisation, and those that use a test situation. A welfare assessment protocol is a description of the procedures to collect the indicators. In the final sections of this chapter, methods to prioritise between different indicators, depending on the purpose of the assessment, and future trends to improve poultry welfare assessment are discussed.

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8. Reliability, practicability and farmers' acceptance of an animal welfare assessment protocol for broiler chickens and turkeys

This study presents an evaluation of on-farm self-assessment using animal-based indicators to support fattening poultry farmers in managing the welfare of their animals. Self-assessment guidelines elaborated by a German expert group were evaluated together with 11 trained broiler and 11 trained turkey farmers. The participating farmers tested a protocol

with 18 indicators for broilers and a protocol with 20 indicators for turkeys on their farms for 1 y. The reliability of individual animal scoring, the practicability of the protocols, their implementation, and acceptance were then evaluated. Reliability was tested during 2 farm visits by the accompanying scientists, using the scientist as a silver standard. On average, the farmers achieved very good reliability (mean PABAK - prevalence-adjusted and bias-adjusted kappa, broilers: 0.90; turkeys: 0.86), with no detectable influence of the previous training method (online versus in-person), the first versus the second visit of the scientists, the fattening stage of the animals scored, number of animals on the farm or the farmers' professional background. The assessment took longer at the end of the fattening period for both animal species. On farms with more personnel and for farmers with a higher position on farm, the assessment was easier to integrate into their work. Most farmers did not fully document their self-assessment and almost no farmer processed and evaluated the data properly, even though it seemed interesting to them. Overall, there was only moderate acceptance of the welfare self-assessment approach, with mixed responses as to whether it provided early warning information or benefits to animal management. Farmers often pointed to the increased cost associated with carrying out self-assessments in terms of the additional working time required, which is likely to be an important barrier to continuing. Digital applications for data recording, processing and evaluation may help to overcome barriers. Overall, it appears unlikely that the welfare self-assessment approach will be widely implemented in the poultry fattening sector without further incentives.

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9. Positive Welfare Indicators and Their Association with Sustainable Management Systems in Poultry

Animal welfare is a key and distinct component of sustainable agriculture and food security. People, both as citizens and consumers, have become more concerned about the husbandry of livestock species. Positive welfare goes a step further than the common welfare approach, supporting that a good life for animals is not only the alleviation of negative aspects, but also the promotion of positive affectivities. So, a sustainable management system for any livestock species should promote positive aspects in the lives of animals. Poultry is one of the species whose welfare is most impaired, and numerous concerns are raised by society. For all the above, we reviewed the positive welfare indicators that have been studied in livestock poultry and that can be used to promote positive effects and assess welfare for the most common species, i.e., broilers, laying hens, turkeys, ducks, geese, quails and ostriches. We analyzed the results categorized by species, discussed the connection of the indicators with sustainable management, and made proposals for future studies. Exploration and dustbathing have been extensively studied and seem most promising, especially in broilers and laying hens, followed by nesting and perching, and swimming for waterfowl. Qualitative behavioral assessment (QBA) is already applied in protocols for broilers and laying hens, but the results are not as promising due to the homogeneity of the flock and the difficulty in observations. Play has been studied mostly in broilers but is a behavior difficult to recognize and needs further understanding. The results are limited for all species, except broilers and laying hens.

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10. Real-time monitoring of broiler flock's welfare status using camera-based technology

Broiler activity and occupation patterns are of special interest to farmers during visual inspection. However, this is time consuming and precision livestock farming (PLF) technologies can enable the monitoring of such key flock behavioural indicators in a continuous and automated way in the house. The aim is to show how the welfare status of the poultry flock can be evaluated by real-time monitoring of activity and occupation

patterns. Four top view cameras were installed in a commercial broiler house for 9 complete growing cycles. The cameras recorded images continuously and they were translated into numerical values of activity and occupation indices each minute. Three welfare assessments were performed in weeks 3, 4 and 5 of each growing cycle according to the standardised Welfare Quality® assessment protocol for broiler chickens. A real-time dynamic model was developed to monitor and forecast the time evolution of these indices and the confidence intervals for normal behaviour over each growing cycle. Statistically relevant correlations ($p < 0.05$) between the time birds spent in an alert situation during the growing cycle and the percentage of birds showing worse welfare scores were found for occupation deviations and foot pad lesions ($R^2 \approx 0.60$) and activity deviations and hock burns ($R^2 \approx 0.70$). Furthermore, these deviations can be located inside the poultry house through the relation between activity and occupation indices in specific areas associated with particular broiler behaviours, such as feeding, drinking and resting. Evaluating this relation, regular activity and occupation patterns for each behaviour were defined. This work shows that it is possible to link deviations in activity and occupation patterns of broiler flocks in commercial farms with the welfare assessment scores by human experts. This tool allows the farmer to evaluate the risk of welfare issues in the flock and to get early warnings about which bird behaviours are affected and the location in the house where these alerts are being triggered.

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5.3 List of practical knowledge sources

1. Welfare, smart farming and artificial intelligence in poultry

Poultry World. 2025. <https://www.poultryworld.net/the-industrymarkets/market-trends-analysis-the-industrymarkets-2/welfare-smart-farming-and-artificial-intelligence-in-poultry/>

[SUMMARY](#)

2. Animal Welfare and Artificial Intelligence: A Combination of the Poultry Present or Future?

AviNews. 2024. <https://avinews.com/en/animal-welfare-and-artificial-intelligence/>

[SUMMARY](#)

3. Artificial intelligence automates poultry welfare monitoring

WATTPoultry. 2021. <https://www.wattagnet.com/broilers-turkeys/broilers/article/15533664/artificial-intelligence-automates-poultry-welfare-monitoring>

[SUMMARY](#)

4. Balancing poultry welfare with efficiency and technology

Poultry World. 2025. <https://www.poultryworld.net/the-industrymarkets/market-trends-analysis-the-industrymarkets-2/balancing-bird-welfare-with-efficiency-and-technology/>

[SUMMARY](#)

5. Poultry carcass tool helps to advance bird welfare

Poultry World. 2024. <https://www.poultryworld.net/specials/poultry-carcass-tool-helps-to-advance-bird-welfare/>

[SUMMARY](#)

6. Broiler welfare can be monitored with imaging technology

WATTPoultry. 2024. <https://www.wattagnet.com/broilers-turkeys/broilers/article/15670259/broiler-welfare-can-be-monitored-with-imaging-technology>

[SUMMARY](#)

7. Ethical Challenges in the Broiler Value Chain

AviNews. 2025. <https://avinews.com/en/ethical-challenges-in-the-broiler-value-chain/>

[SUMMARY](#)

8. New Aviagen apps join toolbox of management resources

Poultry World. 2021. <https://www.poultryworld.net/health-nutrition/new-aviagen-apps-join-toolbox-of-management-resources/>

[SUMMARY](#)

9. Research: Camera technology advantageous for broiler welfare

Poultry World. 2011. <https://www.poultryworld.net/poultry/research-camera-technology-advantageous-for-broiler-welfare/>

[SUMMARY](#)

10. Sound analysis of broilers to be explored to boost health and welfare

Poultry World. 2019. <https://www.poultryworld.net/health-nutrition/sound-analysis-of-broilers-to-be-explored-to-boost-health-and-welfare/>

[SUMMARY](#)

5.4 Informative summaries

1. **Welfare, smart farming and artificial intelligence in poultry**

Smart farming, including applications of artificial intelligence (AI), has the potential to improve farm animal welfare in many ways, but practically achieving this depends on a number of external factors. British biologist and professor of ethology at the University of Oxford, Marian Dawkins, said for technology to deliver on its promise of being able to improve the lives of animals, 3 conditions needed to be met. These are: 1) Both the public and the agricultural industry must be satisfied that automated measures of welfare can capture what is meant by 'good welfare'. 2) There is scientific evidence that the technology genuinely improves animal welfare when deployed on commercial farms. 3) There are demonstrable financial, environmental and other benefits as well as welfare so that industry is commercially worthwhile. So, the key message is that investment in technology that improves animal welfare is unlikely to be used by commercial producers unless it can be demonstrated to give a return on investment and satisfy other requirements such as lower environmental impacts and greater food safety. Whenever improving welfare costs money, someone has to pay. Working out who and how much calls for imaginative business models that will determine whether technology designed to measure and improve animal welfare does or does not get used on commercial farms.

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2. **Animal Welfare and Artificial Intelligence: A Combination of the Poultry Present or Future?**

Interest in animal welfare has increased over the years and is likely to remain on the agenda of producers and consumers of animal products. The interest and evaluation of welfare has transcended theoretical concepts such as the five freedoms and has been applied in the development of new ones such as artificial intelligence. The aim of this article is to highlight key concepts in welfare assessment and to point out some scientific advances for its evaluation by means of artificial intelligence.

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3. Artificial intelligence automates poultry welfare monitoring

HKScan used a combination of artificial intelligence and smart cameras to identify and monitor broiler activity, welfare and behavior in a recent pilot project. The data collection approach has already been used on two flocks of birds and has revealed variations in behavior as the birds age. For example, younger birds preen themselves more, while the older broilers were more apt to prefer bathing or scratching and pecking the litter.

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4. Balancing poultry welfare with efficiency and technology

Technology has an increasingly important role to play in maintaining the balance between welfare and efficiency, and poultry farmers will need to continue to adapt and harness its benefits as they navigate the opportunities and challenges ahead. There are 3 key challenges for the UK broiler industry as it enters 2025. Firstly, last autumn's budget, including changes to inheritance tax rules, caused significant concern for many farming businesses. For poultry farmers specifically, the threat of avian influenza (AI) looms, particularly during winter and, thirdly, the move to lower bird stocking densities will require careful management throughout the supply chain. In all cases, good stockmanship remains the priority. Unless somebody does something with the information, it's just information and we don't gain improvements. It is important to bring farmers along the journey and fully explain how technology works with their existing set-up, to ensure they feel comfortable with it as a valuable tool to improve the welfare, efficiency and profitability of their business.

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5. Poultry carcass tool helps to advance bird welfare

As consumers continue to rely on poultry protein, broiler welfare has become a top interest alongside dependable product quality. An advanced scoring and benchmarking tool helps to actively improve welfare and reduce losses in poultry production. While many improvements have been made in genetics and management of broilers, we still deal with certain welfare challenges, including (intestinal) diseases, respiratory problems, skin integrity loss, and stressors such as heat, handling and transportation. If unaddressed or undetected, these challenges lead to additional issues in poultry welfare and lower profitability throughout the supply chain. Broilers experiencing health issues or stress in the grow house are less efficient and can yield a lower-quality product at the processing plant. To produce a high-calibre product, we need to monitor meat quality at the packing plant and make sure the correct welfare conditions are in place throughout the broiler's life. It is not enough to identify carcass lesions on the rail with cameras and sensors. These devices cannot look inside the bird to provide the complete picture needed to connect pre-mortem flock health and welfare with post-mortem carcass quality. Instead, we must take a forensic approach to know why a lesion occurred and pinpoint the specific moment in production that caused it. This information allows us to establish actionable next steps, improve processes and results and uncover more profit potential.

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6. Broiler welfare can be monitored with imaging technology

Computer vision system that involves a cameras evaluating the side and top views of a flock can assist poultry producers in monitoring broiler welfare and production related behaviors. The system uses deep learning technology and algorithms to automatically identify welfare- and production- related behaviors, including lameness, preening, stretching, eating and drinking, allowing producers to better manage birds and compare flocks and management practices.

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7. Ethical Challenges in the Broiler Value Chain

The broiler industry is a crucial pillar of India's agricultural economy, ensuring food security, employment, and rural development. However, ethical concerns surrounding animal welfare, feed sourcing, worker rights, environmental sustainability, and consumer transparency continue to challenge the industry. As the sector grows, addressing these ethical issues is critical for long-term sustainability and global competitiveness.

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8. New Aviagen apps join toolbox of management resources

Aviagen has recently introduced flock management apps for Arbor Acres, Indian River and Ross customers across the globe. Providing instant access to Parent Stock and broiler information, the apps are available in 16 languages. Aviagen's goal is to provide practical advice and information to support them in their continuous endeavour to optimise the performance, health and welfare of their flocks. Now new Arbor Acres, Indian River and Ross apps can become part of their flock management toolbox. Available in 16 different languages, the apps put valuable management, benchmarking and other handy tools in the palm of their hands, anytime and from anywhere.

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9. Research: Camera technology advantageous for broiler welfare

Research by the Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC) Animal Welfare Programme have discovered a small-scale camera and computer set-up that is poised to improve the welfare of farm animals, in particular, broiler chickens.

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10. Sound analysis of broilers to be explored to boost health and welfare

Researchers are to look at sound analysis of broiler chickens to see what they can tell about the health, welfare and productivity of birds during their lifetime. No significant difference was shown between expected and observed weights along the entire production cycles. The identified model used to predict the weight as a function of the peak frequency confirmed that bird weight might be predicted by the frequency analysis of the sounds emitted at farm level.

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Chapter 6 Optimizing young chick management

6.1 List of scientific knowledge sources

1. Effect of transportation duration of 1-day-old chicks on postplacement production performances and pododermatitis of broilers up to slaughter age

Bergoug, H., Guinebretière, M., Tong, Q., Roulston, N., Romanini, C.E.B., Exadaktylos, V., Berckmans, D., Garain, P., Demmers, T.G.M., McGonnell, I.M., Bahr, C., Burel, C., Eterradossi, N., Michel, V. 2013. Poult. Sci. 92, 3300–3309. DOI: [10.3382/ps.2013-03118](https://doi.org/10.3382/ps.2013-03118)

[ABSTRACT](#)

2. Resting behavior of broilers reared with or without artificial brooders

Forslind, S., Hernandez, C.E., Riber, A.B., Wall, H., Blokhuis, H.J. 2022. Front. Vet. Sci. 9,908196. DOI: [10.3389/fvets.2022.908196](https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2022.908196)

[ABSTRACT](#)

3. A 'meta-analysis' of effects of post-hatch food and water deprivation on development, performance and welfare of chickens

Jong, I.C. de, van Riel, J., Bracke, M.B.M., van den Brand, H. 2017. PloS one 12, e0189350. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0189350](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0189350)

[ABSTRACT](#)

4. Opportunities to improve the welfare of young chickens

Haas, E.N. de, 2020. In: Nicol, C. (Ed.), Understanding the behaviour and improving the welfare of chickens. Burleigh Dodds Science Publishing, Philadelphia, PA, pp. 261–312. DOI: [10.1201/9781003048039](https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003048039)

[ABSTRACT](#)

5. Health, welfare and lifetime performance implications of alternative hatching and early life management systems for broiler chickens

Hanna, H., Richmond, A., Lavery, U., O'Connell, N.E. 2024. PloS one 19, e0303351. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0303351](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0303351)

[ABSTRACT](#)

6. Effects of early nutrition and sanitary conditions on antibody levels in early and later life of broiler chickens

Hollemans, M.S., Vries Reilingh, G. de, Vries, S. de, Parmentier, H.K., Lammers, A. 2021. Developmental and comparative immunology 117, 103954. DOI: [10.1016/j.dci.2020.103954](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dci.2020.103954)

[ABSTRACT](#)

7. Effects of early nutrition and transport of 1-day-old chickens on production performance and fear response

Hollemans, M.S., Vries, S. de, Lammers, A., Clouard, C. 2018. Poult. Sci. 97, 2534–2542. DOI: [10.3382/ps/pey106](https://doi.org/10.3382/ps/pey106)

[ABSTRACT](#)

8. **Effect of post-hatch transportation duration and parental age on broiler chicken quality, welfare, and productivity**

Jacobs, L., Delezie, E., Duchateau, L., Goethals, K., Ampe, B., Lambrecht, E., Gellynck, X., Tuytens, F.A.M. 2016. *Poult. Sci.* 95, 1973–1979. DOI: [10.3382/ps/pew155](https://doi.org/10.3382/ps/pew155)

[ABSTRACT](#)

9. **Early life environment affects behavior, welfare, gut microbiome composition, and diversity in broiler chickens**

Jong, I.C. de, Schokker, D., Gunnink, H., van Wijhe, M., Rebel, J.M.J. 2022. *Front. Vet. Sci.* 9, 977359. DOI: [10.3389/fvets.2022.977359](https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2022.977359)

[ABSTRACT](#)

10. **Effects of on-farm and traditional hatching on welfare, health, and performance of broiler chickens**

Jong, I.C. de, van Hattum, T., van Riel, J.W., Baere, K. de, Kempen, I., Cardinaels, S., Gunnink, H. 2020. *Poult. Sci.* 99, 4662–4671. DOI: [10.1016/j.psj.2020.06.052](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2020.06.052)

[ABSTRACT](#)

6.2 Informative abstracts

1. **Effect of transportation duration of 1-day-old chicks on postplacement production performances and pododermatitis of broilers up to slaughter age**

This experiment studied the effect of transportation duration of 1-d-old chicks on dehydration, mortality, production performance, and pododermatitis during the growout period. Eggs from the same breeder flock (Ross PM3) were collected at 35, 45, and 56 wk of age, for 3 successive identical experiments. In each experiment, newly hatched chicks received 1 of 3 transportation duration treatments from the hatchery before placement in the on-site rearing facility: no transportation corresponding to direct placement in less than 5 min (T00), or 4 (T04) or 10 h (T10) of transportation. The chicks were housed in 35-m² pens (650 birds each) and reared until 35 d old. Hematocrit and chick BW were measured on sample chicks before and after transportation. During the growout period, bird weight, feed uptake, and feed conversion ratio were measured weekly until slaughter. Transportation duration affected BW; T00 groups had a significantly higher BW than T04 and T10 transported birds but this effect lasted only until d 21. No clear effect on hematocrit, feed uptake, feed conversion ratio, or mortality was observed for birds transported up to 10 h. The decrease in weight in T10 birds was associated with less severe pododermatitis. Increasing age of the breeder flock was correlated with reduced egg fertility and hatchability, and also with higher quality and BW of hatched chicks. Chicks from older breeders also exhibited reduced mortality during the growout period.

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2. **Resting behavior of broilers reared with or without artificial brooders**

Rest and sleep are important for the welfare of mammals and birds. A large part of the daily time budget of broiler chickens is taken up by resting behavior and the quality of resting is important. However, in intensive broiler production systems, disruptions of resting behaviors are common. These disruptions of resting behavior could be negative for the health and growth of the birds. This study investigated if artificial brooders that provide a delimited and darker resting place, away from active birds, reduce disruptions of resting behavior compared to a control situation without artificial brooders. Six pens of each treatment were used in the

same building, keeping 60 chickens (Ross 308) per pen. The artificial brooders were removed at 21 days of age. Data on disturbances and duration of resting bouts and activity between resting bouts were collected on 20 and 34 days of age. Also, as an indicator of the quality of rest, the animals' cognitive performance was evaluated in a spatial learning test that was performed at 11 days of age. The results showed that birds housed in pens with access to brooders have longer resting bouts (260.7 ± 5.2 vs. $132.8 \pm 5.3s$, $p < 0.001$) and are less likely to be disturbed during resting by other individuals (0.15 vs. 0.48 , $p < 0.001$). The effect of the artificial brooders on both the duration of resting bouts and the proportion of disturbances remained after the removal of the brooders at 21 days of age. The duration of activity between resting bouts was shorter if the resting bout was ended by a disturbance (9.98 ± 1.0 vs. $61.0 \pm 2.4s$, $p < 0.001$). Birds reared with brooders were more likely to solve the spatial learning task (0.5 vs. 0.27 , $p < 0.01$), but those succeeding were not faster at solving it. Broilers may be exposed to disrupted rest due to the lack of a dedicated resting place separated from areas with high activity. Using artificial brooders reduces disturbances but does not eliminate them. Therefore, additional changes to the housing conditions or management will be needed to prevent disturbances.

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3. A 'meta-analysis' of effects of post-hatch food and water deprivation on development, performance and welfare of chickens

A 'meta-analysis' was performed to determine effects of post-hatch food and water deprivation (PHFWD) on chicken development, performance and welfare (including health). Two types of meta-analysis were performed on peer-reviewed scientific publications: a quantitative 'meta-analysis' (MA) and a qualitative analysis (QA). Previously reported effects of PHFWD were quantified in the MA, for variables related to performance, mortality and relative yolk sac weight. The QA counted the number of studies reporting (non-)significant effects when five or more records were available in the data set (i.e. relative heart, liver and pancreas weight; plasma T3, T4 and glucose concentrations; relative duodenum, jejunum and ileum weight; duodenum, jejunum and ileum length; and villus height and crypt depth in duodenum, jejunum and ileum). MA results indicated that 24 hours of PHFWD (i.e. ≥ 12 -36 hours) or more resulted in significantly lower body weights compared to early-fed chickens up to six weeks of age. Body weights and food intake were more reduced as durations of PHFWD (24, 48, 72, ≥ 84 hours) increased. Feed conversion rate increased in chickens up to 21 and 42 days of age after ≥ 84 hours PHFWD in comparison with chickens fed earlier. Total mortality at day 42 was higher in chickens after 48 hours PHFWD compared to early fed chickens or chickens after 24 hours PHFWD. First week mortality was higher in chickens after ≥ 84 hours PHFWD than in early fed chickens. The MA for relative yolk sac weight was inconclusive for PHFWD. The QA for plasma T3, T4 and glucose concentrations indicated mainly short-term decreases in T3 and glucose in PHFWD chickens compared to early fed chickens, and no effects of PHFWD on T4 concentrations. Relative weights of liver, pancreas and heart were lower after PHFWD, but only in the first week of life. A retarded development of gut segments (duodenum, jejunum and ileum) was found in the first week of life, measured as shorter, lower relative weight, and lower villus height and crypt depth. It is concluded that 48 hours (≥ 36 -60 hours) PHFWD leads to lower body weights and higher total mortality in chickens up to six weeks of age, the latter suggesting compromised chicken welfare, but effects of PHFWD on organ development and physiological status appear to be mainly short-term.

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4. Opportunities to improve the welfare of young chickens

This chapter reviews the range of issues affecting the health and welfare of young chickens. It starts by assessing the welfare of parental stock and its effects on offspring. The chapter

then reviews research on incubation practices to optimize chick welfare. The chapter also discusses hatching practices to optimise chick welfare, both in commercial hatcheries as well as on-farm hatching. Finally, the chapter assesses rearing practices to optimize pullet welfare, including the importance of enrichment in, for example, in reducing the risk of developing injurious pecking behaviours, reducing risk of injury by improving spatial and navigation skills, as well as reducing feelings of fear and stress.

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5. Health, welfare and lifetime performance implications of alternative hatching and early life management systems for broiler chickens

Broiler chicks are typically hatched in a hatchery, exposing them to handling and transportation before being placed on the farm where (dry) feed and water is offered. This study compared different early life systems, including: (1) typical practice (control), (2) typical practice with wet feed offered upon placement, (3) access to water at the hatchery, (4) access to feed and water at the hatchery, (5) hatching on the farm. Birds were placed in groups of approximately 500 (day 0), with six replicates per treatment. Measures were taken between placement and slaughter (day 39) and included chick quality (navel and red hock scores), body weight, feed conversion ratio (FCR), mortality, gait and litter conditions scores, and behavioral and post-mortem assessments. There were no apparent treatment effects on gait score, play behaviour or novel object test measures, and no consistent effects on litter quality. Chick quality was only evaluated in Treatments 1 and 5 and was numerically worse in Treatment 5. Body weight at slaughter was lowest in Treatment 2, and did not differ between other treatments. Overall FCR was lowest (best) in Treatment 1, and did not differ between other treatments. There was higher overall mortality in Treatments 3 and 4 than in other treatments apart from Treatment 5. Treatment 4 appeared to promote feeding behaviour upon placement, and Treatment 5 birds rested the most, significantly more than in Treatment 2. Treatment 5 birds had the greatest bursa weights, and tibial dyschondroplasia appeared worse in Treatment 4. There were no consistent effects of early access to feed and water on gastrointestinal tract weight measures at slaughter. Compared to the control, there were few benefits in providing feed and/or water in the hatchery, or wet feed. Some benefits of in-house hatching were found, but negative effects were also apparent.

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6. Effects of early nutrition and sanitary conditions on antibody levels in early and later life of broiler chickens

Immune maturation of broiler chickens may be affected by management, such as early life feeding strategy (early versus delayed nutrition) or by low or high sanitary conditions (LSC versus HSC). We compared systemic maternal (MAb), natural (NAb), natural auto- (NAAb), and antigen specific antibody (SpAb) levels (IgM, IgY) between broilers (n = 48 per treatment) that received early (EN) or delayed nutrition for 72 h (DN) housed in either low (LSC) or high sanitary conditions (HSC) between 7 and 35 d of age. We found minimal interactions between feeding strategy and sanitary conditions. At 7 d of age, broilers receiving EN compared with DN, had elevated levels of IgM binding keyhole limpet hemocyanin (KLH), phosphoryl-conjugated ovalbumin (PC-OVA), and muramyl dipeptide (MDP), whereas effects of feeding strategy diminished at later ages. In LSC compared with HSC broilers, levels of NAb agglutinating RRBC and sheep red blood cells (SRBC) were already elevated from 14 d of age onwards. At 33 d of age, antibody levels (NAb, NAAb, anti-LPS, anti-MDP) were all elevated in LSC, compared with HSC broilers, for both IgM and IgY, but not IgM against KLH. Western blotting revealed different binding patterns of NAAb against chicken liver homogenate, which may indicate that the NAAb repertoire is affected by antigenic pressure. Our data suggest that antibody levels are affected for an important part

by environmental conditions (feeding strategy and sanitary conditions), but minimally by their interaction. However, it remains to be further studied whether the enhanced levels of antibodies as initiated by EN and LSC contribute to enhanced resistance to infectious diseases.

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7. **Effects of early nutrition and transport of 1-day-old chickens on production performance and fear response**

The importance of optimal early life conditions of broilers to sustain efficient and healthy production of broiler meat is increasingly recognized. Therefore, novel husbandry systems are developed, in which immediate provision of nutrition post hatch is combined with on-farm hatching. In these novel systems, 1-day-old-chick handling and transport are minimized. To study whether early nutrition and reduced transport are beneficial for broiler performance and behavior, the effects of early or delayed nutrition and post-hatch handling and transport were tested from hatch until 35 d of age, in a 2 × 2 factorial arrangement. In total, 960 eggs were hatched in 36 floor pens. After hatch, chicks were given immediate access to water and feed (early nutrition) or after 54 h (delayed nutrition). Eighteen hours after hatch, chicks remained in their pens (non-transported control), or were subjected to short-term handling and transport to simulate conventional procedures. Subsequently, chicks returned to their pens. Compared with delayed-fed chickens, early-fed chickens had greater body weight up to 21 d of age, but not at slaughter (35 d of age). No effects of transport or its interaction with moment of first nutrition were found on performance. At 3 d post hatch, transported, early-fed chicks had a greater latency to stand up in a tonic immobility test than transported, delayed-fed chicks, but only in chicks that were transported. At 30 d post hatch, however, latency was greater in transported, delayed-fed chickens than in transported, early-fed chicks. This may indicate long-term deleterious effects of delayed nutrition on fear response in transported chickens. It is concluded that early nutrition has mainly beneficial effects on performance during the first 2 wk post hatch, but these beneficial effects are less evident in later life. The combination of transport and early nutrition may influence the chicken's strategies to cope with stressful events in early and later life.

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8. **Effect of post-hatch transportation duration and parental age on broiler chicken quality, welfare, and productivity**

Broiler chicks are transported to production sites within one to 2 d post-hatch. Possible effects of this transportation are poorly understood and could vary among chicks from breeder flocks of different ages. The aim of the present study was to investigate the effects of transportation duration and parental flock age on chick welfare, productivity, and quality. After hatch in a commercial hatchery, 1,620 mixed-sex chicks from 29-wk old (young) and 1,620 chicks from 60-wk old (old) breeders were subjected to transportation of 1.5 h or 11 h duration. After transportation, 2,800 chicks were divided among 100 pens, with each pen containing 28 chicks from one transportation crate (2 or 3 pens per crate). From the remaining chicks, on average 6 chicks (min 4, max 8) per crate (n = 228) were randomly selected and assessed for chick quality, weighed, and culled for yolk sac weighing (one d). Chicks that had not been assigned to pens or were not used for post-transportation measurements, were removed from the experiment (n = 212). Mortality, ADG, BW, and feed conversion (FC:) of the experimental chicks were recorded until 41 d. Meat quality was measured for breast fillets (n = 47). No interaction effect of parental age and transportation duration was found for any variables. BW and yolk sac weight at one d were lower for chicks transported 11 h than 1.5 h and for chicks from young versus old breeders. The effect of parental flock age on BW persisted until slaughter. Additionally, parental age positively affected ADG until slaughter. Chick quality was lower in chicks from old versus young breeders. Chick quality and

productivity were not affected by transportation duration. Mortality and meat quality were not affected by either parental age or transportation duration. To conclude, no long-term detrimental effects were found from long post-hatch transportation in chicks from young or old parent flocks. Based on these results, we suggest that 11 h post-hatch transportations under similar conditions do not impose long-term welfare or productivity risks.

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9. Early life environment affects behavior, welfare, gut microbiome composition, and diversity in broiler chickens

This study aimed to identify whether early-life conditions in broiler chickens could affect their behavior and welfare, and whether or not this was associated with an altered gut microbiome composition or diversity. Broilers were tested in a 2 x 2 factorial design with hatching conditions [home pen (OH) or at the hatchery (HH)] and enrichment (dark brooder (EE) or no brooder (NE) until 14 days of age) as factors (N = 6 per treatment combination). Microbiota composition was measured in the jejunum on days (d) 7, 14, and 35 and in pooled fecal samples on day 14. A novel environment test (NET) was performed on days 1 and 11, and the behavior was observed on days 6, 13, and 33. On day 35, composite asymmetry was determined and footpad dermatitis and hock burn were scored. In their home pen, HH showed more locomotion than OH (P = 0.05), and NE were sitting more and showed more comfort behavior than EE at all ages (P < 0.001 and P = 0.001, respectively). On days 6 and 13 NE showed more eating and litter pecking while sitting, but on day 33 the opposite was found (age*enrichment: P = 0.05 and P < 0.01, respectively). On days 1 and 11, HH showed more social reinstatement in the NET than OH, and EE showed more social reinstatement than NE (P < 0.05). Composite asymmetry scores were lower for EE than NE (P < 0.05). EE also had less footpad dermatitis and hock burn than NE (P < 0.001). Within OH, NE had a more diverse fecal and jejunal microbiome compared to EE on day 14 (feces: observed richness: P = 0.052; jejunum: observed richness and Shannon: P < 0.05); the principal component analysis (PCA) showed differences between NE and EE within both HH and OH in fecal samples on day 14, as well as significant differences in bacterial genera such as Lactobacillus and Lachnospiraceae (P < 0.05). On day 35, PCA in jejunal samples only showed a trend (P = 0.068) for differences between NE vs. EE within the OH. In conclusion, these results suggest that especially the dark brooder affected the behavior and had a positive effect on welfare as well as affected the composition and diversity of the microbiome. Whether or not the behavior was modulated by the microbiome or vice versa remains to be investigated.

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10. Effects of on-farm and traditional hatching on welfare, health, and performance of broiler chickens

In on-farm hatching systems, eggs that have been incubated for 18 D are transported to the broiler farm. After hatching around day 21, the chicks have immediate access to feed and water. By contrast, traditionally hatched chicks are in early life exposed to dust and pathogens in the hatcher, handling procedures, and transport and remain without feed and water until they have arrived on the farm 1 to 3 D after hatching. We compared welfare and performance of on-farm hatched (OH) and traditionally hatched control (C) Ross 308 broiler chickens from day 0 to 40, housed under semi-commercial conditions. The experiment included 3 production cycles in 4 rooms, with each room containing 1 OH and 1 C pen with 1,150 chickens in each pen. Per cycle, C and OH chicks were from the same batch of eggs of 1 parent stock flock. Day-old chick quality was worse for OH than C chickens (hock and navel score; P < 0.05). On-farm hatched chickens were heavier than C chickens until day 21 of age (P < 0.05). Total mortality was significantly lower in OH compared with C pens (P < 0.05). A tendency for lower footpad dermatitis scores was found in OH pens compared with

C pens ($P < 0.10$), probably because of the dryer litter in OH than C pens ($P < 0.05$). No differences between treatments were found in gait, hock burn, cleanliness, and injury scores, and no or only minor, short lasting differences were found in pathology and intestinal histology. In conclusion, the present study showed that on-farm hatching may be beneficial for broiler welfare, as it reduced total mortality and resulted in dryer litter which is known to be beneficial for reducing footpad dermatitis.

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6.3 List of practical knowledge sources

1. TRAINING MANUAL ON POULTRY(BROILER) PRODUCTION AND MANAGEMENT

K. Olajide. 2019. <https://ceadese.funaab.edu.ng/beta/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/Course-material-on-BROILER-PRODUCTION-@CEADESE-Capacity-Building.pdf>

[SUMMARY](#)

2. Broiler chickens: first days life management

Techna. 2024. <https://www.groupe-techna.com/en/feedia/advice/first-days-broiler-chickens#:~:text=2.,excretions%20and%20the%20drinking%20system>

[SUMMARY](#)

3. Focus on optimal starting conditions for day-old chicks

Lohmann Breeders. 2013. <https://lohmann-breeders.com/de/lohmanninfo/focus-on-optimal-starting-conditions-for-day-old-chicks/>

[SUMMARY](#)

4. The effect of on-farm hatching and the presence of hens

Poultry World. 2024. <https://www.poultryworld.net/the-industrymarkets/market-trends-analysis-the-industrymarkets-2/the-effect-of-on-farm-hatching-and-the-presence-of-hens/>

[SUMMARY](#)

5. Benefits of probiotics in chicks explored

Poultry World. 2024. <https://www.poultryworld.net/health-nutrition/health/benefits-of-probiotics-in-chicks-explored/>

[SUMMARY](#)

6. Organic acids act as alternative to antibiotics in broilers: new research

Poultry News. 2017. <https://www.poultrynews.co.uk/health-welfare/food-safety/organic-acids-act-as-alternative-to-antibiotics-in-broilers-new-research.html>

[SUMMARY](#)

7. How on-farm hatching can improve flock health and cut costs

Farmers Weekly. 2021. <https://www.fwi.co.uk/livestock/poultry/how-on-farm-hatching-can-improve-flock-health-and-cut-costs>

[SUMMARY](#)

8. Hatching broilers in stables rather than in hatcheries increases animal welfare

Chapter 6 Chick management

The Poultry Site. 2021. <https://www.thepoultrysite.com/articles/hatching-broilers-in-stables-rather-than-in-hatcheries-increases-animal-welfare>

SUMMARY

9. Top 10 Best Management Practice Tips for Better & Quality Broiler Production

Md. Forhad Hossain. 2022. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/top-10-best-management-practice-tips-better-quality-md-forhad-/>

SUMMARY

10. Broiler Production Stages, Guidelines, and Best Practices

Forms on Fire. 2024. <https://www.formsonfire.com/blog/broiler-production-guidelines>

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6.4 Informative summaries

1. **TRAINING MANUAL ON POULTRY(BROILER) PRODUCTION AND MANAGEMENT**

Module 1: Overview of Poultry production in developing and under developed Countries: Importance and Challenges

Module 2:

- Types of Poultry
- Broiler Chicken Production: History, Types and Strains

Module 3: Management of Broiler Chicken:

- Site selection, housing and equipment
- Brooding Management
- Feeds and Feeding Management
- Water Management
- Litter Management

Module 4: Health Management in Broiler Chicken:

- Medication and vaccination
- Rules of thumb for vaccination
- Bio-security issues in broiler production

Module 5: Broiler Chicken Products and Marketing:

- Primary and Secondary Products
- Marketing: Channels, Information and Strategies

Module 6: Records Keeping in Poultry Production

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2. **Broiler chickens: first day of life management**

During the first week of rearing, a broiler chicken can gain up to five times its starting weight. This period corresponds to one-third of a standard broiler chicken's life. The objectives, at the end of this first week, are to have animals that are as homogeneous as possible, with controlled and increasing growth and the highest possible viability, all while minimising the impact of pododermatitis and with humane treatment of the animals. Three Important Criteria for the First Week of Brooding: 1. Thermally suitable environment, 2. Litter requirements, 3. Nutrition management.

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3. **Focus on optimal starting conditions for day-old chicks**

Theory and practice of early chick husbandry are discussed in the context of increasing public pressure to minimize and eventually eliminate the use of antibiotics in poultry production. Commonly observed mistakes are (1) floor temperatures below the recommended optimum at the time of chick placement; (2) monitoring house temperature high above chick level; (3) low humidity as a result of excessive temperature; (4) insufficient ventilation to save energy; and (5) yolk infections from contaminated litter. Broiler growers are encouraged to use a check-list to monitor the actual husbandry conditions in order to achieve the best possible results with minimal medication.

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4. The effect of on-farm hatching and the presence of hens

On-farm hatching and the presence of adult hens alongside chicks could enhance poultry welfare and robustness of birds, and limit the use of antibiotics. That was the premise for a French study that looked to carry out an experimental analysis of the benefits and risks associated with these practices. To improve the early perinatal conditions of broiler chicks, alternative hatching systems have been developed. On-farm hatching with an enriched microbial and stimulating environment by the presence of an adult hen is a promising solution, the researchers say. In conclusion, the researchers said the OFH system was a hatching system at least equivalent to the CH system. The presence of the hen at hatching and during the start-up phase on performance interacted with the hatching condition and the sex of the chickens.

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5. Benefits of probiotics in chicks explored

Supplementing the diet of young chicks with a probiotic over 21 days significantly enhanced the abundance of beneficial intestinal microorganisms, according to new research. With antimicrobial resistance and the use of antimicrobials in livestock feed a major concern over the spread of resistance to many other drugs, researchers at Penn State University in the US conducted a study of natural feed additives, seen as promising alternatives to substitute for antimicrobial growth promoters. They also collected excreta samples daily during the experimental period and analysed DNA to identify bacteria present. Across all 9 points, supplementing chicken diets with the probiotic or the antibiotic significantly changed the relative abundance of bacterial strains compared to the standard diet. There were, however, no microorganisms affected by essential oils compared to the standard diet.

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6. Organic acids act as alternative to antibiotics in broilers: new research

The acids are used as feed preservatives, helping to protect chicken feed against microbial and fungal damage. Organic acids are also known to suppress the growth of bacteria such as e-coli, salmonella and clostridium perfringens and enhance the digestibility of nitrogen, phosphorus and minerals. The results show that formic acid supplementation had a beneficial effect on performance and immunity of broiler chickens without having any significantly effects on blood biochemical parameters. Formic acid was also shown to be effective against acid intolerant species such as e. coli, salmonella and clostridium count in caecum.

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7. How on-farm hatching can improve flock health and cut costs

On-farm hatching is delivering better broiler performance while improving welfare and cutting carbon emissions for one Hertfordshire producer. Tom Wornham's family farm almost 200,000 birds for one of the UK's largest poultry integrators. He recently switched to 100%

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on-farm hatching, from Belgian firm NestBorn, which means fertilised eggs are now delivered to the farm rather than day-old chicks at the beginning of a flock.

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8. Hatching broilers in stables rather than in hatcheries increases animal welfare

Some of the procedures are sorting, vaccination and packing followed by transport, unloading and placement in a new environment. Based on previous studies, these procedures are considered significant stress factors in the chicks' early life. Hatching on-farm is an alternative to the traditional hatching in a hatchery. Here, the brooded eggs are placed in the barn three days before hatching so that the actual phase of hatching takes place in the stable. Hence, more procedures at the hatchery and transport of day-old chicks are avoided. Furthermore, the chicks have access to feed and water immediately after hatching. But does it make any difference to the chicks' welfare whether they hatch on-farm or in the hatchery? The researchers conclude that hatching broilers on-farm increases animal welfare and is a valid concept. According to Anja Brinch Riber, the positive effects for the on-farm chicks are especially remarkable as they were obtained even though the study partly included handling in terms of vaccination of on-farm chicks (which is not normal procedure for the typical hybrids (faster growing) hatched on-farm). Partly, the period without water and feed in the hatchery chicks' early life was relatively short (few hours), which in practice under Danish conditions can last up to 48 hours.

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9. Top 10 Best Management Practice Tips for Better & Quality Broiler Production

The acronym "FLAWS" has commonly been used as a best management practice for poultry production to check Feed, Litter/light, Air, Water, (bio)security, Sanitation, Space & Staffs. It is not only important during the brooding time but also throughout the life of the flock. To get better & quality broiler production, it is important to have quality day-old chicks. Some standard criteria of good quality chicks are: Pathogen and or Salmonella free chicks; Standard BWT; Look alert & have bright & active eyes; Completely healed navels; Free from deformities.

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10. Broiler Production Stages, Guidelines, and Best Practices

Broiler farming is one of the most popular and profitable sectors of the poultry industry. It involves raising chickens for meat production, ensuring they grow quickly and efficiently. Whether you're new to poultry farming or looking to optimize your existing operation, understanding the basics of broiler production is key to success. The goal of this article is to provide you with clear, practical guidelines and best practices that will help you run an efficient and profitable broiler farm.

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Chapter 7 Minimizing stress and injuries during catching

7.1 List of scientific knowledge sources

1. Effect of different catching practices during manual upright handling on broiler welfare and behaviour

De Lima, V.A.; Ceballos, M.C.; Gregory, N.G.; Da Costa, M.J.R.P. 2019. *Poult. Sci.* 98 (10): 4282–4289. DOI: [10.3382/ps/pez284](https://doi.org/10.3382/ps/pez284).

[ABSTRACT](#)

2. Comparing methods for catching and crating broiler chicken flocks: A trade-off between animal welfare, ergonomics and economics

Delanglez, F.; Watteyn, A.; Ampe, B.; Segers, V.; Garmyn, A.; Delezie, E.; et al. 2025. *Poult. Sci.* 104(2):104704. DOI: [10.1016/j.psj.2024.104704](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2024.104704).

[ABSTRACT](#)

3. Consumers' preferences toward techniques for improving manual catching of poultry

Delezie, E.; Verbeke, W.; De Tavernier, J.; Decuyper, E. 2006. *Poult. Sci.* 85(11): 2019-27. DOI: [10.1093/ps/85.11.2019](https://doi.org/10.1093/ps/85.11.2019).

[ABSTRACT](#)

4. What do we know about the impacts of poultry catching?

Dutra, F.M., Garcia, R.G., Binotto, E., Burbarelli, de Castro Burbarelli, M.F. 2021. *World's Poult. Sci. J.* 77(4), 983–999. DOI: [10.1080/00439339.2021.1976056](https://doi.org/10.1080/00439339.2021.1976056)

[ABSTRACT](#)

5. Improving welfare in catching and transport of chickens

Jacobs, L.; Tuytens, F.A.M. 2020. In Christine Nicol (Ed.): *Understanding the behaviour and improving the welfare of chickens*. 1st edition. Philadelphia, PA: Burleigh Dodds Science Publishing, pp. 417–458. DOI: [10.1201/9781003048039](https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003048039)

[ABSTRACT](#)

6. An Evaluation of Two Different Broiler Catching Methods

Kittelsen, K.E.; Granquist, E.G.; Aunsmo, A.L.; Moe, R.O.; Tolo, E. 2018. *Animals.* 8 (8). DOI: [10.3390/ani8080141](https://doi.org/10.3390/ani8080141).

[ABSTRACT](#)

7. Influence of two catching methods on the occurrence of lesions in broilers

Langkabel, N.; Baumann, M.P.O.; Feiler, A.; Sanguankiat, A.; Fries, R. 2015. *Poult. Sci.* 94 (8): 1735–1741. DOI: [10.3382/ps/pev164](https://doi.org/10.3382/ps/pev164).

[ABSTRACT](#)

8. The welfare impacts of mechanical and manual broiler catching and of circumstances at loading under field conditions

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Mönch, J.; Rauch, E.; Hartmannsgruber, S.; Erhard, M.; Wolff, I.; Schmidt, P.; Schug, A.R.; Louton, H. 2020. Poult. Sci. 99(11):5233-5251. DOI: [10.1016/j.psj.2020.08.030](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2020.08.030).

[ABSTRACT](#)

9. **Welfare of domestic birds and rabbits transported in containers**

EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare (AHAW). 2022. EFSA J. 20 (9): e07441. DOI: [10.2903/j.efsa.2022.7441](https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2022.7441).

[ABSTRACT](#)

10. **Harvesting-induced stress in broilers: Comparison of a manual and a mechanical harvesting method under field conditions**

Wolff, I.; Klein, S.; Rauch, E.; Erhard, M.; Mönch, J.; Härtle, S.; Schmidt, P.; Louton, H. 2019. Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci. 221: 104877. DOI: [10.1016/j.applanim.2019.104877](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2019.104877)

[ABSTRACT](#)

7.2 Informative abstracts

1. **Effect of different catching practices during manual upright handling on broiler welfare and behaviour**

The aim of this study was to identify the influence of different catching practices during manual upright handling on broiler welfare and behavior. Catching was examined in a total of 4,595 Cobb broilers with average live weight of 3.2 kg and 42 days old. Six catching practices were evaluated: shed curtain position, loading time, catching method, catching team, height of the crates from the floor, and placement of the bird in the crate. Behavioral welfare indicators were defined as follows: 1) broiler agitation in the catcher's hands, measured when the birds flapped their wings, kicked, or wriggled in the hands; 2) broiler striking the crate entrance as it was being placed in the crate, measured when the birds get the head, wings, or legs, hit at the crate entrance; and 3) broiler agitation in the crate, measured when birds flapped the wings or jumped inside the crate for 3 s or more after placement in the crate. A logistic regression model was used to calculate the chance of occurrence of each behavioral welfare indicator due to the handling factors. All catching practices evaluated in the present study influenced the birds' welfare and behavior. Thus, some procedures during broiler catching potentially improved their behavior, making them less prone to accidents, and consequently improved their welfare. The catching process should be performed with the curtains in the closed position, carrying one broiler per catcher in an upright position while containing its wings, carefully placing the birds inside the crates, and with the crates being positioned at a height of at least 21 cm from the ground. Additionally, it was concluded that more attention should be given to the broiler catchers, since the position of the curtain, loading time, and position of the crate during handling can influence the work done by them, affecting the welfare and behavior of both humans and birds.

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2. **Comparing methods for catching and crating broiler chicken flocks: A trade-off between animal welfare, ergonomics and economics**

Catching, carrying, and loading of broilers before transport to the slaughterhouse causes stress. In this study three catching methods (two manual (inverted, upright) and one mechanical) were compared using a cost-benefit analysis of animal welfare, ergonomics and economic analysis. Depopulation of approximately 5,000 broilers per catching method per

flock (upright vs. inverted vs. mechanical: n=3; upright vs. inverted: n=9; inverted vs. mechanical: n=3 flocks) was analyzed on 15 commercial farms. Economic considerations (person-hours per 1,000 chickens), ergonomics (catcher survey, ergonomic assessment of simulated catching), and animal welfare on-farm (wing flapping frequency, catcher-bird interaction) and at the slaughterhouse (catch damage and DOA prevalence) were considered. Wing flapping frequency was lower (2.0 ± 0.1 vs. 5.4 ± 0.1 , $P < 0.001$), and catcher-bird interaction was better (3.7 ± 0.2 vs. 4.4 ± 0.2 , $P < 0.01$) for upright catching compared to inverted catching based on a 7-point Likert scale. Prevalence of catch damage was lower for upright versus mechanical catching ($15.5 \pm 1.3\%$ vs. $17.7 \pm 1.4\%$, $P = 0.046$). More person-hours per 1,000 broilers were required for upright versus inverted (1.6 ± 0.1 h vs. 1.0 ± 0.1 h) and mechanical catching (0.6 ± 0.3 h) ($P < 0.001$). Upright catching was 1.5 and 1.2 times more expensive than inverted and mechanical catching based on 20,000 broilers. Compared to inverted catching, fair compensation would increase by €0.012 (upright) and €0.006 (mechanical) per kg of live weight. An ergonomics expert rated manual catching as very demanding, but catchers (n = 16) disliked upright catching (more labor-intensive). This study revealed animal welfare benefits of upright versus inverted (less wing flapping, better catcher-bird interaction) and mechanical catching (less catch damage), whereas mechanical catching provided the best labor conditions. Widespread application of upright catching would require testing of entire flocks and collaboration with the poultry sector to determine fair compensation, improve labor conditions and identify strategies to minimize catch and load duration.

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3. Consumers' preferences toward techniques for improving manual catching of poultry

Growing interest in ameliorating animal welfare has prompted numerous studies that compare various aspects of manual and mechanical catching. In general, mechanical catching has been adopted as a realistic alternative for manual catching. The success of a catching machine as an alternative for manual catching does not only depend on its practical applicability, but also on its acceptance by "the general public." In the history of technological change, public perception of new technologies has often been ambivalent. Against this background, it is important to know how consumers perceive the production methods. This paper provides an evaluation of the preferences for catching methods by "society" to investigate whether there is a shift in preference due to the confrontation with video segments and the potential effect of awareness and importance attached to animal welfare on preference. Data were gathered through a questionnaire-based survey, including 450 respondents, performed in Belgium. For this study, the data indicated that when subjects were provided information concerning catching methods of broilers, they liked the technology much more. However, for those respondents without prior awareness of both catching methods or with high importance attached to animal welfare, giving information could not convince them of the advantage of using a mechanical catching machine. It is obvious that preference varies with the awareness and experience of the respondents. Future research should move forward from simple assessments of consumer concerns about the technologies and focus more directly on questions and issues related to the consumer's expected bottlenecks of these technologies. In this way, working at a better understanding can directly influence the acceptance of these technologies.

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4. What do we know about the impacts of poultry catching?

The global demand for food production, especially poultry, has contributed significantly to the supply of protein. Industries, as an important link in the production chain, aim to serve the consumer market, which increasingly seeks agility, economy and quality in products and

processes, especially for those related to animal and human welfare. This study highlights the context of broiler chicken catching from the animal, human, and economic welfare perspective. A systematic review about the literature was conducted in three phases: definition of the research protocol, analysis of articles selected and synthesis of the findings. After selecting descriptors/ words and searching databases, inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied, 40 articles were selected. The findings showed that the publications on the subject started in Europe, South Africa and North America in the 1980s. Poultry Science, with an impact factor of 2,027, published the most of the articles. The authors brought contributions in some areas, such as lesions, dead on arrival (DOA) at the slaughterhouse and consumer perception on animal welfare (AW). Finally, mechanised catching has the potential to replace manual catching, providing health and welfare benefits for animals and workers besides cost savings.

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5. Improving welfare in catching and transport of chickens

The pre-slaughter phase is the last stage of meat production and for broiler chickens entails feed and water withdrawal, catching, loading, transportation and lairage. Major stressors during pre-slaughter include rough handling, overstocking, thermal stress, and prolonged feed and water withdrawal that can result in injuries, mortality, fear, and distress. The annual global economic loss could roughly vary from 143 million to 3 billion dollars for condemned parts due to injuries, and from 6 to 14 billion dollars for weight loss. Broiler welfare during catching could be improved by gentler mechanical catching and loading, alternative upright manual catching, training of catching crews, herding, and fitness-for-transport assessment. Improvements related to transport include using climate-controlled systems, reducing transport duration or making transportation redundant by on-farm slaughter. In order to reduce animal suffering and associated production losses during pre-slaughter, we recommend an approach with systematic monitoring of animal-based welfare indicators, feedback to responsible actors, and incentives to act when acceptable thresholds are (repeatedly) surpassed. Although this chapter focuses on broiler chickens, the laying hen pre-slaughter phase is briefly discussed as well.

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6. An Evaluation of Two Different Broiler Catching Methods

Catching is the first step in the pre-slaughter chain for broiler chickens. The process may be detrimental for animal welfare due to the associated handling. The aim of this pilot study was to compare two different methods to manually catch broilers: Catching the broilers by two legs and carrying them inverted (LEGS) or catching the broilers under the abdomen and carrying them in an upright position (UPRIGHT). Wing and leg fractures upon arrival at the abattoir, animal density in the drawers, birds on their back, broilers dead-on-arrival and time to fill the transport modules were investigated. The results showed that mean crating time was shorter in the UPRIGHT method ($p = 0.007$). There was a tendency for more wing fractures in broilers caught by the LEGS ($p = 0.06$). The animal density in the drawers was lower and with a smaller range in the UPRIGHT method ($p = 0.022$). The results indicate that catching the broilers under the abdomen in an upright position may improve broiler welfare in terms of fewer wing fractures, more consistent stocking density in drawers and potentially reduced loading time.

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7. Influence of two catching methods on the occurrence of lesions in broilers

During the catching of broilers for slaughter, 2 to 3 birds are grabbed per hand at one leg at the same time. From an animal welfare point of view, this procedure is under critical

observation from animal welfare administration and the general public. In this paper 2 catching methods were compared: the routinely used 1-leg catching method, and a second technique whereby birds were grabbed by both legs with a maximum of 2 birds per hand (2-leg catching method). Lesions on the body, legs, and wings (hemorrhages and fractures) were recorded by a camera system located after the plucking position. Two weight classes, 2 catching teams, and 2 flocks were included in the study. Heavy animals showed more lesions than birds of the light weight class. In all investigations, lesions on the body and legs were rare, whereas wing lesions occurred at a rate of up to 15.32%. Statistical analysis showed no significant difference between the 2 methods or between the catching teams for both weight classes. A correlation between lesions and weight was observed, with a significant odds ratio (OR) of 3.6 (95% CI: 3.299-3.957). During 2-leg catching, the animals appeared to be more restless. Workers stated that the grabbing of both legs of a bird was more difficult and that working in a crouching position for a longer time was harder. We conclude that the cautious handling of animals to reduce stress is more important than "holding animals by both legs", as has been proposed.

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8. The welfare impacts of mechanical and manual broiler catching and of circumstances at loading under field conditions

Loading of broilers for transport to the processing plant poses a notable injury risk for broilers. Therefore, the poultry industry has developed mechanical methods as alternatives to manual loading methods. Our objective in the present study was to compare manual loading (MAN) of broilers with the mechanical loading (MECH). We assessed the injuries of broilers of 12 MAN and 12 MECH flocks on-farm before and immediately after loading, documented the numbers of broilers dead on arrival reported by the processing plant, and assessed the circumstances at loading. A smaller number of broilers with a hematoma (≥ 0.5 cm in diameter) on the wing were observed after MAN compared with MECH using the examined harvester (MAN vs. MECH odds ratio: 0.16; 95% confidence interval: 0.10, 0.28). The number of broilers with severe wing injuries did not differ between the loading methods. The number of broilers dead on arrival was greater in mechanically loaded flocks (MAN vs. MECH odds ratio: 0.26; 95% confidence interval: 0.10, 0.68), but lower than in comparable studies. We observed a lower average stocking rate than targeted in the drawers of MECH containers, most likely because the used harvester can adapt to short-term changes in weight and adjust the stocking rate during the loading process. A longer total loading duration in MAN was associated with an increase of wing hematomas, and the involvement of more working people per 10,000 broilers during MAN was associated with a lower occurrence of hematomas. The total loading duration in MECH had no notable influence on the occurrence of injuries. Physical conditions of the involved personnel might play a larger role in MAN than in MECH. The harvester that was examined should be further developed to reduce the occurrence of hematomas. Our results indicate that the choice of loading method alone does not determine the injury risk, and multiple factors are associated with broiler welfare during loading. It is important that the chosen method is performed under the most adequate conditions.

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9. Welfare of domestic birds and rabbits transported in containers

This opinion, produced upon a request from the European Commission, focuses on transport of domestic birds and rabbits in containers (e.g. any crate, box, receptacle or other rigid structure used for the transport of animals, but not the means of transport itself). It describes and assesses current transport practices in the EU, based on data from literature, Member States and expert opinion. The species and categories of domestic birds assessed were mainly chickens for meat (broilers), end-of-lay hens and day-old chicks. They included to a lesser

extent pullets, turkeys, ducks, geese, quails and game birds, due to limited scientific evidence. The opinion focuses on road transport to slaughterhouses or to production sites. For day-old chicks, air transport is also addressed. The relevant stages of transport considered are preparation, loading, journey, arrival and uncrating. Welfare consequences associated with current transport practices were identified for each stage. For loading and uncrating, the highly relevant welfare consequences identified are handling stress, injuries, restriction of movement and sensory overstimulation. For the journey and arrival, injuries, restriction of movement, sensory overstimulation, motion stress, heat stress, cold stress, prolonged hunger and prolonged thirst are identified as highly relevant. For each welfare consequence, animal-based measures (ABMs) and hazards were identified and assessed, and both preventive and corrective or mitigative measures proposed. Recommendations on quantitative criteria to prevent or mitigate welfare consequences are provided for microclimatic conditions, space allowances and journey times for all categories of animals, where scientific evidence and expert opinion support such outcomes.

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10. Harvesting-induced stress in broilers: Comparison of a manual and a mechanical harvesting method under field conditions

Harvesting of broilers is a stressful event, whether done mechanically or manually. The use of harvesting machines might compromise animal welfare less than manual harvesting methods because it is less influenced by environmental and flock-specific factors. In this paper, a mechanical and a manual harvesting method are compared in regard to stress-induced behavioural and physiological reactions. The stationary person test and the avoidance distance touch test were applied before harvesting to estimate pre-treatment fear of humans in the flocks. We then recorded the behaviour of the flocks during harvesting and evaluated stress-induced behaviour such as wing flapping and escape behaviour. Furthermore, we took blood samples at the abattoir and analysed the corticosterone concentration and heterophil/lymphocyte ratio. In a statistical analysis, all assessed parameters were related to environmental and flock-specific factors, as well as to the risk of lesions such as haematomas and fractures. Our aim was to figure out if the use of a harvesting machine, in this case the Apollo Generation 2, puts less stress on broilers during harvesting than manual catching. The applied behaviour tests indicate the excitability and fear of humans of the flocks but are complex to interpret. Compared with mechanical harvesting, manual harvesting was more influenced by environmental and flock-specific factors such as average weight (odds ratio [OR]=1.49; 95% confidence interval [CI] [1.11; 2.22]) or catching duration (OR=1.79; 95% CI [1.44; 2.19]). The results verified a correlation between stress-induced behaviour and the occurrence of lesions. The risk for haematomas was influenced by escape behaviour during manual harvesting (OR=1.07; 95% CI [1.02; 1.13]) and by bumps against the containers (OR=1.06; 95% CI [1.05; 1.07]) and flips (OR=6.23; 95% CI [3.99; 9.27]) during mechanical harvesting. The risk for fractures during mechanical harvesting was influenced by the occurrence of flips (OR=2.74; 95% CI [1.07; 5.67]). The risk for wing flapping was twice as high during manual harvesting as during mechanical harvesting (OR=2.11; 95% CI [1.82; 2.44]). The blood parameters showed no correlations with the initial behaviour test results and the assessed stress-induced behaviour during harvesting. Corticosterone concentration was strongly influenced by light intensity (beta=3.75; 95% CI [2.55; 4.95]) and outdoor temperature (beta=46.34; 95% CI [39.18; 53.27]) during manual harvesting. The results showed weak points of both harvesting methods, and we offer suggestions to improve animal welfare during harvesting.

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7.3 List of practical knowledge sources

1. Preparing the catching of broilers

European Commission, 2017. https://food.ec.europa.eu/document/download/21e35353-c54a-4a03-94c4-92084f30a2cb_en?filename=aw_awp_transport_guides_poultry_broilers_en.pdf&prefLang=en

SUMMARY

2. Welfare Issues with Conventional Manual Catching of Broiler Chickens and Turkeys

The Humane Society of The United States, 2014. <https://www.humaneworld.org/sites/default/files/docs/hsus-report-manual-catching-of-poultry.pdf>

SUMMARY

3. Welfare Sheet: Broiler chickens

Compassion in World Farming, 2013. <https://www.ciwf.org.uk/media/5235309/Welfare-sheet-Broiler-chickens.pdf>

SUMMARY

4. Poultry catching and handling

Humane Slaughter Association, 2018. <https://www.hsa.org.uk/downloads/technical-notes/hsatechnicalnote15-may2018.pdf>

SUMMARY

5. Industry tips: Poultry transport

Eyes on Animals, 2017. <https://www.eyesonanimals.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Industry-tips-poultry-transport-final-EN.pdf>

SUMMARY

6. Pre-slaughter welfare of broilers

Modern Poultry, 2025. <https://modernpoultry.media/pre-slaughter-welfare-of-broilers/?mp=1745483334405>

SUMMARY

7. Humane Broiler Catching: For Catching Crews

Ontario Ministry of Agriculture and Food, 2013. <https://www.poultryindustrycouncil.ca/downloads/humane-broiler-catching-course.pdf>

SUMMARY

8. Preparation of vehicle, driver and loading of poultry

European Commission, 2017. https://food.ec.europa.eu/document/download/55a60baf-f1aa-4826-819c-93c4ad12c17d_en?filename=aw_awp_transport_guides_poultry_preparation_en.pdf

SUMMARY

9. Good and Better practices in bird transport

Chapter 7 Catching

FVE, 2019.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MmdnHyfsVNk&list=PLpC8eSF4MyA8tkSolCw6yNgPSNaqDhkuw&index=48>

SUMMARY

10. Guide to good practices for the transport of poultry

European Commission, 2017. https://food.ec.europa.eu/document/download/7e082580-304b-4be3-8d66-07d912121771_en?filename=aw_awp_transport_guides_poultry_transport-good-practices_en.pdf

SUMMARY

7.4 Informative summaries

1. Preparing the catching of broilers

Factsheet about good conditions for catching. This includes guidelines for both farmer and catching crew on how to prepare the barn and how to assess fitness for transport. Furthermore, it shows recommendations to consider animal welfare during both manual and mechanical catching.

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2. Welfare Issues with Conventional Manual Catching of Broiler Chickens and Turkeys

When broilers reach market weight, they must be caught and crated for transport from production facilities to slaughter plants. Conventional manual catching results in severely compromised welfare. Birds experience stress and fear, and can be physically harmed, suffering bruises, broken bones, dislocated joints, and other injuries. Alternatives to conventional manual catching practices that improve bird welfare exist, including mechanical harvesters, gentle manual catching, and, for turkeys, herding into specially designed transport crates.

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3. Welfare Sheet: Broiler chickens

This document gives an overview of the different welfare problems that are associated with intensive meat chicken production. It will outline how some welfare problems may be overcome during catching, loading and transport.

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4. Poultry catching and handling

The slaughter process begins when poultry are caught and handled on the farm, for transportation to the slaughterhouse. Rough, aggressive catching can result in poultry panicking, becoming distressed and injured. Bone breaks, joint dislocations and bruising can be common and result in birds suffering, carcass downgrading and financial loss. Handling birds with care and consideration can reduce these problems. This leaflet focuses on humane methods for the manual capture and handling of broilers and end-of-lay chickens, turkeys, ducks, geese, guinea fowl and quail. It aims to provide constructive, practical advice to maximise bird welfare and meat quality.

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5. Industry tips: Poultry transport

Practical recommendations for crate and container design, transport during extreme temperatures, and welfare hazards during crating and transport.

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6. Pre-slaughter welfare of broilers

This article will focus on the animal welfare risk factors in the pre-slaughter phase. This phase includes multiple steps: withdrawal of feed and water, catching, loading into transportation crates, and transportation by road. In some cases, chickens may be placed in lairage (waiting area) after arrival at the processing plant. The chickens are then removed from crates, shackled on the processing lines, and stunned prior to actual slaughter.

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7. Humane Broiler Catching: For Catching Crews

Practical guide to improve welfare of the broiler. Catching crew actions impact the welfare of the birds being caught. Poor catching, handling and loading practices are sources of stress and trauma to broilers. If catchers are careful, conscientious and properly supervised, then catchers can reduce the number of injuries to broilers. This leaflet gives some tips about bird behaviour and humane handling.

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8. Preparation of vehicle, driver and loading of poultry

Factsheet for transporters with information on journey planning and preparation, including contingency plans, loading and space on the vehicle, preparation of birds for the journey and loading facilities. It also gives good and better practice recommendations on water, feed and resting times, unloading of animals and their care following unloading and biosecurity, cleaning and disinfection.

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9. Good and Better practices in bird transport

Five-minute video showing how to improve the catching, loading, and transport conditions for broilers.

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10. Guide to good practices for the transport of poultry

Guide on how to ensure the welfare of broilers during transport. It involves recommendations for the preparation of transport and catching, for the right conditions during travelling, and for proper unloading of the animals at the slaughterhouse. The Animal Transport Guide was a project funded by the European Commission and developed between 2015 and 2017 to improve the welfare of the main livestock species (cattle, pigs, poultry, sheep and horses) during their transport within Europe and to third countries for slaughter, fattening and breeding.

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Chapter 8 Optimizing light management

8.1 List of scientific knowledge sources

1. Effects of intermittent lighting program and light colour on ocular health variables as welfare indicators in broiler chickens

Dereli Fidan, E.; Yaygingül, R.; Kaya, M. 2025. Br. Poult. Sci. 66 (1): 10-18. DOI: [10.1080/00071668.2024.2383911](https://doi.org/10.1080/00071668.2024.2383911)

[ABSTRACT](#)

2. Light intensity preferences of broiler chickens is affected by breed, age, time of day and behaviour

van der Eijk, J.A.J.; Izquierdo Garcia-Faria, T.; Melis, S.; van Riel, J.W.; Te Beest, D.E.; de Jong, I.C. 2025. Sci. Rep. 15(1): 6302. DOI: [10.1038/s41598-025-90582-3](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-90582-3)

[ABSTRACT](#)

3. Light spectrum and intensity preferences of fast- and slower-growing broilers vary by age, behaviour and time of day

van der Sluis, M.; van der Eijk, J.A.J.; Izquierdo Garcia-Faria, T.; Te Beest, D.E.; Wolthuis-Fillerup, M.; de Jong, I.C. 2025. Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci. 283: 106532. DOI: [10.1016/j.applanim.2025.106532](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2025.106532)

[ABSTRACT](#)

4. Does the distribution of light intensity within the barn impact broiler production and welfare?

Shynkaruk, T.; Parsons, M.; Adler, C.A.B.; Goeree, C.; Long, K.; Schwean-Lardner, K. 2024. Br. Poult. Sci. DOI: [10.1080/00071668.2024.2414460](https://doi.org/10.1080/00071668.2024.2414460)

[ABSTRACT](#)

5. Effects of a variable light intensity lighting program on the welfare and performance of commercial broiler chickens

Kang, S.W.; Christensen, K.D.; Kidd, M.T.; Orłowski, S.K.; Clark, J. 2023. Front. Physiol. 14: 1059055. DOI: [10.3389/fphys.2023.1059055](https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2023.1059055)

[ABSTRACT](#)

6. Light color and the commercial broiler: effect on behavior, fear, and stress

Remonato Franco, B.; Shynkaruk, T.; Crowe, T.; Fancher, B.; French, N.; Gillingham, S.; Schwean-Lardner, K. 2022. Poult. Sci. 101 (11): 102052. DOI: [10.1016/j.psj.2022.102052](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2022.102052)

[ABSTRACT](#)

7. Effects of a commercial broiler enrichment programme with or without natural light on behaviour and other welfare indicators

De Jong, I.C.; Gunnink, H. 2019. Animal. 13 (2): 384-391. DOI: [10.1017/S1751731118001805](https://doi.org/10.1017/S1751731118001805)

[ABSTRACT](#)

8. Light intensity preferences of broiler chickens: implications for welfare

Raccoursier, M.; Thaxton, Y.V.; Christensen, K.; Aldridge, D.J.; Scanes, C.G. 2019. *Animal*. 13 (12): 2857-2863. DOI: [10.1017/S175173111900123X](https://doi.org/10.1017/S175173111900123X)

[ABSTRACT](#)

9. Effects of color of light on preferences, performance, and welfare in broilers

Riber, A.B. 2015. Effects of color of light on preferences, performance, and welfare in broilers. *Poult. Sci.* 94 (8): 1767-1775. DOI: [10.3382/ps/pev174](https://doi.org/10.3382/ps/pev174)

[ABSTRACT](#)

10. The effect of supplementary ultraviolet wavelengths on broiler chicken welfare indicators

James, C.; Asher, L.; Herborn, K.; Wiseman, J. 2018. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 209, 55-64. DOI: [10.1016/j.applanim.2018.10.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2018.10.002)

[ABSTRACT](#)

8.2 Informative abstracts

1. **Effects of intermittent lighting program and light colour on ocular health variables as welfare indicators in broiler chickens**

The objective of the present study was to examine the effect of lighting programs and light colour on ocular health variables as welfare indicators in Ross 308 broilers. A total of 384, male, one-d-old broiler chickens (Ross 308) were placed in a completely randomised design with a 2 × 2 factorial arrangement of lighting program (continuous or intermittent) and light colour (white and green LED light). Ross 308 broilers under restricted lighting had 18 h of light (18L:6D), while those under intermittent lighting had cycles of 17 L:3D:1 L:3D throughout the experimental period, which lasted 42 d. At the end of the experiment, all eyes of birds (n = 96 birds) underwent a complete ophthalmic examination, which included the Schirmer tear test I, intraocular pressure and eye dimensions. In addition, 32 broilers (eight birds per trial groups) aged 42 d underwent ophthalmic examination to include assessment of ocular ultrasound biometry. Light colour had a significant influence on the mean intraocular pressure (p < 0.001). The Ross 308 broilers kept with intermittent lighting had lower eye weights (2.29 g; p < 0.05), palpebral fissure length (14.39 mm; p < 0.01), eye dorsoventral diameter (17.46 mm; p < 0.05), anteroposterior size (13.70 mm; p < 0.01) and corneal dorsoventral diameter (7.81 mm; p < 0.05) compared to those reared under restricted lighting. In conclusion, these values for Ross 308 broilers may be applied in poultry ophthalmology to detect early eye disease symptoms and to help the diagnosis of tear disorders that could cause economic losses and welfare issues. Intermittent lighting and green LED light may help reduce eye health problems thus contributing to improved welfare in broilers.

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2. **Light intensity preferences of broiler chickens is affected by breed, age, time of day and behaviour**

Light is an important aspect of broiler husbandry and management as it influences behaviour and welfare. However, a lot remains unknown regarding broiler preferences for light intensities, especially for slower-growing broilers which are increasingly used in broiler production systems in the EU. We identified preferences of fast (F)- and slower (S)-growing broilers for intensities in relation to behaviour, age and time of day. Broilers were housed in

pens with four sections, each having one intensity (0.2, 20, 50 or 1000 lx). Both breeds showed more active behaviours at higher intensities and more inactive behaviours at lower intensities. They preferred higher intensities when young and lower intensities when older, with S broilers preferring the lowest intensity more when older. They preferred higher intensities at the end and start of the light period, with F broilers preferring the highest intensity more when young and S broilers more when older. Thus, light intensity could be used to create functional zones within a broiler house for specific behaviours and light intensity programs could be adapted to age and time of day, taking into account breed differences. Furthermore, broilers were always present at each intensity, suggesting individual preferences and offering a choice might be beneficial for broiler welfare.

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3. Light spectrum and intensity preferences of fast- and slower-growing broilers vary by age, behaviour and time of day

Light is an important management factor in broiler production. However, our knowledge of broiler preferences for different lighting conditions is limited, especially regarding changes in preference with age, across breeds with different growth rates and for different behaviours. Here we investigated preferences of fast- (Ross 308; R) and slower-growing (Hubbard JA757; H) broilers for a combination of light spectra (sky blue (S) and green (G) light) and intensities (15 and 100 lux), examining over time 1) where broilers chose to spend most time, 2) what behaviours were performed, and 3) the feed intake of the birds. A choice test setup was applied, where broilers were housed in replicate pens with four compartments that they could freely move between, with the four light conditions (15S, 15G, 100S and 100G) provided in the separate compartments. The birds' locations were scored every five minutes, two days a week, using an automated computer vision approach. Behaviour was observed through instantaneous scan sampling at five ages per breed and feed intake was recorded per compartment approximately every week. It was observed that broilers initially spent most of the daytime in bright, G light (week 1), before a preference for bright, S light came up (weeks 2–3 for R broilers, week 2 for H broilers) and then no clear preference was visible for weeks 4–6 for R and 3–6 for H broilers. For H broilers, a preference for low intensity light was shown in weeks 7–8 with no clear preference for G or S light. We observed differences in the proportions of behaviours shown in the light treatments, with more inactive behaviour in dimmer and S light conditions and more active behaviours in brighter and/or G light conditions. Furthermore, there was an initial higher feed intake in 100G for R birds, and a higher feed intake in 100S than in 15S later on. For H birds, there was a higher feed intake at 15 lux than at 100 lux (for both spectra) at the end of the production period. Overall, the outcomes of this study highlight that broiler preferences for specific light conditions differ between breeds, ages and for different behaviours. These outcomes can inform the development of functional lighting programs for fast- and slower-growing broilers and suggest that providing broilers with variation in light conditions in space and time may better suit the birds' behavioural needs and preferences, hereby potentially improving broiler welfare.

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4. Does the distribution of light intensity within the barn impact broiler production and welfare?

The objective of this study was to determine if rearing broilers under variable light intensity (VLI) impacted their welfare or productivity. Ross 308 broilers ($n = 7,256$) were reared until 35 d of age and exposed to a uniform intensity of 10 lux (CON) or VLI with low intensity areas of 2–5 lux proximal to the walls and high intensity areas of 84–133 lux proximal to feeders. The data were analysed as a complete randomised design using an analysis of variance. Significance was declared when $p \leq 0.05$. Applying VLI resulted in increased feed

intake early in life but had no impact on body weight. Overall efficiency was improved in the CON treatment. Mortality diagnoses of skeletal problems were reduced under VLI. Treatment had no impact on footpad, hock or gait score, heterophil to lymphocyte ratio or melatonin concentration. Birds performed certain behaviours in specific locations within the room, independent of light intensity treatment. In conclusion, raising broilers under VLI had little impact on production or most welfare parameters assessed in this study. However, satisfying the bird's preference for different light intensities may improve welfare.

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5. Effects of a variable light intensity lighting program on the welfare and performance of commercial broiler chickens

Our previous variable-light intensity lighting program studies indicate the light intensity preference behavior of broilers for their daily activity including eating and resting. To evaluate the effects of variable-light intensity lighting program on performance and welfare of broilers, four commercial trials were conducted for looking at behaviors, mortality, leg-health, performance, and brain welfare indicator genes including tryptophan hydroxylase 2 and tyrosine hydroxylase (TH), glucocorticoid receptor (GR), brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), and melanopsin (Opn4) gene expression. One-day-old broilers were housed in four commercial broiler houses. Each quadrant (section) of the house was placed with 4,800 chicks. A total of four lighting programs began on day 7 with 5 lux (lx), 20 lx, natural light (NL, 480 lx), and variable light (2–5/40 lx) using LED lights on a 16L:8D photoperiod. In the variable-light house, the number of dustbathing holes was significantly higher than that in natural-light houses and 5-lx and 20-lx houses. Daily physical activities, footpad condition, fear response to novel objects, body weight, feed conversion ratio, and the number of leg-problem induced culled birds were affected by the variable-light intensity lighting program. Expression of tryptophan hydroxylase 2 in the DRN and VTA of variable-light treated birds was lower than that of 5-lx- and 20-lx-treated birds on day 42 ($p < 0.05$). Higher expression of VTA-TH in 5-lx-treated birds than that in 20-lx-, NL-, and variable-light-treated birds suggests the high stress-susceptibility of 5-lx treated birds. Lower VTA-GR expression in 20-lx- and variable-light-treated birds indicates lower stress than that in NL- and 5-lx-treated birds ($p < 0.05$). The VTA-BDNF expression of NL-treated birds was 2.5 fold higher than that of 5lx-, 20-lx-, and variable-light-treated birds ($p < 0.05$), and variable-light-treated birds showed the lowest level of BDNF expression ($p < 0.05$), suggesting the chronic social defeat stress in NL-treated birds. The result of VTA-Opn4 expression on day 42 suggests the possible role of VTA-Opn4 in broiler welfare through central light perception. Taken together, the variable-light intensity lighting program increased volunteer natural behaviors and physical activity, which may improve footpad condition and leg health of birds, consequently. Performance data including the increased daily weight gain and the lowered feed conversion ratio and results of brain welfare indicator gene expression showed the beneficial effect of the variable-light intensity lighting program on the performance and welfare of commercial broilers.

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6. Light color and the commercial broiler: effect on behavior, fear, and stress

Light is an important component in poultry production, and it may impact bird behavior, an important component of animal welfare. Light-emitting diode (LED) lamps are of interest for broiler production since they are inexpensive to run and provide monochromatic colors. This study aimed to understand the impact of three light colors (blue, green, or white), provided by LED lighting, on behavioral expression, stress and fear levels of broilers. A total of 14,256 male and female broilers of 2 genotypes (Ross EPMx708 and Ross YPMx708) were housed in 9 rooms in 2 blocked trials (3 room replicates per light per trial), with sexes and genotypes housed in 12 separate pens per room. Behavioral expression was recorded using an infrared

camera and analyzed using a scan sampling technique. To assess fear, 3 tests were conducted: tonic immobility, novel object, and response to observer. Blood was collected to evaluate chronic stress using the heterophil:lymphocyte (H:L) ratio. Data were statistically analyzed using SAS (MIXED procedure) in a $3 \times 2 \times 2$ factorial design, with lighting treatment nested within room. Fear tests indicated reduced fear levels in birds raised under blue light (lower latency to rise during the tonic immobility test and a lower percentage of birds moving due to the passage by of an observer). No differences were observed for the novel object test. Light color resulted in changes in stress levels, indicated by a lower H:L ratio for broilers raised under blue light compared to those raised under white light. Behavior was influenced by light color, especially at 33 to 34 d of age, where birds raised under white light were more active, and birds raised under blue light spent more time resting. Overall, results indicated that light color has minor influences on behavioral expression. Utilizing blue light during the brooding and rearing phase leads to lower stress and a reduction in fear, suggesting that blue light may improve the emotional states of fear and stress, thereby improving the welfare of poultry.

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7. Effects of a commercial broiler enrichment programme with or without natural light on behaviour and other welfare indicators

Commercial broiler production systems based on market initiatives to improve animal welfare beyond minimum legal requirements have emerged in several European countries. A common factor in the 'higher welfare' indoor systems is the application of environmental enrichment, with or without natural light, to promote locomotor activity and natural behaviours of the broiler chickens. In the current study, we evaluated the effects of a commercial enrichment programme for fast-growing indoor-housed broiler chickens, with or without natural light entering the broiler house. Enrichment materials were selected in relation to perceived minimal hygiene risk and ease of cleaning in between production cycles. Selected enrichments were a combination of wood shavings bales (1.5 bale/1000 chickens), round metal perches (2.7 m/1000 chickens) and metal chains as pecking objects (1/1000 chickens). Three treatments were studied: control (C) without enrichment and natural light, enriched (E) with enrichments as previously defined but without natural light and enriched plus natural light (EL) with enrichments as previously defined and natural light entrance. The experiment was carried out during five subsequent production cycles on one commercial broiler farm with three identical houses. EL could only be assigned to the middle house that was equipped with roof windows (light entrance area: 3% of floor space). C and E were in the two outer houses (alternated in between production cycles). Behaviour was observed during daytime at days 25 and 39 of age by scan sampling. Lameness, footpad dermatitis, hock burn, cleanliness and injuries were scored at the same ages, in addition to the response of the chickens to a novel object. Results showed that the treatments only affected broiler behaviour. E flocks showed significantly more resting as compared with EL and C. EL flocks showed significantly more walking, exploration and foraging behaviour as compared with E and C. Thus, broiler activity was highest in the EL treatment and lowest in the E treatment, with the C treatment in between. No treatment effects were found on the other welfare indicators and only a few tendencies for treatment effects were found for the novel object test, with E birds tending to be more reluctant to approach the object as compared with EL and C birds. We concluded that providing environmental enrichment and natural light-stimulated activity and natural behaviours in broiler chickens, whereas providing enrichment only seemed to have the opposite effect as compared with control flocks without enrichment.

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8. Light intensity preferences of broiler chickens: implications for welfare

There is considerable debate as to the optimal light intensities for growing chickens. This is influencing regulations and industry practices. The present study examines the preference of broiler chickens for light intensity. A choice system was developed to allow determination of the preferences of broiler chickens for light intensity. This system had three light proof pens each with feeders or waterers but different light intensities. There was a connecting transit pen with a light intensity of 1 to 2 lux. This allowed birds access to the pens each with feeders or waterers. There were markedly more chickens observed in the pens each with feeders or waterers and a light intensity of 20 lux than 5 lux. Moreover, more feed was consumed in the 20 lux pens than 5 pens. There were also high numbers of chickens in the transit compartment with its low light intensity (1 to 2 lux) and no feeders or waterers. Broiler chickens exhibited a preference for 20 lux light intensity for feeding compared to 5 lux light intensity. The present study supports the view that there should be a light intensity of at least 20 lux for the areas around the feeders and also suggests that light intensity may be reduced in other areas for resting and other activities.

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9. Effects of color of light on preferences, performance, and welfare in broilers

Broiler houses are mainly lit by fluorescent light. With the expected continued increase in energy prices, the interest in less energy consuming light sources is growing. The light-emitting diode (LED) is an energy-saving alternative. The aims of the present 2 studies were to examine 1) the preference for LED color temperature and effects on behavior, and 2) effects of LED color temperature on performance and welfare of male broilers (Ross 308). Two color temperatures were investigated: neutral-white (4,100 K) and cold-white (6,065 K). First, 6 groups of 6-day-old chicks were housed in pens consisting of 2 lightproof compartments with a pop-hole between allowing chicks to move freely between compartments. Number of broilers in each compartment and their behavior were recorded every 15 min on 6 d. A preference for 6,065 K was found ($P < 0.001$). On d 16, 28, and 34, more time was spent in the 6,065 K treatment ($P < 0.03$), whereas indifference between treatments was found on d 4, 10, and 22 ($P > 0.07$). Second, each of the 2 light conditions was applied to 6 groups of 75 chicks. BW and feed consumption were registered weekly. On d 34, we scored gait, foot pad dermatitis, and hock burns in 15 individuals/pen. At slaughter (d 35), cold carcass weight was recorded from all individuals, while yields of different body parts were collected from 9 individuals/group. Broilers from the 6,065 K treatment were 67.4 ± 19.2 g heavier on the day of slaughter ($P = 0.0009$), whereas no difference was found at other ages ($P > 0.12$). Feed intake was found to be similar for the 2 treatments ($P = 0.52$). Pectoralis minor was 4.1 ± 1.9 g heavier in the 6,065 K treatment ($P = 0.03$). There was no difference between the light treatments in any of the welfare parameters. We conclude from the results that of the 2 color temperatures examined, the most suitable for use in commercial broiler houses is 6,065 K.

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10. The effect of supplementary ultraviolet wavelengths on broiler chicken welfare indicators

Qualities of the light environment are important for good welfare in a number of species. In chickens, UVA light is visible and may facilitate flock interactions. UVB wavelengths promote endogenous vitamin D synthesis, which could support the rapid skeletal development of broiler chickens. The aim of the study was to investigate the impacts of Ultraviolet wavelengths (UV) on welfare indicators in broiler chickens. Day-old Ross 308 birds reared under commercially representative conditions were randomly assigned to one of three lighting treatments: A) White Light Emitting Diode (LED) and supplementary UVA LED lighting (18-hour photoperiod); B) White LED with supplementary UVA and UVB fluorescent lighting providing 30 micro watts/cm² UVB at bird level (on for 8 h of the total photoperiod to avoid

over-exposure of UVB); C) White LED control group, representative of farm conditions (18-hour photoperiod). Welfare indicators measured were; feather condition (day 24, n = 546), tonic immobility duration (day 29, n = 302), and gait quality, using the Bristol Gait Score (day 31, n = 293). Feather condition was improved in male broilers in the UVA treatment (A), compared to the control treatment (C). Birds in the UVA treatment had shorter tonic immobility durations compared to the control treatment (C), suggesting lower fearfulness. Broilers reared in UVA (A) and UVA + UVB (B) had better Bristol Gait Scores compared to the control (C). Together these results suggest UV may be beneficial for broiler chicken welfare. While treatment A and B both provided UVA, the improvements in welfare indicators were not consistent, which may be due to exposure time-dependent beneficial effects of UVA. The modification of commercial lighting regimes to incorporate UVA wavelengths for indoor-reared broiler chickens would be an achievable change with significant positive impacts on bird welfare.

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8.3 List of practical knowledge sources

1. Why broilers need darkness everyday

WattPoultry, 2022. <https://www.wattagnet.com/broilers-turkeys/article/15532654/why-broilers-need-darkness-everyday>

[SUMMARY](#)

2. Farmers urged to fortify broiler chicks' welfare for approaching winter

Herald Online, 2024. <https://www.heraldonline.co.zw/farmers-urged-to-fortify-broiler-chicks-welfare-for-approaching-winter/>

[SUMMARY](#)

3. Light spectrum and intensity preferences of broilers

Poultry World, 2023. <https://www.poultryworld.net/poultry/broilers/light-spectrum-and-intensity-preferences-of-broilers/>

[SUMMARY](#)

4. Poultry house lighting must meet the needs of birds' eyes

Poultry World, 2018. <https://www.poultryworld.net/health-nutrition/poultry-house-lighting-must-meet-the-needs-of-birds-eyes/>

[SUMMARY](#)

5. Gradient lighting emerging in the U.S. poultry industry

WATTPoultry, 2022. <https://www.wattagnet.com/broilers-turkeys/broilers/article/15536840/gradient-lighting-emerging-in-the-us-poultry-industry>

[SUMMARY](#)

6. Why LED lighting can improve layer and broiler margins

Farmers Weekly, 2020. <https://www.fwi.co.uk/livestock/poultry/why-led-lighting-can-improve-layer-and-broiler-margins>

[SUMMARY](#)

7. Proper lighting when fattening broilers

De Heus, 2021. <https://www.deheus.com/articles/insights/proper-lighting-when-fattening-broilers>

[SUMMARY](#)

8. Lighting for Broilers

Aviagen, 2010.

https://en.aviagen.com/assets/Tech_Center/Broiler_Breeder_Tech_Articles/English/LightingforBroilers1.pdf

[SUMMARY](#)

9. Evaluating broiler house lighting intensity, wavelength

WATTPoultry, 2022. <https://www.wattagnet.com/broilers-turkeys/broilers/article/15536521/evaluating-broiler-house-lighting-intensity-wavelength>

[SUMMARY](#)

10. Four factors to select ideal poultry-house lighting systems

Modern Poultry, 2024. <https://modernpoultry.media/four-factors-to-select-ideal-poultry-house-lighting-systems/?mp=1748442296555>

[SUMMARY](#)

8.4 Informative summaries

1. **Why broilers need darkness everyday**

Commercial broiler birds may not spend enough time in the dark. At least four hours of darkness a day should be provided for the best performance.

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2. **Farmers urged to fortify broiler chicks' welfare for approaching winter**

With winter fast setting in, poultry experts have urged farmers to prioritise the well-being of broiler chicks by providing proper bedding, curtains and lighting to ensure they achieve optimal growth and market returns.

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3. **Light spectrum and intensity preferences of broilers**

Chickens prefer variation in light conditions in their environment to help them with natural behaviours such as foraging and resting.

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4. **Poultry house lighting must meet the needs of birds' eyes**

Measurements of light in poultry houses and assessment of illuminants have until now been based on parameters developed for human perception of light.

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5. **Gradient lighting emerging in the U.S. poultry industry**

Creating a gradient of lighting intensities inside a chicken house using natural or artificial lighting may be the way of the future for the integrated poultry industry.

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6. **Why LED lighting can improve layer and broiler margins**

Research work has shown modern lighting systems can increase layer production by up to 38 eggs a hen and gross margins by 0.87p/kg on broiler units.

But lighting often slips down the list of potential performance inhibitors because flock-keepers assume systems are effective as long as they are functioning. Correct lighting will stimulate the birds' natural day/night behaviour in a housed environment.

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7. **Proper lighting when fattening broilers**

From breeding to slaughter, every phases in rearing broilers requires an optimal light plan.

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8. **Lighting for Broilers**

Traditionally, it has been assumed that using long daylengths for broilers will maximize growth rate. However recent research examining the relationship between daylength and a range of characteristics in commercial broilers has shown that this is not always correct. This document gives updated information on the response of broilers (Production, meat yield, and welfare parameters) to daylength.

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9. **Evaluating broiler house lighting intensity, wavelength**

The correct management of broiler house lighting will help to ensure that birds perform well and that welfare is not compromised.

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10. **Four factors to select ideal poultry-house lighting systems**

Poultry-production systems are continually evolving, with advancements in research and technology allowing greater precision in meeting the unique needs of bird genetic lines and individual flocks.

Lighting, among other factors like feeding and ventilation, plays a critical role in the growth and behavior of poultry and should be given careful consideration.

Gabrielle House, PhD, ONCE by Signify, discusses the four main factors to consider when selecting which light source is best for your poultry house: light source, light spectrum, dimmability and light plan design.

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Chapter 9 Reducing stress during thinning

9.1 List of scientific knowledge sources

1. The association between meat inspection codes, footpad lesions and thinning of broiler flocks in the Danish broiler production

Alfifi, A., Dalsgaard, A., Christensen, J.P., Larsen, M.H., Sandberg, M. 2020. *Prev. Vet. Med.* 185:105205. DOI: [10.1016/j.prevetmed.2020.105205](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2020.105205).

ABSTRACT

2. Effects of financial incentives and cessation of thinning on prevalence of Campylobacter: a longitudinal monitoring study on commercial broiler farms in the UK

Higham, L.E.; Scott, C.; Akehurst, K.; Dring, D.; Parnham, A.; Waterman, M.; Bright, A. 2018. *Vet. Rec.* 183: 595-595. DOI: [10.1136/vr.104823](https://doi.org/10.1136/vr.104823)

ABSTRACT

3. Effects of season, catching method, and thinning on carcass quality and production parameters in 4 different broiler production systems in the Netherlands

Emous, R.A.; van Harn, J.; van Riel, J.W. *Poult. Sci.* 103 (6): 103688. DOI: [10.1016/j.psj.2024.103688](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2024.103688)

ABSTRACT

4. The effect of partial depopulation on Campylobacter introduction in broiler houses

Hertogs, K.; Heyndrickx, M.; Gelaude, P.; Zutter, L. de; Dewulf, J.; Rasschaert, G. 2021. *Poult. Sci.* 100 (2): 1076-1082. DOI: [10.1016/j.psj.2020.11.017](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2020.11.017)

ABSTRACT

5. Stakeholder perceptions on broiler chicken welfare during first-day processing and the pre-slaughter phase: a case study in Belgium

Lambrecht, E., Jacobs, L., Delezie, E., De Steur, H., Gellynck, X., Tuytens, F. 2020. *World's Poult. Sci. J.* 76(3), 473-492. DOI: [10.1080/00439339.2020.1790329](https://doi.org/10.1080/00439339.2020.1790329)

ABSTRACT

6. Improving welfare in catching and transport of chickens

Jacobs, L.; Tuytens, F.A.M. 2020. In Christine Nicol (Ed.): *Understanding the behaviour and improving the welfare of chickens*. 1st edition. Philadelphia, PA: Burleigh Dodds Science Publishing, pp. 417-458. DOI: [10.1201/9781003048039](https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003048039)

ABSTRACT

7. Welfare of domestic birds and rabbits transported in containers

EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare (AHAW). 2022. *EFSA J.* 20 (9): e07441. DOI: [10.2903/j.efsa.2022.7441](https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2022.7441).

ABSTRACT

8. Effects of pre-slaughter fasting on broiler welfare, meat quality, and intestinal integrity

Pereira, R.E.P., Martins, M.R.F.B., Mendes, A.A., Almeida, P.A.Z., Komiyama, C.M., Milbradt, E.L., Fernandes, B.D.S. 2013. *Braz. J. Poult. Sci.* 15, 119-122. DOI: [10.1590/S1516-635X2013000200007](https://doi.org/10.1590/S1516-635X2013000200007)

ABSTRACT

9. An investigation of broiler caecal *Campylobacter* counts at first and second thinning

Koolman, L., Whyte, P., Bolton, D.J. 2014. *J. Appl. Microbiol.* 117(3), 876-881. DOI: [10.1111/jam.12580](https://doi.org/10.1111/jam.12580)

ABSTRACT

10. Comparison of the Automatic and Manual Broiler Pre-Slaughter Chain Based on Trailer Microclimate during Transportation and Its Effect on *m. pectoralis major*

Beňo, F., Škorpiľová, T., Pohůnek, V., Bauer, J., Ševčík, R. 2021. *Animals* 11(10): 2946 DOI: [10.3390/ani11102946](https://doi.org/10.3390/ani11102946)

ABSTRACT

9.2 Informative abstracts

1. The association between meat inspection codes, footpad lesions and thinning of broiler flocks in the Danish broiler production

The foundation of the condemnation practices in Post-Mortem Inspection (PMI) of poultry should be based on up-to-date scientific evidence about the cause of infection and hence whether the lesions observed are of food safety, animal health or welfare concerns. This study aimed to investigate the association between meat inspection codes, footpad lesions, and thinning of flocks in Danish broiler production. The data set was based on the delivery of chicken flocks to one of the two larger chicken slaughterhouses in Denmark, representing 71 farms, 174 houses, and 4,068 flocks over three years from January 2016 to December 2018. Post-mortem condemnation data of slaughtered chickens recorded and stored in the Danish Quality Assurance System (KIK) database was used in the study. Five potentially causal models were developed to investigate whether there was an association between dermatitis, arthritis, systemic infection, emaciation, mortality and possible explaining factors` (footpad lesion, age at slaughter, scratches, ascites, systemic infection and thinning of the flock). These five ecological logistic regression models were analyzed with the three levels: farm, house, and flock. Data from a total number of 126,137,002 (N) slaughtered chickens recorded in KIK databases were used for modeling and analyses. The prevalence of condemned carcasses was 1.1 % (n = 1,420,812). Overall, 12 individual reasons for condemnation of carcasses were recorded. The most frequently observed reason for condemnation was skin disease (scratches and dermatitis) with a prevalence of 0.5 %. Prevalence of ascites was 0.2 %, discoloration 0.09 %, emaciation 0.09 %, hepatitis 0.09 % and arthritis 0.07 %. In the first model, dermatitis was shown to be positively associated with age at slaughter with an OR = 1.04 (CI95 %: 1.02–1.05), while arthritis was considered an intervening variable. Moreover, there was a small protective effect of thinning of the flock for first and second delivery. There was a positive association between arthritis and age at the time of slaughter with an OR = 1.13 (CI95 %: 1.12–1.15). Systemic infections were associated with scratches with an OR = 24.5 (CI95 %: 16.6–36.3) and footpad lesions with

an OR = 1.007 (CI95 %: 1.006–1.008). Further modelling of emaciation and mortality was not considered because of unbalanced groups in the data probably caused by the fact that some condemnation codes were rare. We observed that the most common causal factors of condemnation in the systemic infection models were scratches and footpad lesion, therefore preventing and controlling such lesions could reduce losses. Specific management and environmental etiological factors of the main infections causing condemnation in Danish broilers should be determined.

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2. Effects of financial incentives and cessation of thinning on prevalence of Campylobacter: a longitudinal monitoring study on commercial broiler farms in the UK

Campylobacter is the leading cause of food poisoning in the UK. 2 Sisters Food Group, with retail partners, monitored the effect that: (1) awarding financial incentives to farmers and stockpersons for producing houses that were not highly contaminated with Campylobacter, or (2) the cessation of thinning (where ~30 per cent of birds are removed and processed at around day 35 of the crop cycle), had on prevalence of Campylobacter on UK broiler farms in a longitudinal monitoring study. Ninety-four farms and 759 houses were monitored from November 2013 to October 2015, with and without interventions. Financial incentives and thinning were significantly associated with Campylobacter prevalence. Houses on farms receiving an incentive had a 54 percent reduction in odds of being highly contaminated with Campylobacter. Houses that were thinned had a 309 per cent increase in odds of being highly contaminated. Temperature and bird age were significantly positively associated with Campylobacter. Changes in industry practice at supply chain level can support Campylobacter control plans in commercial broiler locks. Elucidating farm-level factors associated with Campylobacter prevalence (such as house type, condition, lock size) as well as individual factors related to thinning (stocking density, weight profile and associated economic consequences) require further investigation

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3. Effects of season, catching method, and thinning on carcass quality and production parameters in 4 different broiler production systems in the Netherlands

In the Netherlands, poultry meat production has been evolving in recent years toward broiler production systems with slow-growing broilers. In this study the effects of season, catching method, and thinning on carcass quality and production parameters in four different broiler production systems in the Netherlands was evaluated. The data for this study were collected from slaughterhouse data in 2018, 2019, and 2020 and contained information about four different broiler production systems: conventional (fast growing) broilers (CONV), 2 different indoor slow-growing broilers (SGB1 and SGB2), and Better Life 1 Star (BLS) concept with slow-growing broilers. The data set consisted of 14,976, 1,730, 3,713, and 1,121 records (flocks) for CONV, SGB1, SGB2, and BLS, respectively. All three production systems with slow-growing broilers had a lower slaughter weight, average daily gain (ADG), first-week mortality, and total mortality than CONV (no-thinning). ADG of SGB2 and BLS was lower than that of SGB1. Slaughter weight and ADG were the lowest when day-old chicks were placed in March/April and the highest when they were placed in September/October. All slow-growing broiler production systems had a lower footpad lesion score and a lower incidence of hock burns, leg hematomas, breast hematomas, dead-on-arrival chickens (DOA), and total rejects than CONV. Autumn flocks had more hock burns, a higher footpad lesion score, and more wing hematomas than spring flocks. More scabby hips and fewer total rejects were found during the summer months than during the winter months. Thinning flocks had more scabby hips, ammonia burns, and DOAs and fewer hock burns, footpad lesions, wing

hematomas, leg hematomas, breast hematomas, and total rejects than no-thinning flocks. Mechanically caught flocks had more ammonia burns, DOAs, and total rejects than manually caught flocks. In conclusion, this study showed that all three production systems with slow-growing broilers had a lower first-week mortality and total mortality and better scores on most carcass quality parameters and welfare indicators than CONV.

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4. The effect of partial depopulation on Campylobacter introduction in broiler houses

Poultry is seen as the main reservoir for Campylobacter. Control of this zoonotic pathogen in primary production could potentially reduce the colonization in broiler flocks and consequently reduce the number of human infections. In the present study, 20 broiler flocks from 10 farms, were sampled immediately before and 5 to 7 d after partial depopulation (thinning) for the presence of Campylobacter using cecal droppings and overshoes. At the time of thinning, the catching crew, transportation vehicles, forklift, and transport containers were sampled for the presence of Campylobacter. Samples were cultivated; presumed positive isolates were confirmed by PCR. The isolates were molecularly typed by flaA restriction analysis and pulsed field gel electrophoresis. Results show that all flocks were thinned using Campylobacter-contaminated equipment and materials. One-third of the broiler flocks became colonized after thinning. In 67% of the colonization cases, identical strains were found matching those of container systems, transport trucks, and/or forklifts. This identifies thinning as an important risk factor for Campylobacter introduction into broiler houses. Setup and compliance with biosecurity practices during thinning is essential to prevent Campylobacter colonization of broiler flocks.

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5. Stakeholder perceptions on broiler chicken welfare during first-day processing and the pre-slaughter phase: a case study in Belgium

Day of hatch and pre-slaughter processing are stressful events (involving selection, handling and transport) for broiler chickens, putting pressure on welfare, which has economic consequences. This case-study documented common industry practices and evaluated poultry industry stakeholder perceptions related to broiler welfare during day-of-hatch processing and the pre-slaughter phase. Twenty-three individual in-depth interviews were conducted with representatives of key stakeholders in the Flemish poultry sector: hatchery personnel (five), farmers (six), poultry catchers (two), transporters (three) and slaughterhouse personnel (seven). The findings showed various factors influencing broiler welfare during day of hatch processing and the pre-slaughter phase, with some discrepancies between stakeholder views and the scientific evidence. While stakeholders perceived the day of hatch processing procedures of chicks to be relatively under control, with no major issues, literature points out several issues, including first-week mortality and time without feed and water as major welfare problems. For broilers at slaughter age, the industry stakeholders' views aligned well with scientific evidence on major welfare issues, such as injuries, thermal stress, mortality during fasting, catching, loading, transportation and lairage. This study provides novel insights in stakeholder perceptions, and potential avenues for future research and actions to reduce animal welfare problems in the poultry sector.

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6. Improving welfare in catching and transport of chickens

The pre-slaughter phase is the last stage of meat production and for broiler chickens entails feed and water withdrawal, catching, loading, transportation and lairage. Major stressors during pre-slaughter include rough handling, overstocking, thermal stress, and prolonged feed and water withdrawal that can result in injuries, mortality, fear, and distress. The annual

global economic loss could roughly vary from 143 million to 3 billion dollars for condemned parts due to injuries, and from 6 to 14 billion dollars for weight loss. Broiler welfare during catching could be improved by gentler mechanical catching and loading, alternative upright manual catching, training of catching crews, herding, and fitness-for-transport assessment. Improvements related to transport include using climate-controlled systems, reducing transport duration or making transportation redundant by on-farm slaughter. In order to reduce animal suffering and associated production losses during pre-slaughter, we recommend an approach with systematic monitoring of animal-based welfare indicators, feedback to responsible actors, and incentives to act when acceptable thresholds are (repeatedly) surpassed. Although this chapter focuses on broiler chickens, the laying hen pre-slaughter phase is briefly discussed as well.

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7. Welfare of domestic birds and rabbits transported in containers

This opinion, produced upon a request from the European Commission, focuses on transport of domestic birds and rabbits in containers (e.g. any crate, box, receptacle or other rigid structure used for the transport of animals, but not the means of transport itself). It describes and assesses current transport practices in the EU, based on data from literature, Member States and expert opinion. The species and categories of domestic birds assessed were mainly chickens for meat (broilers), end-of-lay hens and day-old chicks. They included to a lesser extent pullets, turkeys, ducks, geese, quails and game birds, due to limited scientific evidence. The opinion focuses on road transport to slaughterhouses or to production sites. For day-old chicks, air transport is also addressed. The relevant stages of transport considered are preparation, loading, journey, arrival and uncrating. Welfare consequences associated with current transport practices were identified for each stage. For loading and uncrating, the highly relevant welfare consequences identified are handling stress, injuries, restriction of movement and sensory overstimulation. For the journey and arrival, injuries, restriction of movement, sensory overstimulation, motion stress, heat stress, cold stress, prolonged hunger and prolonged thirst are identified as highly relevant. For each welfare consequence, animal-based measures (ABMs) and hazards were identified and assessed, and both preventive and corrective or mitigative measures proposed. Recommendations on quantitative criteria to prevent or mitigate welfare consequences are provided for microclimatic conditions, space allowances and journey times for all categories of animals, where scientific evidence and expert opinion support such outcomes.

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8. Effects of pre-slaughter fasting on broiler welfare, meat quality, and intestinal integrity

The Brazilian Ministry of Agriculture (MAPA) regulations establish 12 hours as the maximum pre-slaughter fasting period for broilers; however, many processing plants have considered this time is not sufficient, and consequently return the birds to the farms, with consequent economic losses and welfare problems. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate the possible effects of longer pre-slaughter fasting times. The objective of the present study was to evaluate the effect of pre-slaughter fasting times longer than those established by MAPA on broiler welfare, breast meat quality, and intestinal integrity. Forty 42-d-old broilers were submitted to different pre-slaughter fasting times: group I: 6 hours, group II 9h, group III 12h, and group IV 15h. Bird welfare was assessed before slaughter. After sacrifice, intestinal samples were collected to assess their morphology and morphometrics, and the Pectoralis major muscle was analyzed for pH and color. There was no influence ($p>0.05$) of treatments on breast muscle pH or color. There were no significant changes in intestinal morphometrics ($p<0.05$). Bird behavior was affected ($p<0.05$), suggesting that welfare was impaired as fasting time increased, but no differences in the analyzed parameters were

detected between broilers fasted for 12 or 15 hours. It was concluded that the behavioral differences between birds fasted for 12 and 15 hours are not sufficient to assert that those fasted for 15 hours were in worse welfare conditions.

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9. **An investigation of broiler caecal Campylobacter counts at first and second thinning**

Aims

The objectives of this study were the following: (i) to investigate if Campylobacter negative flocks at first thinning remain negative at second thinning; (ii) to determine if the caecal counts in birds infected during first thinning remain lower than in birds that were positive at first thinning; and (iii) to determine if reducing the time between first and second thinning to a maximum of 4 days would reduce both the incidence and prevalence of broiler caecal contamination.

Methods and Results

Twenty-two flocks were tested at first and second thinning using ISO methodologies. Of the 14 that had a 4-day duration between first and second thinning, nine flocks were Campylobacter negative at first thinning. By second thinning, all 14 flocks were positive and Campylobacter counts ranged from 5.5 to 6.6 log₁₀ CFU g⁻¹ regardless of the status at first thinning. The other eight flocks were all Campylobacter positive at first thinning with counts ranging from 0.8 to 6.1 log₁₀ CFU g⁻¹ which increased to 5.1 to 6.9 log₁₀ CFU g⁻¹ by second thinning (3–10 days). PCR speciation and MLST genotyping suggested the majority of isolates were Camp. jejuni belonging to STs 257, 814, 6763 and 6764.

Conclusions

It was concluded that; thinning introduces Campylobacter into broiler flocks; caecal counts in birds at second thinning are similar, regardless of flock status at first thinning and reducing the time between first and second thinning to a maximum of 4 days is not an effective control strategy.

Significance and Impact of the Study

This study informs Campylobacter control strategy at primary production, suggesting all post-first thinning broilers should be treated as 'high risk' regardless of Campylobacter status at first thinning or duration between first and second thinning.

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10. **Comparison of the Automatic and Manual Broiler Pre-Slaughter Chain Based on Trailer Microclimate during Transportation and Its Effect on m. pectoralis major**

This study aims to compare two broiler pre-slaughter chain methods: (i) the automatic pre-slaughter chain (APC) and (ii) manual pre-slaughter chain (MPC). The comparison is based on the evaluation of the trailer microclimate, number of injuries, and breast muscle (m. pectoralis major) quality. Transportation lasts 3.5 h, unloading 1 h. The selection of two hundred 39-day-old broilers (Ross 308 and Cobb 500 breeds) is random for each type of method. After slaughter, the pH value, electrical conductivity (EC), and color (lightness) of breast muscle tissues are determined at different post-mortem intervals. The MPC negatively affects the microclimate ($p < 0.001$), meat qualitative characteristics ($p < 0.001$), and places a greater strain on the body of chickens compared with APC. The average pH_{15min} value of MPC broiler breast muscle tissue, generally used as the main meat quality parameter, is 5.97 ± 0.12 , in contrast to 6.36 ± 0.16 for APC. Higher pH_{15min} value of APC indicates better

welfare and pre-slaughter handling. Values of EC and L* of breast tissues also confirms a difference between the methods of broiler handling ($p < 0.001$). No difference is found between the breed lines ($p > 0.05$).

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9.3 List of practical knowledge sources

1. Flock Thinning to Be Banned on RSPCA Assured Farms

The Poultry Site. 2015. <https://www.thepoultrysite.com/news/2015/12/flock-thinning-to-be-banned-on-rspca-assured-farms>

[SUMMARY](#)

2. European Chicken Commitment (and thinning)

Albert Schweitzer Foundation. <https://albertschweitzerfoundation.org/campaigns/european-chicken-commitment>

[SUMMARY](#)

3. Pre-Processing Handling in Broilers

Aviagen. 2012.

https://en.aviagen.com/assets/Tech_Center/Ross_Tech_Articles/RossTechNotePreProcessHandlingOct2012.pdf

[SUMMARY](#)

4. Economic consequences of stopping 'thinning' in broiler production

Poultry world. 2022. <https://www.poultryworld.net/poultry/broilers/economic-consequences-of-stopping-thinning-in-broiler-production/>

[SUMMARY](#)

5. All in-All out: No thinning

BroilerNet (Finnish Poultry Association). 2024. <https://broilernet.eu/all-in-all-out-no-thinning/>

[SUMMARY](#)

6. Global Broiler Chicken Certification Schemes Comparison Table

Compassion In World Farming. 2017.

https://www.compassionlebensmittelwirtschaft.de/media/akid1klw/how-welfare-schemes-compare-to-compassions-criteria-for-higher-welfare_broilers.pdf

[SUMMARY](#)

7. Broiler production with reduced antibiotics. The essentials

EW Nutrition. 2021. <https://ew-nutrition.com/broiler-production-with-reduced-antibiotics-the-essentials/>

[SUMMARY](#)

8. Zoonotic diseases, human health, and farm animal welfare: Campylobacter

Compassion In World Farming. 2013.

<https://www.ciwf.org.uk/media/3756117/Campylobacter.pdf>

SUMMARY

9. Economic consequences of stopping 'thinning' in broiler production

Poultry World, 2022 <https://www.poultryworld.net/poultry/broilers/economic-consequences-of-stopping-thinning-in-broiler-production/>

SUMMARY

10. Importance of feed withdrawal and the loading process to the poultry industry

WATTPoultry, 2020. <https://www.wattagnet.com/home/article/15531149/importance-of-feed-withdrawal-and-the-loading-process-to-the-poultry-industry-wattagnet>

SUMMARY

9.4 Informative summaries

1. Flock Thinning to Be Banned on RSPCA Assured Farms

The RSPCA said that the new rules could also be beneficial to consumers, after a study by the European Food Safety Authority reported that thinning is linked to increased rates of campylobacter in chickens. The thinning process involves rearing the birds to the maximum stocking density permitted and then removing a proportion of them to lower the density. This can take place several times before all the birds are finally removed from the shed. The animal welfare organisation said that thinning can be a stressful experience for the birds as their feed is removed to allow catching teams to round-up the birds more easily. The RSPCA added that the temperature inside the shed can also drop, particularly during the winter, as teams of catchers enter. From January 1 2016 farmers rearing to RSPCA welfare standards under the RSPCA Assured label will not be permitted to thin their flocks.

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2. European Chicken Commitment (and thinning)

The criteria defined in the European Chicken Commitment are considerably more stringent than those required by animal welfare law and also the standards of the wide-spread German »Initiative Tierwohl« (Animal Welfare Initiative), according to which a proportion of the meat sold in supermarkets and discounter chains is sold. This article highlights some main differences in criteria. One criteria is on thinning. Thinning describes the process whereby a proportion of chickens are removed from a shed for slaughter earlier than the rest. This causes considerable stress both for the captured chickens and for those that remain in the shed. This method is used for increasing the number of animals that can be fattened in a shed. While the European Chicken Commitment calls for an end to thinning, it does permit it a maximum of once in each fattening cycle. The companies are required to implement the criteria in full by 2026 at the latest, although we do expect German companies to implement the criteria more quickly. We chose the year 2026 to make the deadline more realistic for southern and eastern European countries, where animal welfare standards generally lag behind.

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3. Pre-Processing Handling in Broilers

Pre-processing bird management can have a significant impact on bird welfare, food safety, and profitability. It is important to achieve a clear understanding of how to manage birds during the 24 hours prior to processing through: 1) Applying good feed withdrawal practices to prevent fecal contamination at the processing plant and minimize the effects of pre-

processing weight loss. 2) Catching should be done with care to avoid injury and also quickly and efficiently, to minimize the time taken to transport the birds to the processing plant. 3) Transport vehicles must provide birds with the appropriate protection and ventilation to minimize stress. 4) Holding time at the processing plant should be kept to a minimum and proper environmental control in the holding area is critical. All stages of pre-processing management should be monitored and reviewed regularly to ensure it remains efficient while maintaining bird welfare. Following the guidelines described in this article can help achieve a successful transition from farm to processing plant, maximizing bird welfare, carcass quality, and flock profitability

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4. Economic consequences of stopping 'thinning' in broiler production

Retail chicken prices would have to rise to compensate stopping partial depopulation of broiler flocks. Flock 'thinning' is often used in broiler production to optimise the use of farm space and rear a larger number of birds while still respecting the EU regulations that set the maximum stocking density in a house at 42 kg/square metre. While performing partial depopulation, the maximum density allowed by law is reached faster, and a part of the flock is sent for slaughter earlier while the remaining animals continue until the end of the production round. But the practice does constitute a serious break in farm biosecurity that can lead to the introduction of various pathogens in the flock, including *Campylobacter spp.* Partial depopulation is stressful to the broilers that are deprived of food and water several hours before the arrival of the catching crew. Researchers from the University of Ghent, Belgium, looked at whether depopulating flocks could increase the risk of the introduction of *Campylobacter spp.* in the poultry house. A simulation was performed to evaluate production consequences of 'thinning'. In this article the results are summarized.

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5. All in – all out: no thinning

The Finnish national production method, All in–All out: No thinning, includes the fact that all chicks are delivered to the rearing farm at once and the entire flock is also sent to be slaughtered at the same time. The broiler houses are emptied, washed, dried and disinfected carefully between breeding batches. The method is a requirement for ensuring biosecurity, it improves food safety (prevents the spread of campylobacter and salmonella) and reduces stress and injuries among the broiler chickens, as fasting and loading only occurs once during their life. With this method disease pressure is lower, the birds are doing better and are healthier.

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6. Global Broiler Chicken Certification Schemes Comparison Table

This comprehensive table outlines how different global and regional legislation and certification schemes for broiler chickens align with the European Chicken Commitment (ECC) and the Better Chicken Commitment for the United States and Canada (BCC). This includes an overview of their criteria on thinning (i.e. whether no more than 1 thin per flock is allowed).

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7. Broiler production with reduced antibiotics. The essentials

This article discusses experience-based insights and practical advice concerning best practices for broiler meat production with reduced antibiotic use, focusing on the following points. If thinning (partial depopulation) is practiced, it should be done with the highest biosecurity measures. Producers must ensure that the equipment used in the catching process

is thoroughly cleaned before entering the house, and bird-catching personnel takes the same measures as farm personnel when entering the farm and the house. These policies will help to minimize the introduction of infectious agents. Keep the feed withdrawal period for this process as short as possible to avoid flightiness, which can induce skin lesions (some regions catch birds in low light intensities to avoid flightiness). A short feed withdrawal period also prevents over-consumption of feed in a short amount of time, possibly disrupting feed passage in the gut and leading to bacterial imbalance and dysbacteriosis in the remaining birds. After thinning, feed and temperature must be adapted to the lower number of animals.

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8. Zoonotic diseases, human health, and farm animal welfare: Campylobacter

Compassion in World Farming and the World Society for the Protection of Animals are sharing a report written by Professor T. Humphrey from the National Centre for Zoonosis Research at the University of Liverpool on Campylobacter. Thinning is an important risk factor for the spread of and/or infection with Campylobacter. This report lists the sources and consequences of this bacteria.

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9. Economic consequences of stopping 'thinning' in broiler production

The researchers said for current conventional broiler production, it may be financially challenging to stop partial depopulation practices. Instead, focusing on external biosecurity to avoid the introduction of Campylobacter into poultry houses may be the right compromise.

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10. Importance of feed withdrawal and the loading process to the poultry industry

Chicken processing age and weight vary from country to country, ranging from 4 weeks to 10 weeks and weights anywhere from 4 lbs to 7 lbs. However, to obtain the lowest production cost and highest yield, flock uniformity should factor into the processing schedule. Once birds achieve the processing targets, there are multiple factors that can significantly impact carcass quality, and a key part of producing high-quality products involves implementing a solid feed withdrawal program.

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Chapter 10 Slower growing broilers

10.1 List of scientific knowledge sources

1. In pursuit of a better broiler: tibial morphology, breaking strength, and ash content in conventional and slower-growing strains of broiler chickens

Reference Santos, M.N.; Widowski, T.M.; Kiarie, E.G.; Guerin, M.T.; Edwards, A.M.; Torrey, S. 2022. Poult. Sci., 101(4), 101755. DOI: [10.1016/j.psj.2022.101755](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2022.101755)

[ABSTRACT](#)

2. Are Dual-Purpose Chickens Twice as Good? Measuring Performance and Animal Welfare throughout the Fattening Period

Tiemann, I.; Hillemacher, S.; Wittmann, M. Animals, 10(11), 1980. DOI: [10.3390/ani10111980](https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10111980)

[ABSTRACT](#)

3. Slow-growing broilers are healthier and express more behavioural indicators of positive welfare

Rayner, A.C.; Newberry, R.C.; Vas, J.; Mullan, S. 2020. Sci. Rep., 10(1), 15151. DOI: [10.1038/s41598-020-72198-x](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-72198-x)

[ABSTRACT](#)

4. Behaviour in one fast-growing and one slower-growing broiler (Gallus gallus domesticus) hybrid fed a high- or low-protein diet during a 10-week rearing period

Wallenbeck, A.; Wilhelmsson, S.; Jönsson, L.; Gunnarsson, S.; Yngvesson, J. 2016. Acta Agric. Scand. - A: Anim. Sci. 66(3), 168-176. DOI: [10.1080/09064702.2017.1303081](https://doi.org/10.1080/09064702.2017.1303081)

[ABSTRACT](#)

5. Associations between behaviour and health outcomes in conventional and slow-growing breeds of broiler chicken

Abeyesinghe, S.M.; Chancellor, N.M.; Hernandez Moore, D.; Chang, Y-M; Pearce, J.; Demmers, T.; Nicol, C. J. 2021. Animal, 15(7), 100261. DOI: [10.1016/j.animal.2021.100261](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.animal.2021.100261)

[ABSTRACT](#)

6. In pursuit of a better broiler: growth, efficiency, and mortality of 16 strains of broiler chickens

Torrey, S.; Mohammadigheisar, M.; dos Santos, M.N.; Rothschild, D.; Dawson, L.C.; Liu, Z.Z.; Kiarie, E.G.; Edwards, am; Mandell, I.; Karrow, N.; Tulpan, D.; Widowski, T.M. 2021. Poult. Sci. 100(3). 100955. DOI: [10.1016/j.psj.2020.12.052](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2020.12.052)

[ABSTRACT](#)

7. Evaluating broiler welfare and behavior as affected by growth rate and stocking density

Zhou, S., Watcharaanantapong, P., Yang, X., Thornton, T., Gan, H., Tabler, T., Prado, M., Zhao, Y. 2024. Poult. Sci. 103(4), 103459. DOI: [10.1016/j.psj.2024.103459](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2024.103459)

[ABSTRACT](#)

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8. **Slow and steady wins the race: The behaviour and welfare of commercial faster growing broiler breeds compared to a commercial slower growing breed**

Dixon, L.M. 2020. PLoS one, 15(4), e0231006. DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0231006](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0231006)

[ABSTRACT](#)

9. **In pursuit of a better broiler: a comparison of the inactivity, behavior, and enrichment use of fast- and slower growing broiler chickens**

Reference with linked DOI Dawson, L.C., Widowski, T.M., Liu, Z., Edwards, A.M., Torrey, S. 2021. Poult. Sci. 100(12), 101451. DOI: [10.1016/j.psj.2021.101451](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2021.101451)

[ABSTRACT](#)

10. **Broiler flocks in production systems with slower-growing breeds and reduced stocking density receive fewer antibiotic treatments and have lower mortality**

Slegers, Y.; Hostens, M.; Matthijs, M G.R.; Stegeman, J.A.; Wit, J.J. de. 2024. Poult. Sci., 103(11), 104197. DOI: [10.1016/j.psj.2024.104197](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2024.104197)

[ABSTRACT](#)

10.2 Informative abstracts

1. **In pursuit of a better broiler: tibial morphology, breaking strength, and ash content in conventional and slower-growing strains of broiler chickens**

This study was conducted to determine the differences in bone traits in 14 strains of broiler chickens differing in growth rate. The strains encompassed 2 conventional (CONV; ADG0-48 >60 g/d) and 12 slower-growing (SG) strains classified as FAST (ADG0-62 = 53–55 g/d), MOD (ADG0-62 = 50–51 g/d), and SLOW (ADG0-62 <50 g/d), with 4 strains represented in each SG category. A total of 7,216 mixed-sex birds were equally allocated into 164 pens (44 birds/pen; 30 kg/m²) in a randomized incomplete block design, with each strain represented in 8 to 12 pens over 2–3 trials. From each pen, 4 birds (2 males and 2 females) were individually weighed and euthanized at 2 target weights (TWs) according to their time to reach approximately 2.1 kg (TW1: 34 d for CONV and 48 d for SG strains) and 3.2 kg (TW2: 48 d for CONV and 62 d for SG strains). Tibiae samples were dissected, and length and diameter were recorded. Left tibiae were used for tibial breaking strength (TBS) at both TWs and tibial ash at TW2. At TW1, CONV birds' tibiae were narrowest and shortest ($P < 0.001$), yet had similar TBS compared to the other categories ($P > 0.69$). At TW2, category ($P > 0.50$) had no effect on tibial diameter, yet CONV birds had the shortest tibiae ($P < 0.001$). The CONV birds had greater TBS:BW ratio than FAST and MOD birds at both TWs 1 and 2 ($P < 0.039$) and similar ash content as the other categories at TW2 ($P > 0.220$). At 48 d of age, CONV birds had the greatest absolute TBS ($P < 0.003$), yet lower TBS:BW ratio than SLOW birds ($P < 0.001$). Tibiae from CONV birds were longer than MOD and SLOW birds, and thicker in diameter than the other categories, yet CONV birds had the lowest dimensions relative to BW ($P < 0.001$) at 48 d, indicating a negative association between accelerated growth and tibial dimensions. These results indicate that differences in functional abilities among categories may be due to differences in morphometric traits rather than differences in bone strength and mineralization.

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2. **Are Dual-Purpose Chickens Twice as Good? Measuring Performance and Animal Welfare throughout the Fattening Period**

Chickens are the world's most widely used farm animal and have a significant genetic diversity. In the current study, we investigated three strains for their suitability as dual-purpose chickens, with a focus on the fattening ability and welfare of the cockerels: 1. layer

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cockerels (Lohmann Brown, LB, n = 714); 2. cockerels of a dual-purpose hybrid (Lohmann Dual, LD, n = 844); and 3. cockerels of a native breed (Rhineland, RL, n = 458). Chicks were raised under identical conditions and marked individually to compare focus and random sampling methods for weighing birds weekly. Because chicks of dual-purpose origins are usually raised mixed-sex, cockerels and pullets were weighed and observed together until sexes were identifiable at week 10 of their life. During the 10th to 20th week of life, investigations were continued on 100 cockerels per genotype. Key figures for growth performance, such as feed conversion ratio (FCR) and European production efficiency factor (EPEF), were also calculated at weekly intervals. LD cockerels showed considerable growth performance ($p < 0.001$ compared to LB, RL, 2 kg at 9 weeks), whereas LB reached a live weight of 2 kg at 13 weeks and RL at 15 weeks of age. Genotype-dependent differences were also evident, with favorable FCR and EPEF for LD, intermediate for LB, and unfavorable for RL (all $p < 0.001$). The results of the FCR and EPEF suggest that cockerels should be slaughtered around week 8 of life, although only the carcass of the LD might be marketable. Thus, the optimal time of slaughter based on production parameters such as FCR and EPEF is different from the time when the animal reaches a marketable 2 kg live weight. Animal-based welfare indicators revealed that the RL are not adapted to production environments, including those that are extensive. Further research aimed at adapted feed management, including better FCR, and animals adapted to the respective production environments is necessary to improve alternative poultry production in the future.

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3. Slow-growing broilers are healthier and express more behavioural indicators of positive welfare

Broiler chicken welfare is under increasing scrutiny due to welfare concerns regarding growth rate and stocking density. This farm-based study explored broiler welfare in four conditions representing commercial systems varying in breed and planned maximum stocking density: (1) Breed A, 30 kg/m²; (2) Breed B, 30 kg/m²; (3) Breed B, 34 kg/m²; (4) Breed C, 34 kg/m². Breeds A and B were 'slow-growing' breeds (< 50 g/day), and Breed C was a widely used 'fast-growing' breed. Indicators of negative welfare, behavioural indicators of positive welfare and environmental outcomes were assessed. Clear differences between conditions were detected. Birds in Condition 4 experienced the poorest health (highest mortality and post-mortem inspection rejections, poorest walking ability, most hock burn and pododermatitis) and litter quality. These birds also displayed lower levels of behaviours indicative of positive welfare (enrichment bale occupation, qualitative 'happy/active' scores, play, ground-scratching) than birds in Conditions 1–3. These findings provide farm-based evidence that significant welfare improvement can be achieved by utilising slow-growing breeds. There are suggested welfare benefits of a slightly lower planned maximum stocking density for Breed B and further health benefits of the slowest-growing breed, although these interventions do not offer the same magnitude of welfare improvement as moving away from fast-growing broilers.

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4. Behaviour in one fast-growing and one slower-growing broiler (*Gallus gallus domesticus*) hybrid fed a high- or low-protein diet during a 10-week rearing period

This study compared behavioural time budgets, presence of comfort behaviours and social behaviours in two different broiler genotypes (the fast-growing Ross 308 (R) and the slower-growing Rowan Ranger (RR)) fed organic diets with high (17.0% crude protein (CP)) or low (14.5% CP) protein content during a 10-week rearing period. 429-day-old chicks (218 R and 211 RR, respectively) were included in the study and behaviour was recorded at 2, 6 and 9 weeks of age. The results showed no effect of diet treatments but that R broilers were less active and sat, ate and drank more frequently than RR broilers, which stood and perched more frequently. However, both hybrids showed decreasing activity and foraging behaviour

with increasing age, while time spent eating and sleeping was approximately similar over the entire rearing period.

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5. **Associations between behaviour and health outcomes in conventional and slow-growing breeds of broiler chicken**

Broiler chickens are prone to a range of complex health and welfare issues. To support informed selection of welfare traits whilst minimising impact on production efficiency and to address a major gap in understanding, we systematically explored associations between health and behavioural indicators of broiler welfare. One conventional (CNV, n = 350) and two slow-growing broiler breeds (SGH and SGN, respectively n = 400) were reared from hatch in pens of 50 birds. Birds were assessed for health (gait, plumage cover and dirtiness, pododermatitis, hockburn, and leg deviations) at 2.2 kg liveweight according to the Royal Society for the Prevention of Cruelty to Animals Broiler Breed Welfare Assessment Protocol. Behaviour and resource-use of 10% of birds per pen, on days 29 (all breeds) and 43 (SGH and SGN), was (i) scan sampled every 60 min between three to six and between twelve to fifteen hours after photoperiod onset; and (ii) continuously sampled sequentially from focal birds for 3 min each in a random order, during 15 min observation periods at three and twelve hours after photoperiod onset. Binary logistic generalized linear models were used, to assess respective associations between pen prevalence of each health outcome and (i) pen mean percentage scans of behaviour, and (ii) pen mean frequency and duration per 3 min focal observation of behaviour. Better growth rate and feed conversion but poorer health outcomes (mortality, gait, pododermatitis, feather cover) were more prevalent in CNV. Strong associations between behaviour and several health indicators revealed, (i) increases in side-lying inactive, sitting inactive, and use of the litter relative to other resources, as primary and general indicators of poorer health, and (ii) increases in standing inactive, perch use, walking, Comfort, High Energy and Exploratory behaviour as primary and general indicators of better health. Of these, changes in side-lying, standing inactive, walking, Comfort and High Energy behaviour were particularly sensitive to small differences in health outcomes important for breed acceptance in high-welfare schemes. Crucially these behavioural measures additionally represent motivational and affective aspects of welfare not captured by health measures and allow opportunity for earlier intervention. Thus, to provide a comprehensive assessment of broiler experience, behaviour should be incorporated into broiler welfare assessments.

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6. **In pursuit of a better broiler: growth, efficiency, and mortality of 16 strains of broiler chickens**

To meet the growing consumer demand for chicken meat, the poultry industry has selected broiler chickens for increasing efficiency and breast yield. While this high productivity means affordable and consistent product, it has come at a cost to broiler welfare. There has been increasing advocacy and consumer pressure on primary breeders, producers, processors, and retailers to improve the welfare of the billions of chickens processed annually. Several small-scale studies have reported better welfare outcomes for slower-growing strains compared to fast-growing, conventional strains. However, these studies often housed birds with range access or used strains with vastly different growth rates. Additionally, there may be traits other than growth, such as body conformation, that influence welfare. As the global poultry industries consider the implications of using slower growing strains, there was a need for a comprehensive, multidisciplinary examination of broiler chickens with a wide range of genotypes differing in growth rate and other phenotypic traits. To meet this need, our team designed a study to benchmark data on conventional and slower-growing strains of broiler chickens reared in standardized laboratory conditions. Over a 2-year period, we studied 7,528 broilers from 16 different genetic strains. In this paper, we compare the growth, efficiency, and mortality of broilers to one of two target weights (TW): 2.1 kg (TW1) and 3.2

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kg (TW2). We categorized strains by their growth rate to TW2 as conventional (CONV), fastest-slow strains (FAST), moderate-slow strains (MOD), and slowest-slow strains (SLOW). When incubated, hatched, housed, managed, and fed the same, the categories of strains differed in body weights, growth rates, feed intake, and feed efficiency. At 48 d of age, strains in the CONV category were 835 to 1,264 g heavier than strains in the other categories. By TW2, differences in body weights and feed intake resulted in a 22 to 43-point difference in feed conversion ratios. Categories of strains did not differ in their overall mortality rates.

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7. **Evaluating broiler welfare and behavior as affected by growth rate and stocking density**

This study evaluated the welfare and behaviors of Cobb 700 broilers as affected by growth rate (GR) and stocking density (SD). Slower-growth (weight gain < 50 g/d) and medium-growth (weight gain = 50–60 g/d) broilers were produced by providing 57.1% and 78.6% of the feed intake listed in the Cobb 700 production manual for standard (fed ad libitum) broilers (weight gain > 60 g/d). Broilers at all 3 GRs were reared at 2 SDs of 30 and 40 kg/m². Broiler welfare indicators, including gait score, tibia strength, feather coverage, and footpad condition were evaluated when birds reached 1, 2, and 3 kg of body weight. The activity index was determined by overhead cameras and image processing, and the time spent at feeders was recorded using the radio-frequency identification (RFID) systems. The results show that it took 45 d for standard, 52 d for medium-growth, and 62 d for slower-growth broilers to reach a 3 kg market body weight. Feed conversion ratios (FCR, kg/kg) were 1.57 for standard, 1.67 for medium-growth, and 1.80 for slower-growth broilers. Growth rate and SD had an interaction effect on feather cleanliness ($P = 0.03$), and belly feather coverage ($P = 0.02$). Slower-growth broilers were more active and had better feather coverage and gait scores than medium-growth and standard broilers (all $P < 0.01$) but may feel hungry and depressed, medium-growth broilers spent the most time at the feeder among the 3 growth groups ($P = 0.02$), and standard broilers showed the best production performance. Broilers at 30 kg/m² showed better bone strength ($P = 0.04$), and footpad condition ($P < 0.01$) compared to those at 40 kg/m². In conclusion, reducing GR and SD may slightly improve broiler leg health at the high expense of compromised production performance and prolonged production cycles.

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8. **Slow and steady wins the race: The behaviour and welfare of commercial faster growing broiler breeds compared to a commercial slower growing breed**

Broilers have been bred for fast growth which has led to welfare problems such as high mortality, lameness and skin lesions. Slower growing breeds are thought to have better welfare but are not as efficient in production. This study investigated welfare, behaviour, production and meat quality of faster growing broilers from three main commercial broiler companies (breeds FA, FB and FC) with a commercially available slower growing breed (Hubbard JA757, S). Four hundred birds of each breed (total 1600 birds) were reared in pens of 50 birds, 8 per breed (total 32 pens). Home pen behaviour was recorded once a week in hourly scan samples to get behavioural time budgets. Welfare Assessments (WA) were done when the average bird weight per breed was 2.2 and 2.5kg. Birds and feed supplied were regularly weighed by pen and Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR) and Average Daily Gain (ADG) were calculated at 2.2kg. Birds were then slaughtered and meat quality measures were taken. S and FC had lower mortality and culls due to lameness ($P < 0.05$ for both). Breeds FA, FB and FC grew faster, ate less feed and had better FCR and ADG ($P < 0.05$ for all). S had scores indicating higher welfare for the majority of WA measures and spent more time active and less time sitting, feeding and drinking than the other breeds ($P < 0.05$ for all). Faster growing breeds had more breast meat and S had more leg meat; although S had better meat quality scores ($P < 0.05$). Overall, S birds have improved welfare in terms of activity and welfare measure scores compared to the other breeds but

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take longer to reach slaughter weight and are not as efficient in production measures. However, if lower mortality and improved meat quality are taken into account, as well as the premium price paid for these birds, slower growing broilers may be a viable commercial option.

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9. In pursuit of a better broiler: a comparison of the inactivity, behavior, and enrichment use of fast- and slower growing broiler chickens

Selection for rapid growth has produced heavier, more efficient broiler chickens, but has also introduced health and welfare issues, which may cause or be caused by inactivity. Rapid growth may also limit the performance of motivated behaviors, whereas the provision of enrichment may increase these behaviors and general activity. This study aimed to evaluate the inactivity, behavior patterns, and enrichment use of 2 fast- (CONV) and 12 slower growing broiler strains (categorized as fastest [FAST], moderate [MOD], and slowest [SLOW]), based on their growth rates; 4 strains/category]. To evaluate inactivity, one male and one female from 153 pens were outfitted with omni-directional accelerometers from d 21 until processing (14-24 birds/strain from 8 to 12 pens/strain). Additionally, to supplement inactivity data, 5-min continuous behavioral observations of four focal birds per pen (2 males, 2 females) were conducted on days 26, 42, and 56 (72-148 observations of 8-12 pens/strain) to quantify the duration and frequency of various behaviors; at the same time, 5 to 11 instantaneous scan samples were also performed for pen-based enrichment use. Inactivity peaked at 78 to 80% of the day for all strains; however, those with slower growth rates reached these levels at older ages. Compared to slower growing strains at the same age, faster growing strains were more inactive, spent more time sitting and feeding, spent less time standing and walking, and used enrichments less; these differences mostly occurred at younger ages. Generally, at the same age, strains with similar growth rates (within the same category) behaved similarly, with only a few exceptions. Results suggest that not all strains identified as "slow-growing" broilers behave differently from fast-growing broilers, nor do they all behave similarly to each other. As such, results suggest that improved broiler welfare, particularly with respect to reduced inactivity, the performance of a wider range of normal, motivated behaviors, and/or increased enrichment use, is related to the broiler strain's specific growth rate.

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10. Broiler flocks in production systems with slower-growing breeds and reduced stocking density receive fewer antibiotic treatments and have lower mortality

In the Netherlands, the number of broiler production systems with higher welfare standards, using slower-growing broilers and decreased stocking densities, has increased over the last decade. This study aimed to investigate the effect of this change on antibiotic treatments, mortality, and footpad lesions. Data from national monitoring databases from 2013 to 2021 were used, resulting in 113,380 included flocks from 917 farms. Flocks were divided into conventional (CONV), medium-growing (MED), and slow-growing (SLOW), based on breed and slaughter age (median age: CONV 42 d; MED 50 d; SLOW 56 d). Generalized mixed-effect models were created to compare antibiotic treatments in and after the first week, total on-farm mortality, and footpad lesion scores between these 3 production systems. Year, quarter, flock size, thinning, number of houses, and regional density of poultry farms were included as fixed effects. Random effects were farm and veterinary practice in all models, with an additional random slaughterhouse effect to describe footpad lesions. Probability of treatment in the first week of age in CONV flocks overall years (7.2%, 95% CI [5.9, 8.7]) was higher than in MED (2.0%, 95% CI [1.6, 2.5]) and SLOW flocks (1.3%, 95% CI [1.0, 1.7]). Treatment probability after the first week was similarly higher in CONV flocks (14.7%, 95% CI [12.1, 17.6]) than in MED (3.2%, 95% CI [2.5, 4.0]) and SLOW flocks (2.2%, 95% CI [1.7, 2.9]). CONV flocks had a higher mean mortality (3.2%, 95% CI [3.0, 3.4]) than MED (2.0%, 95% CI [1.9, 2.1]) and SLOW flocks (1.9%, 95% CI [1.8, 2.0]). Regarding

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footpad lesions, CONV flocks had the highest mean scores (range 0-200) over all years, whereas SLOW flocks had the lowest scores (CONV: 46.1, 95% CI [42.1, 50.6]; MED: 21.3, 95% CI [18.9, 24.0]; SLOW: 13.2, 95% CI [11.5, 15.1]). This analysis of data from flocks over a 9-yr period indicates that switching from conventional to alternative production systems with higher welfare standards could positively affect broiler health and antibiotic use.

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10.3 List of practical knowledge sources

1. Economics of slow growing broilers

Wageningen University & Research. 2022.

https://www.eurogroupforanimals.org/files/eurogroupforanimals/2023-03/Wageningen%20UR%20-%20Factsheet%20Economic%20analysis%20of%20ECC-21dec2022_FINAL%20%281%29.pdf

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2. Market trends: slow-growing breeds and the impact on efficiency

The Poultry Site. 2022. <https://www.thepoultrysite.com/articles/market-trends-slow-growing-breeds-and-the-impact-on-efficiency>

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3. In research and reality slower-growing birds costs more

WATT Poultry. 2019. <https://www.wattagnet.com/broilers-turkeys/article/15528729/in-research-and-reality-slower-growing-birds-costs-more-wattagnet>

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4. Paving the way for higher welfare broiler breeds in the EU: from market initiatives to legislation

EuroGroup for Animals. 2024. <https://www.eurogroupforanimals.org/library/paving-way-higher-welfare-broiler-breeds-eu-market-initiatives-legislation>

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5. The Impact of Breed on Broiler Welfare

Compassion in World Farming. 2023.

<https://www.compassioninfoodbusiness.com/media/7455399/the-impact-of-breed-on-broiler-welfare-2023.pdf>

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6. Adopting slower-growing breeds of chicken would reduce animal suffering significantly

Our World in Data. 2023. <https://ourworldindata.org/adopting-slower-growing-breeds-of-chicken-would-reduce-animal-suffering-significantly>

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7. Ready, steady, slow! Slow-growing broilers are healthier and have more positive welfare

Business Wales. 2022. <https://businesswales.gov.wales/farmingconnect/news-and-events/technical-articles/ready-steady-slow-slow-growing-broilers-are-healthier-and-have-more-positive-welfare>

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8. Do slow growing meat chickens have better welfare than fast growing meat chickens?

RSPCA. 2024. <https://kb.rspca.org.au/knowledge-base/do-slow-growing-meat-chickens-have-better-welfare-than-fast-growing-meat-chickens/>

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9. Impact of the Better Chicken Commitment and the adoption of slower-growing breeds on the welfare of broiler chickens

Welfare Footprint Institute. 2022. <https://welfarefootprint.org/broilers/>

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10. Slower growing broiler breeds

mEAT quality. 2025. <https://meatquality.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/1-Slow-growing-broiler-breeds.pdf>

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10.4 Informative summaries

1. Economics of slow growing broilers

Since 2018, more than 200 food companies across Europe committed to the European Chicken Commitment (ECC). These companies will raise their animal welfare standards to the requirements of the ECC by 2026. The Eurogroup for Animals commissioned a project to Wageningen University & Research to obtain insight in the costs of transitioning to broiler production systems that comply with these requirements in various EU member states. This project includes the following tasks: 1) Provide a build-up of the production costs (feed costs, other variable costs, housing costs etc.) for conventional broiler production systems and the ECC system without and with thinning. 2) Calculate production costs of conventional broiler production systems and estimate the slaughter costs in selected EU countries for 2021. 3) Calculate production costs of broilers reared in the ECC system and estimate the slaughter costs in selected EU countries for 2021. The following six EU countries will be included in the study: the Netherlands, Poland, Germany, Italy, Spain and France.

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2. Market trends: slow-growing breeds and the impact on efficiency

Some poultry farms have switched to slow-growing broilers. Why? Will the whole sector follow soon? Frank Hartmann has analyzed the trend and summarizes the results. In this article, we discuss the switch to slow-growing chicken breeds and the impact this has. Moving towards alternative breeds has a negative impact on our environmental footprint. So, how can we mitigate this? New, smart technologies may offer a solution to the problem of efficiency. The key to this will be collecting and processing data, so you can learn from it and make better decisions — at individual poultry companies, but also in the entire poultry processing industry. Therefore, the next phase of the transition can't be far off.

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3. In research and reality slower-growing birds costs more

The U.S. broiler industry faces a sizeable challenge in a potential widescale transition to slower growing broiler genetics. A widespread switch to slower-growing broiler genetics

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would require the chicken industry to use far more resources, and charge significantly higher prices, to produce the same amount of meat. This article looks into the potential impacts of introducing slower growing broiler breeds into the US broiler industry including some real-world examples describing the higher economic costs.

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4. **Paving the way for higher welfare broiler breeds in the EU: from market initiatives to legislation**

In order to achieve higher animal welfare in the broiler farming industry, 'fast-growing' broiler breeds must be phased out, and only higher welfare, slower-growing breeds should be permitted to be farmed under EU law. In this white paper, we dive into how different European countries have been approaching a shift to farming slower-growing broiler breeds, and explore existing market initiatives geared at improving broiler welfare, including the European Chicken Commitment. We also provide clear and comprehensive suggestions for the paths policy-makers could take to legislate on higher welfare breeds, and present three different options: the most protective and preferred option (which provides an adaptable, positive list of breeds authorised for farming), the intermediary option (which would be to establish a negative list of breeds forbidden to be farmed), and the option with the lowest protection (which would be to include an average daily weight gain threshold in the legislation, above which breeds could not be approved to be farmed).

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5. **The impact of breed on broiler welfare**

Most of the modern broiler breeds are the result of decades of genetic selection mainly for fast growth, higher breast yield, leaner meat and lower Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR). This intense selection for performance traits has had negative repercussions on the health and welfare of the birds. Fast-growing birds have a high basal metabolic rate, and a high energy demand which can create oxygen deficits. This results in a high incidence of heart and pulmonary conditions, ascites, and even sudden death. Fast-growing broilers are also prone to leg and foot disorders. These conditions influence their gait score and general activity, causing a poor walking ability, reduced access to feed and water, pain, and inability to perform natural behaviours. Additionally, there is also abundant evidence regarding the prevalence of breast muscle myopathies and skin lesions related to fast growth and high breast yield. Those painful conditions, added to the inability to perform highly motivated behaviours, often result in chronic stress, which is well known to have a negative effect on the immune system, leading to immunosuppression and an increased vulnerability to disease. Consequently, antibiotic use is significantly higher in fast-growing broilers compared to slower-growing ones (e.g. antibiotic use in Dutch farms using fast-growing broiler breeds was 9 times higher than on farms using slower-growing breeds in 2022). Therefore, using slower-growing breeds with better health and stronger immune systems can significantly contribute to the reduction of antibiotic use in broiler production. Fast-growing broilers, due to their body conformation and poor health, have difficulties to express natural behaviours such as perching, preening, or exploring. This often translates in an increase in the percentage of time that the birds spend inactive and has a negative effect on their mental welfare. Slower-growing breeds demonstrate a better response to stress than fast-growing ones, are more active and display a larger range of natural behaviours, resulting in a better mental wellbeing overall. Scientists and animal welfare organizations are calling for the phase out of fast-growing breeds in favour of slower-growing strains selected for better health and welfare outcomes. By signing up to the European Chicken Commitment, companies commit to adopt slower growing breeds with improved welfare outcomes, offering consumers a higher quality product from healthier, happier chicken.

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6. Adopting slower-growing breeds of chicken would reduce animal suffering significantly

Fast growth rates result in significant pain and suffering for chickens. Selecting slower-growing breeds would reduce some of this suffering. Every year, almost ten chickens are slaughtered for every person on Earth. We raise and kill around 74 billion every year. That's more than ten times the number in 1960 and almost twice as many as in 2000. Part of this rise has come from gains in the 'efficiency' of chicken production. Chickens today are much bigger than in the past, and are much more efficient at converting feed into meat. This push for increased efficiency has increased the time and intensity each chicken spends in pain. This article looks at estimates of pain duration in fast-growing chicken breeds. The research shows that even opting for slightly slower-growing breeds – that reach the same final weight – would provide large welfare benefits.

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7. Ready, steady, slow! Slow-growing broilers are healthier and have more positive welfare

Selection for increased feed efficiency and muscle deposition has resulted in a number of health and welfare concerns in fast-growing broilers. Although the welfare of these birds can be improved by good husbandry practices and at lower stocking densities, it cannot eliminate the issues, especially those associated with rapid growth rates. Slow-growing broilers offer a solution to the health and welfare issues of these fast growers. Additionally, they express more natural behaviours and are more resilient to infections. Slow growing broilers consume more time and resources to reach slaughter weight hence may not be an environmentally friendly option. A thorough detailed study of the environmental impact and carbon footprint of slow-growing broilers is needed before completely transitioning from fast-growing breeds. They also come at a premium cost to consumers hence their affordability by all sections of society is questionable.

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8. Do slow growing meat chickens have better welfare than fast growing meat chickens?

In Australia, the two predominant commercial breeds of meat chicken are conventional fast-growing breeds. These breeds have been selectively bred over time to rapidly gain muscle mass and reach slaughter weight at 4-5 weeks of age to meet production and consumer demands. Genetically selecting for fast growth has led to an increased risk of meat chickens having significant welfare concerns such as skeletal abnormalities, lameness, and metabolic diseases. The development of slow-growing meat chicken breeds aims to address these welfare concerns and these meat chickens gain muscle mass more slowly and reach slaughter weight at a later age.

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9. Impact of the Better Chicken Commitment and the adoption of slower-growing breeds on the welfare of broiler chickens

This article summarizes the results of the Cumulative Pain Framework - a novel analytical framework that enables establishing the welfare footprint of animal-sourced products and services - to quantify the loss of welfare endured by different animal species raised under multiple production conditions. In this case, the authors address commercial broiler production (chickens raised for their meat), widely recognized as one of the most serious animal welfare issues in the global agricultural sector. This article presents the first quantitative estimates of the time in pain chickens experience as a result of the challenges emerging from management and intensive genetic selection for traits desirable for fast and cheap meat production. The authors also investigate how adoption of the Better Chicken Commitment (a set of standards supported by a coalition of animal protection organizations)

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and similar welfare certification programs affect the welfare of broilers. Neglected and widely unknown issues by the public, such as chronic hunger in broiler breeder females and problems of substandard operation in different stunning systems, are also scrutinized under the objective metric (time in pain of different intensities) used in this framework.

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10. Slower growing broiler breeds

In conventional intensive broiler production, fast-growing breeds with a daily growth of 50 – 55 grams (g) are common. In the EU's organic regulation (EU 2018/848), fast-growing breeds have a minimum slaughter age of 81 days. So called "slow-growing" breeds are used in these systems, as normal breeds would become too big too early, which may result in major health issues. There is no common definition of slow-growing in the EU member states, but various slow-growing broiler breeds are available for various free-range systems. For free-range systems (organic and extensive label production), slow-growing breeds with a daily growth of 30 – 45 grams are preferred. Slow-growing breeds are recommended or obligatory in organic and extensive label production. Slow-growing birds seem to be healthier and seem to perform better in organic production than conventional fast-growing broilers. This practice abstracts lists some common breeds to use in practice, e.g. Hubbard JA 757, Hubbard JA 787, Hubbard Colouryield, Hubbard Naked Neck, Ranger Gold, Rowan Ranger, Sasso X44, Sasso T44, T44NI, Kabir as slow-growing breeds (30-45 g daily growth).

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